

D3.7

First periodic report on ongoing JRPs

WP3 Joint Research Projects

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Contributing partners: /

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D3.7 First periodic report on ongoing JRPs
WP and Task	WP3; Task 3.2
Leader	Sciensano
Other contributors	ANSES, SVA, WBVR, INSA
Due month of the deliverable	M13
Actual submission month	M14
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

First periodic report on ongoing JRP

Introduction

Joint Research Projects serve as an instrument that help OneHealth EJP partners to work together in developing new detection methods, improved diagnostic tests, fast and accurate typing methods, in gaining new insight in the spread of pathogens and their resistance traits etc. At the same time, through setting up these scientific collaborations, researchers spread over Europe identify new possible partners and strengthen links between known colleagues. As such, the JRP help in creating and consolidating a firm network of organizations that have reference tasks in their scope and that deal with foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

Summary of the performance of the Joint Research Projects

Project deliverables and milestones

The 11 joint research projects planned to submit a total of 77 deliverables. While most deliverables have been finalized at the end of 2018 (50 deliverables or 65%, see Table), only 32% of the deliverables have been uploaded to the private area of the OHEJP website. Probably, the project leaders are not yet familiar with using the private space. The WP3 team will further support them to ensure that the deliverables will be uploaded in due time.

About one-fifth of the expected deliverables have been postponed to the second year. The delays were mainly due to recruitment and leave of staff, delays in the availability of samples or equipment or to minor reorganization of the activities in agreement with the project consortium partners. These delays are unlikely to have a major impact on most projects. MoMIR-PPC however, faced the loss of expertise (Norwegian public health institute FHI), difficulties with co-funding (Bulgarian SAIM) and the reorganization in DTU (that saw DTU-Vet move to the Copenhagen university who is not a partner of the OneHealth EJP). These setbacks induced considerable delays in performing several tasks, resulting in modification of the work plan. Similarly, changes in the management of Tox-Detect, both at the level of the project leader and of a key task leader, made that strategic and operational responsibilities had to be re-allocated. Consequent loss of commitment of one partner needs to be corrected and appropriate actions have been proposed in January 2019.

About thirteen percent of the project deliverables will not result in a written document and should therefore be considered as milestones (NR category in table). To avoid this for the second call, the difference between milestones and deliverables will be better documented.

Deliverables	Total	Finalized submitted and on OHEJP website	Finalized but not yet submitted on OHEJP website	Delayed to 2019	NR (no report)
Number of Deliverables	77	25	25	17	10
Percentage	100	32	32	22	13

Of the 50 project deliverables reported as finalized (submitted or not) at the end of 2018, 6 were submitted late (estimated delay of 1 to 6 months) and having no major impact on the final outcome of the projects.

Deliverables	Total	Finalized submitted and on OHEJP website	Finalized but not yet submitted on OHEJP website	Delayed to 2019	NR (no report)
IMPART	9	3	0	2	4
ARDIG*	4	4	0	0	0
RaDAR	4	1	3	1	0
MAD-Vir	5	3	0	1	1
Tox-Detect*	3	0	2	1	0
NOVA*	10	10	0	0	0
LISTADAPT	10	0	7	3	0
METASTAVA	8	2	1	3	2
AIR Sample	2	2	0	0	0
MoMIR-PPC	11	0	5	4	2
MedVetKlebs	11	0	8	3	0
<i>Total</i>	<i>77</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>9</i>

Finally, the 11 joint research projects planned to achieve a total of 77 milestones. Seventy-three percent of the milestones were finalized while 27% have been delayed, again due to recruitment and departure of staff, delays in the delivery of samples / equipment or as agreed by project consortium partners.

Publications

Published

Project	DOI	ISSN	ISBN	Title
NOVA	10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1	1435-4373		Garrido-Esteba, M., Latasa, P., Ordóñez-León, G.Y. et al. <i>Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi Salmonella-related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, clinical aspects, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs.</i> Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis (2018).
NOVA	10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.24.1700503			Møller Frederik T, Mølbak Kåre, Ethelberg Steen. Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review. Euro Surveill. 2018;23(24):pii=1700503
LISTADAPT	10.3389/fmicb.2018.00684			Félix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M, Roussel S. Population Genetic Structure of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Strains Isolated From the Pig and Pork Production Chain in France. Front. Microbiol., 06 April 2018
MoMIR-PPC			2253-7244. 2018.	Moreno MA., Florez-Cuadrado D., Ugarte-Ruiz M. and Dominguez L Veterinarios y antibióticos: destinados a entenderse. Profesión Veterinaria. Asis, 2018
MoMIR-PPC	10.1016/bs.afnr.2018.04.004		9780128139776. 2018	Florez-Cuadrado D., Moreno MA., Ugarte-Ruiz M. and Dominguez L Antimicrobial Resistance in the Food Chain in the European Union. Advances in Food and Nutrition Research. Elsevier, 2018.
MoMIR-PPC	10.1111/1462-2920.14294			Menanteau P, Kempf F, Trotereau J, Virlogeux-Payant I, Guitton E, Dalifard J, Gabriel I, Rychlik I, and Velge P. (2018) Role of systemic infection, cross contaminations and super-shedders in <i>Salmonella</i> carrier state in chicken. Environmental Microbiology.
MedVetKlebs	10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000			Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Brisse S (2018). Identification of <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Klebsiella quasipneumoniae</i> , <i>Klebsiella variicola</i> and related phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry. Front. Microbiol. 9:3000

In preparation or submitted

Project	DOI	ISSN	ISBN	Title
MAD-Vir				Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, Fursted K, Nielsen HV, Andersen LOB, Bødker R, Fomsgaard A. Field samplings of (<i>Ixodus ricinus</i> ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV) micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark demonstrate an apparent disappearance of TBEV but a plenitude of other virus and bacteria. Submitted to Tick and Tick borne diseases 2018 (not yet published)
AIR-Sample				Giuliano Garofolo, Gro S. Johannessen, Ivana, Renata, Kinga, Jasek, Julia, Mona Torp, Jeffrey Hoorfar. <i>Campylobacter</i> in chicken houses – critical parameters for international, multicentre evaluation of sampling and detection methods. For submission to Food Control. (in preparation)

Integrative activities and impact of the research projects

Even if the principal objective of a research project is the delivery of high quality scientific outcome, most if not all JRP also comprise integrative activities, i.e. capacity building (including building expertise with ring trials and developing tools that are useful for risk analysis), experimental facilities, detection and typing methods, strains and biobanks collections, reference materials, digital infrastructures and databases, surveillance strategies and legal or policy aspects. An overview of such integrative activities per JRP is shown below.

	Capacity building, training + ring trial + tools for RA	Experimental facilities	Detection, typing methods, PRO	Strain collection, ref material	Digital infrastructure, DB	Surveillance strategies	Legal, Policy aspects
IMPART	X		X	X		X	X
ARDIG	X		X	X			X
RaDAR	X				X		
TOX-Detect	X		X				
MAD-VIR	X		X	X			
NOVA	X				X	X	
ListAdapt	X		X	X			
Metastava	X		X				
AIR Sample	X		X			X	X
MoMIR-PPC	X					X	
MedVetKlebs	X		X			X	

In all 11 JRP, training activities or the organization of ring trials are done. On the contrary, no specific experimental facilities (biosafety 2, 3 or 4 capacities for instance) were identified.

Detection and typing methods and the drafting of protocols are also well appreciated activities that can be shared and thus make partners collaborating. These are developed in the domains of antimicrobial resistance, for the detection and typing of various foodborne zoonoses, as well as for the detection of a broad range of viruses and of toxins produced by foodborne bacteria. Often, the creation of new or improved harmonized protocols, ring trials, etc. are based on a collection of well-defined strains or biobank samples and reference materials; these are often set up in the various JRP.

Also activities that may lead to improved surveillance strategies or better protocols for policy (risk assessment and risk management tools) are being developed. Examples are the specific surveillance of colistine resistance in *Enterobacteriaceae* and of resistance in *Clostridium difficile* (IMPART), the improved detection of *Campylobacter* in poultry houses (AIR-Sample) and the efficient detection of K. pneumonia in samples from various origins (MedVetKlebs).

Finally, two JRP set up databases for modelling of AMR transmission on farm and through the food chain (RaDAR) and for the exploitation of existing food purchase data in outbreak investigation and for syndromic surveillance (NOVA).

Interactions with other JRP/JIPs, European and national projects

Most of the Joint Research Projects (JRPs) collaborate with other European projects and some also have collaborations at national level (see figure blow).

In order to identify possible synergies and avoid overlap with major European projects, OHEJP WP4 Team (Joint Integrative Projects) organized two cogwheel workshops in 2018: one with COMPARE and one with EFFORT. The JRPs METASTAVA and IMPART participated in both cogwheel workshops, while ARDIG took part to the EFFORT Workshop.

Regarding COMPARE and EFFORT, the projects RaDAR and LISTADAPT have reported to use data generated by these projects.

Other interactions at the European level involve the H2020 project MEDILABSECURE (MAD-Vir), interactions between MoMIR-PPC and the former ERA-NET ANIHWA consortium concerning the

influence of gut microbiota composition and *Salmonella* infection on chicken behavior, and the participation of NOVA at several workshops and the annual meeting of COST ASF-STOP.

Besides interactions with European projects, METASTAVA also participated to workshops organized by the European Society for veterinary Virology and the European Society for clinical Virology.

At the national level, the project NOVA had several interactions with:

- VET+i: an interdisciplinary forum that integrates all relevant stakeholders from academia, research, farmers, veterinarians, industry, regulators, etc. interested in animal health
- A Swedish research project on Spatial modelling of VTEC/EHEC financed by the Swedish Research Council Formas.
- A national project on predicting the occurrence of AMR in Danish pig production when altering the AMU. 2018-2022 (founded by the Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark).
- The project “Evaluate and Establish Surveillance programs of Salmonella in imported and domestic Poultry Meat in Jordan”. 2016-2020 (founded by the Islamic Development Bank)

Finally, The MAD-Vir project collaborated with the Danish virology society while the MoMIR-PPC project presented a session at the CEMRACS Summer School, organized by the French Society of Applied and Industrial Mathematics (SMAI).

Critical risks

Three projects (ARDIG, AIR Sample and MedVetKlebs) did not mention any critical risks and three (RaDAR, MAD-Vir and NOVA) reported on some risk that will not have any consequences for the further progress of their activities. IMPART struggles with the provision of specific material, ListAdapt announces that an additional few months would be useful to fully exploit the mass of data that are gathered in the project and in addition informs that it will take action to improve the intra-project communication in 2019, and METASTAVA detailed that a limited delay in the work plan is expected, related to a replacement of senior laboratory expert and a change in management. The delays documented for TOX-Detect (change in management and lower than expected commitment of a partner with key expertise) and for MoMIR-PPC (reorganization of tasks and responsibilities due to loss of expertise or partners) on the other hand are likely to have a major impact on the respective deliveries. OneHealth EJP WP3 is in close contact with these consortia.

Critical Risks	IMPART	ARDIG	RaDAR	MAD-Vir	Tox-Detect	NOVA	LISTADAPT	METASTAVA	AIR SAMPLE	MoMIR-PPC	MedVetKlebs
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)			X		X	X		X		X	
Delay in work plan execution	X		X		X	X	X	X		X	
Conflicts within the consortium					X						
Lack of commitment of partners				X	X						
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting			X							X	
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship							X				
Potential entry/exit of partners										X	
Other risks (please describe)											

Green: Minor delays, other risks (conflicts, loss of key persons, ...) have been sorted out

Yellow: Delays & other risks don't have an impact on the project but should be followed up

Orange: Delays & other risks might have an impact on the project

Red: Delays & other risks will have a significant impact on the project

Reports of the JRP in the first round of projects

1. IMPART

1.1. Summary of the work carried out

A kick-off meeting for all consortium members of IMPART was organised on 20 February 2018 at Schiphol, Amsterdam. During this meeting, general information about EJP was provided, the results of a questionnaire were discussed and the initial plans for the different work packages (WP) were presented by the WP leaders and discussed in more detail afterwards.

Two separate pre-ring trials were organised for WP1 (Selective isolation, detection and characterization of colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae) and WP2 (Selective isolation, detection and characterization of carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae). The planning, sample preparation and distribution of the trials were done by ANSES Fougères. A small number of participants were involved (NVI, RIVM and WBVR) and all commercially available culture media were included. The pre-ring trial for WP1 consisted of caecal and meat samples of pigs and turkey spiked with different mcr-positive Enterobacteriaceae. The ring trial of WP2 consisted of caecal and meat samples of pigs spiked with different carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae. The samples for the pre-ring trial of WP2 were sent on 20 November 2018 and the samples for WP1 on 11 December 2018. The results of both ring trials will be evaluated in January 2019. Based on this, the set-up of the final ring trials will be designed and discussed with all consortium members.

For WP3 (Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)), information about the strain collection and antimicrobials were gathered using a questionnaire. During the kick-off meeting consensus was reached on the main stream of bacteria to be tested. Three concepts of different Sensititre plates were designed and shared with all consortium members by email. Feedback was received and the design of the plates was amended. Finally, the plates were ordered in July 2018. The plates were initially promised to be delivered to the Dutch distributor (MCS Diagnostics) in December 2018, but the delivery is postponed for several weeks. As a consequence, the distribution of the plates to the partners will take place in January or February 2019. For this reason the actual minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) testing will not start before the beginning of 2019.

In WP4 (Developing and optimizing a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*), a first draft protocol for disk diffusion was developed based on available descriptions and literature. For optimization and standardization, ten *C. difficile* strains were selected. The experiments are not finished at the moment. The collection of isolates was completed and all isolates were confirmed as *C. difficile* using different techniques. Furthermore, the MIC was determined. The ring trial will be organized after the completion of a method recommendation for the participating partners. Inhibition zone diameter distributions and proposing cut-off values for *C. difficile* will be determined after the completion of a method description.

Regarding the communication within IMPART a kick-off meeting was held at Schiphol for all consortium members. In addition, emails were sent out by the WP leaders to all consortium members containing general information on the progress of the different WP's. Furthermore, all WP leaders were in contact via Skype every two weeks discussing the organization of IMPART and the progress of the different WPs. In addition, extra Skype meetings were organized to discuss the pre-ring trials of WP1 and WP2. Furthermore, IMPART activities were presented on both Cogwheel meetings organised in 2018 with EFFORT and COMPARE. IMPART will keep on looking for synergies with other research projects in order to avoid duplicate research.

1.2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

1.2.1. WP1: Selective isolation, detection and characterization of colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae

JRP1-WP1-T1: Describe existing methods to be evaluated in a ring trial

A literature review had been performed to determine which media were used to isolate colistin-resistant Enterobacteriaceae. This review had been complemented by exploring any other commercially available option on the market as of September 2018. We selected both ready-to-use commercial reagents available throughout Europe and in-house prepared reagents. The selected media for the pre-ring trial were: Mc Conkey Agar + 2mg/L colistin, SuperPolymyxin, CHROMagar™ COL-APSE (CHROMagar), CHROMID® Colistin R (BioMerieux). Protocols using selective (1, 2 or 4mg/L of colistin) versus non-selective enrichment broth were also explored.

JRP1-WP1-T2: Preparation of the samples for the pre-ring trial (WP1)

In order to avoid false positive detection, our samples to be artificially contaminated (later called “blank” samples) were mostly collected from slaughtered Specific Pathogen Free (SPF) animals from collaborating animal housing facilities (pig and turkey caecal content, turkey meat). Due to unavailability, pig meat had to be purchased at retail shop. Nevertheless, meat and caecal “blank” samples had been checked for absence of colistin resistant determinant by both multiplex PCR (Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance) and plating on MacConkey + 2mg/l colistin agar. Non-contaminated sampled had been preserved frozen (-20°C).

The strains to be used for artificial contamination of the “blank” samples are listed below:

N°ANSES	Species/origin	Colistin MIC (µg/ml)	mcr gene	Reference	Matrix
15Q003582	<i>Salmonella</i> Rissen pig	≤1	-	Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance	Pig
15Q004074	<i>Salmonella</i> 4,12:i:- calf 2015	4	mcr-4	Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance	Pig
15F001211	<i>E. coli</i> calf 2015	4	mcr-3	Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance	Pig
15F001188	<i>E. coli</i> pig 2015	≤1	-	Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance	Turkey
15F001279	<i>E. coli</i> calf 2015	4	mcr-1	Rebelo et al, 2018, Eurosurveillance	Turkey
S12LNR3592	<i>Salmonella</i> Schwarzengrund broilers 2012	8	mcr-5	Webb et al, to be published Genbank: LKJL00000000	Turkey

Prior to spiking, a 0.5 McFarland ($\approx 10^8$ CFU/ml) target bacterial suspension in ultrapure sterile water using fresh colonies had been prepared and diluted to obtain the target concentrations in the pooled samples of minced meat or caecal content (10^2 CFU/g sample). The aliquots were stored at 4°C until shipping on Tuesday, December 11th.

Artificially contaminated aliquots were distributed at 4°C to the three participating labs (NVI, RIVM and WBVR). In order to avoid deviations due to different batches of reagents, ready-to-use media and powders for in-house media were distributed to the participants along with the samples.

JRP1-WP1-T3: Performance of the pre-ring trial and evaluation (WP1)

Participating labs proceeded the experiment as soon as they received the samples. Difficulties in routing the samples within 24h were experienced and every option to improve the parcel distribution before the final trial are explored.

Detailed results would be sent out to the organizers through a detailed excel file

At the time this report is written, the results are not available so far.

1.2.2. WP2: Selective isolation, detection and characterization of carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae

JRP1-WP2-T1: Describe existing methods to be evaluated in a ring trial

To establish the protocol for the WP2 pre-ring trial, a literature study and a questionnaire were performed to share experiences between the participants. All information was gathered together with a summary of a questionnaire sent out by the EURL-AR regarding selective media. Further, the following conditions were discussed: pre-enrichment (which media, selective/non-selective), choice of selective agar plates, incubation temperatures for pre-enrichment and selective agar plates, levels of contamination of the samples, which bacteria/gene-combination to spike with, and what kind of samples to use (turkey, chicken, pig, cattle).

A list of selective agar plates used for carbapenemase producers was made and the availability and possibility to make the plates in-house was taken into consideration. We ended up with nine plates:

NAME	PRODUCER	Ready-to-use	In-house
Brilliance™ CRE Agar	Oxoid	Yes	No
chromID® CARBA Agar	bioMerieux	Yes	No
chromID® OXA-48 Agar	bioMerieux	Yes	No
Chromatic™ CRE	Liofilchem	Yes	Yes
Chromatic™ OXA-48	Liofilchem	Yes	No
CHROMagar™ mSuperCARBA™	CHROMagar	No	Yes
ChromArt CRE / CRE-ESBL	BioLife	Yes	Yes

JRP1-WP2-T2: Preparation of the samples for the pre-ring trial (WP2)

The strains to be used for artificial contamination of the “blank” samples are listed below:

Number	Species/origin	Meropenem MIC (g/mL)	CPE gene	Matrix
2014LSAL00827	<i>Salmonella</i> Kentucky		NDM	Pig
ATCC BAA-2469	<i>E. coli</i>	>16	NDM-1	Pig
ATCC BAA-1705	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	>16	KPC-2	Pig
NCTC 13476	<i>E. coli</i>	2	IMP	Pig
NCTC 13440	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	>16	VIM-1	Pig
NCTC 13442	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	4	OXA-48	Pig
ATCC25922	<i>E. coli</i>	S	-	Pig

All samples were prepared at Anses Fougères as described under JRP1-WP1-T1 with the only exception of the OXA-48 positive strain diluted to both 10² CFU/g and 10³ CFU/g sample. The samples were shipped on Tuesday November 20th. The samples were distributed at 4°C and processed at arrival within 48 hours.

JRP1-WP2-T3: Performance of the pre-ring trial and evaluation (WP2)

The pre-ring trial of WP2 took place in week 47 and the final protocol and reading scheme was sent to the participants on Friday November 16th.

Anses prepared all the samples (JRP1-WP2-T2), ordered all ready-to-use and media for in-house selective agars, and shipped them to the participating laboratories (NVI, RIVM and WBVR) the week before the pre-ring trial to ensure that there was enough time to prepare the in-house selective agars. In total sixteen samples from pig, eight meat and eight caecal samples, and two negative samples (not spiked) were included. The samples were sent as 2 x 1g for the caeca samples and 1 x 25 g for the meat samples. The samples were run in parallels and 1 g of caeca sample or 10 g meat sample was pre-enriched in 1:9 in BPW-ISO and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours.

All selective agar plates were validated using *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *E. coli* TZ 3638 (GES-5 +) and *E. coli* 16874 (OXA-48 +) following the laboratory protocol from EURL-AR: https://www.eurl-ar.eu/CustomerData/Files/Folders/2-content/364_protocol-validation-selective.pdf.

The overnight broth was plated onto the selective agar plates and they were further incubated at 37°C AND 44°C for 18-24 hours. The readings of the selective agar plates were recorded in the reading scheme and the scheme was sent back to the WP2 leader the week after the pre-ring trial for further analyses. To date, the analyses are not finished.

1.2.3. WP3. Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)

JRP1-WP3-T1: Inventory, prioritizing and inclusion criteria

Consensus on the bacterial species and antimicrobials to be tested were reached during the kick-off meeting (held on 20 February 2018 at Schiphol airport) where the results of an earlier held questionnaire were discussed. The final lay-out of the panels needed some fine tuning, but was agreed upon before the end of June 2018. The plates (2500/batch) were ordered in July 2018 and are mainly, but not exclusively, designed for testing veterinary pathogens.

The first panel (NLD1GNS) is intended for testing Gram-negative bacteria especially *Pasteurellaceae* (e.g. *M. haemolytica*, *P. multocida*, *H. somnus* etc.), but can also be used for testing *Enterobacteriales* (*Klebsiella* spp., *Enterobacter* spp.) and possibly *Pseudomonas* spp.. For most antimicrobials in this plate ECOFFs are already available for *E. coli* and *Salmonella*, so testing these bacteria is not preferred. The second panel (NLD1GPS) is intended for testing Gram-positive bacteria including staphylococci, streptococci and possibly enterococci. The third panel (NLD1MAC) with macrolides, penicillin's is intended for testing staphylococci, streptococci and *Pasteurellaceae*.

JRP1-WP3-T2: Production of MIC data

The production of the three different batches of Sensititre plates (NLD1MAC, NLD1GPS, NLD1GNS) by Thermo Fischer Scientific was seriously delayed. The plates were initially promised to be delivered to the Dutch distributor (MCS Diagnostics) in December 2018, but the delivery is postponed for several weeks. As a consequence, the distribution of the plates to the partners will take place in January or February 2019. Therefore, susceptibility testing of bacterial isolates has not started yet.

JRP1-WP3-T3: Collection and quality control of MIC data

The collection of MIC data and quality control has not started yet.

1.2.4. WP4: Developing and optimizing a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*

JRP1-WP4-T1: Establishment of a disk diffusion method for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *C. difficile*

To establish a robust protocol for disk diffusion testing of *C. difficile*, we reviewed recent literature regarding this topic and identified critical parameters for reliability and repeatability of inhibition zone diameters (IZD) and growth of *C. difficile*. A first draft protocol was developed that is based on the EUCAST disk diffusion method (v 6.0) and includes recommendations from the literature. For optimization and standardization experiments, ten *C. difficile* strains were selected from the strain collection (see WP4-T2) based on different resistance properties. Optimization experiments included the comparison of different media for inoculum preparation (BHI, TPGY, Brucella broth), different turbidity steps (McFarland 0.5 – 4.0) and different solid media (Brucella blood agar, Wilkins-Chalgren-agar, Columbia blood agar) for the disk diffusion itself. Furthermore, different procedures and conditions of anaerobic incubation and pre-treatment were analysed, to be able to propose guidelines later. While the different inoculum and solid media had no significant effect on IZD, the turbidity has to be amended

from EUCAST recommendations to reach confluent growth for most of the strains. The biggest variance resulted from different anaerobic conditions and indicates this factor as the most critical for standardization. The most promising setup will be repeated for at least six times to determine standard deviations and repeatability.

The experiments are not finished at the moment. Due to problems in recruiting the applied technician and problems in delivery of a gas mixture for working in an anaerobic workstation, this task including milestone M-JRP1-4 (M8) is delayed to M14.

JRP1-WP4-T2: Assembly and characterization of *C. difficile* strain collection

Potential partners in IMPART that can contribute *C. difficile* strains from different origins were identified and asked to submit their isolates until end of June 2018. As several partners had to arrange the exchange with third parties, it took until December 2018 to receive all strains at the BfR. So far, we received 487 isolates from SVA, SLU, RIVM, NVWA, INSA, SSI, FLI and the German NRC for *C. difficile*. Some of the announced strains were not recultivable or showed up not to be *C. difficile*, so that the total number strain number remained below 500. Nevertheless, the milestone M-JRP1-5 is regarded as fulfilled in month 12.

If no corresponding data were available, the isolates were confirmed as *C. difficile* using MALDI-ToF, PCR-ribotyped and the toxin genes determined. Furthermore, the MIC was determined for all isolates using the agar dilution method as described by CLSI (M11-A8) and for the following antimicrobials: cefotaxime*, clindamycin, imipenem, metronidazole, moxifloxacin, rifampicin, tetracycline and vancomycin. We found that most of the isolates were resistant (according to EUCAST cut-offs) to cefotaxime, the corresponding MICs in a very narrow range and therefore not suitable for a comparison with IZD from the disk diffusion. Finally, we decided in agreement with the collaboration partners in WP4 to replace cefotaxime by clarithromycin for further testing and especially with regard to the disk diffusion testing.

As several isolates could be incorporated in the strain collection only with delay, we were not able to finish the characterization during the first project year, and this task is still ongoing.

JRP1-WP4-T3: Performance of a ring trial study

Will be organized after the completion of a method recommendation for the participating partners.

JRP1-WP4-T4: Producing inhibition zone diameter distributions and proposing cut-off values for *C. difficile*

Will be started after the completion of a method description for a robust and reliable procedure.

1.2.5. WP5: Coordination of the four work packages and knowledge dissemination both internally within and externally beyond the IMPART consortium

JRP1-WP5-T1: Organization of IMPART

IMPART consists of 5 different WP's supervised by WP leaders. The first four WP's have defined scientific goals whereas WP5 is intended for the communication and dissemination of knowledge.

JRP1-WP5-T2: Communication within IMPART

During the first year a kick-off meeting was held at Schiphol for all consortium members. In addition emails were sent out by the WP leaders to all consortium members containing general information on the progress of the different WP's. Furthermore, all WP leaders were in contact via Skype every two weeks discussing the organization of IMPART and the progress of the different WPs. In addition extra Skype meetings were organized to discuss the planning and results of the pre-ring trials of WP1 and WP2 with all people involved (with extra people from RIVM and ANSES).

JRP1-WP5-T3: Communication beyond IMPART

IMPART presented its activities on both Cogwheel meetings organised in 2018 with EFFORT and COMPARE. IMPART will keep on looking for synergies with other research projects in order to avoid duplicate research.

1.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

1.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
IMPART	D-JRP1-5.1	Invitation to the Kick-Off meeting sent to participants	1	22-01-2018		Kick-off meeting was organized on Tuesday 20 February at Schiphol airport in Amsterdam
IMPART	D-JRP1-3.1	Priority list	3	20-02-2018		Agreed on during kick-off meeting
IMPART	D-JRP1-5.2	Kick-off meeting notes sent to participants	3	22-02-2018		
IMPART	D-JRP1-1.1	Protocol of methods ready to be used in the pre ring trial	6	14-12-2018	12	A Junior scientist, Tifaine Hechard, was hired from July 2018 to January 2019. She took care of setting the protocol for WP1 pre-ring trial and organising the WP1 and WP2 pre-ring trials.
IMPART	D-JRP1-2.1	Protocol of methods ready to be used in the pre-ring trial	6	16-11-2018	11	A Junior scientist, Tifaine Hechard, was hired from July 2018 to January 2019. She took care of setting the protocol for WP1 pre-ring trial and organising the WP1 and WP2 pre-ring trials.
IMPART	D-JRP1-1.2	Samples ready to be shipped for the pre-ring trial	10	11-12-2018		Samples were shipped at 4°C on 11 December 2018. Samples for the two pre-ring trials (WP1-T2 and WP2-T2) were shipped separately in order to test a maximum of different conditions.
IMPART	D-JRP1-2.2	Samples ready to be shipped for the pre-ring trial	10	13-11-2018		Samples were shipped at 4°C on 20 November 2018. Samples for the two pre-ring trials (WP1-T2 and WP2-T2) were shipped separately in order to test a maximum of different conditions.
IMPART	D-JRP1-1.3	Evaluation of the pre-ring trial	11		13	The evaluation of the pre-ring trial has been postponed to February 2019.

IMPART	D-JRP1-2.3	Evaluation of the pre-ring trial	11		13	The evaluation of the pre-ring trial has been postponed to February 2019.
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1.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
IMPART	M-JRP1-1	Kick-off meeting (notes of meeting)	2	Yes		
IMPART	M-JRP1-2	Ordering of microtiter plates with antimicrobials (WP3)	4	No	13-14	Creating the layout of the microtiter plates was more complicated than expected. The plates should have been delivered in week 51, but delivery was postponed again.
IMPART	M-JRP1-3	IMPART EXTRANET in place	6	Yes/no	9	OH-EJP platform opened in month 9.
IMPART	M-JRP1-4	Established disk diffusion method (WP4)	8	No	14	Advertised technician position could not be recruited on time. Delay in gas delivery by manufacturer.
IMPART	M-JRP1-5	Completed strain collection (WP4)	10	Yes/no	12	As several partners had to arrange the exchange with third parties, it took until December 2018 to receive all strains at the BfR
IMPART	M-JRP1-6	Performing pre-ring trial (WP1 and WP2)	11	Yes	11 (WP2) 12 (WP1)	Results will be available in March 2019.

1.4. Publications and patents

No publications yet.

1.5. Impact & relevance

IMPART stimulates the improvement of methods and exchange of essential practical knowledge between veterinary and medical institutes regarding the detection of bacteria with emerging types of resistances to critically important antimicrobials.

The legislation, 'Commission Implementing Decision on the monitoring and reporting of antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic and commensal bacteria' (2013/652/EU), includes the obligatory monitoring of ESBL- and AmpC-producing *E. coli* and the voluntary monitoring of carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* in meat and caecal samples, according to the most recent version of the protocol of the European Union Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance (EURL-AR). Currently, there is no EURL protocols available (yet) for culturing of colistin resistant Enterobacteriaceae.

IMPART is in close contact with the EURL-AR and the results of WP1 and WP2 can be used as input for the EURL-AR future protocols.

Setting epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs) leads to an improved international harmonization of the monitoring of antimicrobial resistance in bacterial pathogens from animals and humans and is an essential first step in the development of missing clinical breakpoints. MIC data will be uploaded by IMPART in the EUCAST database and the subsequent analysis for setting ECOFFs will be performed in close cooperation with EUCAST/VetCAST.

By establishing and validating a less laborious method for susceptibility testing for *C. difficile*, the project will also contribute to an improved and harmonized surveillance of AMR in this zoonotic pathogen. Ultimately, ECOFFs will be set for a number of relevant antimicrobials in close cooperation with EUCAST.

1.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must clarify the safety mitigation measures in place to protect the environment and staff	The PL of IMPART has asked his supervisor at WBVR if it was possible to arrange this on management level of the partners; because this remarks will account for all JRP's within EJP.

1.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information: /

1.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

The EURL-AR (www.eurl-ar.eu) was contacted regarding WP2. They had performed a questionnaire between the NRLs on which selective agars the different NRLs used and their experience for the detection of carbapenemase producers in caecal and meat samples. This document was made available under the EURL-AR workshop in April 2018. They also provided a list of reference strains available for us to use in the pre-ring trial for WP2.

The preliminary results of IMPART WP1, WP2 and WP3 will be presented at the EURL-AR Workshop in Lyngby (DK) on 25th of April 2019.

IMPART also presented its activities on both Cogwheel meetings organised in 2018 with EFFORT and COMPARE. IMPART will keep on looking for synergies with other research projects in order to avoid duplicate research

1.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>External communication WBVR</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>14-12-2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Lelystad</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>YES</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>YES</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>No</i>		
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>+ - 500</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Cogwheel workshop with COMPARE</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>12-04-2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Online workshop</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>YES</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>No</i>		
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Cogwheel workshop with EFFORT</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>26/10/2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Online workshop</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
<i>w</i>	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>YES</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>No</i>		
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>+20</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

1.10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

In 2019, WP leaders will have a Skype meeting every two weeks (not planned yet).

In 2019, extra Skype meetings will be held to discuss the results of the different WPs for all partners involved (not planned yet).

In May 2019 a physical meeting for all consortium members will be held at the first One Health EJP annual scientific meeting in Dublin.

2. ARDIG

2.1. *Summary of the work carried out*

The ARDIG project has successfully completed its first year with all partners contributing substantially to its progress. Details of progress made by each partner for the three scientific work packages (WPs) are described within the report. The partners met at the kick-off meeting in early March 2018, and have since had three teleconferences to discuss progress/updates (June, September, and December). There have also been regular communications within the consortium by email. Furthermore, for each WP, questionnaires have been designed by the WP leads (WPLs), and all relevant partners have responded. The results, where appropriate, have been summarised in the report.

WP1 (Comparison of AMR and antibiotic sales/usage data collected through existing national surveillance and research programs and assessment of risk factors). In WP1, all partners participated in the detailed questionnaire/survey designed by the WPL, which included information on available AMR and AMU data sources in each country/institute. In addition to the survey, an extensive literature and data research addressing not only peer reviewed scientific papers but also grey literature such as reports from national agencies and non-governmental institutions that collect data on AMR and AMU, was performed. This collection has been summarized in deliverable D-JRP2-1.1 that is planned to be submitted by the end of M12 in accordance with the foreseen schedule. The draft of the deliverable has already been circulated by the WPL to the Partners and comments have been received. These comments are currently being integrated for finalisation of the report. Based on the deliverable, data for further analyses will be chosen and collated. However, issues with accessibility of data have to be overcome in several instances.

WP2 (Longitudinal studies of AMR persistence). Partners have planned, and in most instances commenced longitudinal studies, including retrospective studies where relevant archived isolates have/will be examined. A prospective human study involving five institutes, has also been planned to start in January 2019 and will last for one year. Collection and whole genome sequencing (WGS) of *Escherichia coli* from urinary tract infections will be performed, to compare the molecular profile and any epidemiological data of these isolates from four countries. Animal isolates are also being collected from prospective longitudinal studies, which have started or will start imminently. Most partners are involved in pig studies, and two partners are also involved in poultry and veal studies, so will enable comparison of resistance profiles between and within countries.

WP3 (AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates). All partners have been progressing with molecular characterisation of isolates from WP2, collected from prospective studies or archives. For most partners this has involved characterization of isolates by WGS (short and long reads), although other techniques such as PCR and Pulse Field Gel Electrophoresis have also been used. Most partners have been characterising the AMR profiles of isolates, and several are attempting to identify/characterise the circulating plasmids which may be involved in AMR transmission using WGS, conjugation or in-vitro gut models. Based on a questionnaire designed by WPLs, a workshop will be organized in 2019 where partners can describe the methods they are using for WGS analysis, so methods/protocols may be harmonized.

2.2. *Work carried out work carried out in the JRP, Scientific results*

2.2.1. WP1 Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

JRP1-WP1-T1: Exploration and collection of data available on AMR, AMU and potential risk factors (M1-M12)

UoS

UoS has collected antimicrobial use data for chickens, pigs and cattle from a local farm.

APHA

The aim of the current work was to explore AMR and AMU data sources in England and Wales in order to:

Identify and collect suitable datasets on AMR and AMU in livestock (pigs, poultry and cattle).

Assess and describe the potential compatibility issues of different data sources.

Characterize and map (geographically and with diagrams) the existing epidemiological data collection activities.

A literature search was performed to identify relevant projects and schemes that could be used for either benchmarking or ongoing monitoring of AMR and AMU. The search was conducted through Pubmed and Google Scholar using the term 'Antimicrobial Resistance' and the first 150 results were reviewed at both databases. Results were filtered to exclude articles from before 2010 to allow the creation of a "contemporary" dataset. The resulting articles were assessed for relevance based on whether they were UK-based studies, were not literature reviews or opinion pieces and included data of interest. The references of the articles were also assessed to determine other potentially useful publications. The remaining list consisted of ~350 articles, which were then reviewed for relevance by the lead epidemiologist.

The resulting list consisted of around 60 articles. The details were recorded and stored in an excel file. The articles were ranked low/medium/high based on the usefulness to the current review.

After the literature search on peer-reviewed journals, an online search was conducted to look for data sources on AMR and AMU from the public sector, industry and the retail sector. All relevant stakeholders were contacted to obtain additional information on the content of the databases. Using the information provided, a short evaluation of the surveillance databases was conducted following the Royal Veterinary College (RVC) framework for the evaluation of animal health surveillance¹. The surveillance evaluation (SERVAL) framework was used to provide a standardised and adaptable template to collect information of surveillance data sources. For each data source information on the nature of the data was recorded along with 13 chosen surveillance attributes which were each scored according to a traffic light system.

The results of the literature search and evaluation were included in a report and this information fed into the WP1 ARDIG questionnaire developed by BfR. Tables describing various attributes of the data sources were created for the report. A map showing data collection geographically and a diagram displaying data dissemination were included in the report. After the identification of the various data sources, all relevant stakeholders were contacted to request data. APHA attended meetings with the industry and the VMD in an effort to obtain non-aggregate AMU data and presented the current project. At the moment, the work focuses on collecting available data and planning the analysis.

IP

Like other partners and with the great help from BfR (Octavio Mesa) the Institut Pasteur has provided national data on AMR and AMU. The data collection was quite complex and will evolve to be more complete and accurate.

NVI

Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

The questionnaire on availability of AMU and AMR data from animals and humans in Norway was completed and submitted in September 2018.

WVR

Assistance has been given to BfR in their effort to summarize the existing AMR and AMU databases at national level. Discussion is still ongoing on how we can best contribute to some of the requested data sets.

PHE

Information on human AMR/AMU datasets (open/restricted access) in England as well as edits to the WP1 report have been provided.

BfR and RKI

A survey was performed by the BfR and RKI (Germany) and shared with all ARDIG members in order to collect relevant information on AMR and AMU in humans and animals. The survey results are available in the One Health EJP website (<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/structure/jrp2-ardig/>) within the ARDIG project in “Files” tab and in the folder “Template for Project Deliverables”.

In parallel to the survey data collection, a thorough review of literature and data on the topic was carried out based on the databases of surveillance and monitoring systems, scientific literature and national and European public reports. Along with the review, annexes are attached indicating AMU data available and type of bacteria studied from 2014 to 2017 based on national report data.

Information from literature and the survey was collated in deliverable D-JRP2-1.1, a report on the available data (see below). It shows a high degree of heterogeneity between the data from the different countries included in ARDIG and sometimes also within countries. However, it also shows that in addition to the data that are reported by MS to the European level (sales data to the ESVAC project of EMA, AMR data to EFSA in line with Commission implementing decision 2013/652/EU, and AMR and AMU (consumption) data from the human sector to ECDC (EARS-Net/ESAC-Net)) there are many data sources that have not yet been used for international comparative studies. Many of the AMU data are more detailed than the data reported to the agencies. However, the degree of harmonization, especially for the veterinary data is limited with e.g. some systems expressing use in defined daily doses and others (e.g. German data) as treatment frequencies. With regards to AMU, for the human sector, issues of comparability have been identified with respect to denominator data (e.g. DDD/patients days vs. DDD/1000 inhabitants as in ESAC-Net) or whether reimbursement data of pharmacy dispensing data or sales data are used. To appraise the representativeness of the data, yearly variations of number (voluntary) participating data providers, distribution of the hospital size and level of care, etc. have to be taken into account in order to extrapolate data on a country-level. Likely for the human AMR, data, variations in sample representativeness (e.g.

voluntary participation), different standards used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing have to be considered. This variability needs to be overcome or at least considered when using the data for comparisons across countries.

On account of the heterogeneity the final decision on which data will be included in the analysis has not been taken. The decision will also take into consideration that the European agencies have already performed and are going to continue performing data analyses in the framework of the JIACRA process. However, so far these analyses were based on sales data that do not accurately reflect the use of antimicrobial substances in the different animal populations. On the resistance side, the agencies only use a subset of the available data, with the advantage of using standardized data and the disadvantage that this excludes a relevant body of data, e. g. collected from different age groups in animals. Likewise, data on clinical isolates from animals are not included as they are not collected by EFSA. In the medical field, the focus is on isolates from blood stream infections, while many data on e.g. isolates from urinary tract infections are also available and shall possibly be included in our analyses.

A major point that needs to be discussed is the limitation of access to some of the data collected in MS. While some of the data are publicly available in great detail, others are very limited with respect to access and ways have to be identified to overcome these limitations without impairing data privacy.

Relevant efforts have also been performed to avoid the overlapping work with other projects. As a result, a connection with the EFFORT project (WP5) has been set up.

JRP1-WP1-T2: Investigation of trends, associations and risk factors (M9-M30)

BfR and RKI

To work on this task, the heterogeneity of available years has already been investigated and is reflected in deliverable D-JRP2-1.1. While for some bacteria/animal population combinations annual data are available, other combinations are sometimes only covered in one year therefore precluding longitudinal analyses. However, it needs to be decided whether these data can be included in cross-sectional international analyses highlighting the differences between populations and countries and potential associations with AMR rather than changes in AMR over time.

Detailed analyses will be carried out, once the data have finally been collated. However, methodological considerations have already been done in Germany on the comparison of AMR data between animal populations and humans originating from different collection systems.

2.2.2. WP2. Longitudinal studies of persistence ESBL/AmpC/carbapenem/mcr-1 and -2/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae on farms or hospitals.

JRP2-WP2-T1: Assessment and selection of longitudinal data from historical studies (M1-M12)

IP

In order to better characterize strains exchange among patients we are currently analyzing a collection of stool samples and MDR *E. coli* isolates from a follow up study of 329 patients in a 200-bed long-term care facility over 4 months (Duval A. et al. (2018) 8:1686 | DOI:10.1038/s41598-018-20008-w). 429 *E. coli* strains have been

isolated, among which 329 are predicted as ESBL producers. Epidemiological studies and modelling predicted transmissions path which are currently tested by WGS. 69 *E. coli* isolates have been sent for sequencing as well as 50 *K. pneumoniae* for comparison. In addition, and in collaboration with the national reference center laboratory for carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae headed by Thierry Naas (Bicêtre Hospital) we are analyzing all *E. coli* isolates received by the NRC. Genomic and plasmidic data on these isolates will be compared with similar data from other isolates of human and animal origins analyzed during the project (see also WP3).

NVI

Isolates from two previous studies focusing on cephalosporin resistant Enterobacteriaceae have been further investigated (phylotyping, PFGE and relevant meta data added). These results will serve as a basis for selection of isolates to be submitted to WGS (in 2019).

WVR

A questionnaire was sent out to all participating partners in this task to assess what data is available from published or unpublished studies. Some partners have complete datasets, others still need further molecular characterisation before these could be used for a joint analysis.

	Poultry	Pigs	Veal/cattle
NVI	X		
UCM	X	X	
APHA		X	
ANSES			X
WBVR	X	X	X

Samples of a longitudinal study conducted in 2017 on a single broiler farm in the Netherlands have been made available. ESBL *E. coli* were found to increase rapidly throughout the animals from the age of 2 days with all tested animals positive at slaughter age. Only a single ESBL gene was identified in all isolates, *bla*-SHV-12. Molecular analysis to determine the plasmid on which the gene is encoded is ongoing.

PHE

Consideration of sequenced published datasets of ESBL and non-ESBL human *E. coli* that were systematically sub-sampled collected from 2001-2012 UK human blood-stream infections revealed that isolates were sub-selected for resistance from the larger systematically collected surveillance collection. The fastq dataset's from these isolates are published and publically available.

Early analysis of other UK ESBL *E. coli* isolated from human bacteraemia, food and sewage samples revealed little overlap in the STs occurring in different compartments. Isolates from STs that overlap compartments will form 'per ST' analysis sub-sets for comparison in the next phase of the study.

JRP2-WP2-T2: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae on farms (M1-M24)

UoS

UoS is currently collecting *E. coli* isolates from healthy chickens and pigs (five faecal samples per animal per month) over a 12-month period (July 2018 - June 2019) in collaboration with a local farm, which has also provided

data regarding antibiotic use. Furthermore, *E. coli* isolates from cattle faecal samples (five per month) have been collected over a 3-month period (August - October 2018). Ethics approval to collect animal samples are in place.

APHA

APHA has extensively sampled a group of pig farms at two time points. These farms are part of the same breeding pyramid, and are characterised by the fact that antibiotic usage is very low. The aim of this work is to investigate whether there has been a decline in the proportion of antibiotic resistant *E. coli* and *Salmonella*, or a decline in resistance levels to selected antibiotics can be detected, over time in a breeding pyramid where antibiotic usage is very low. At the breeding herd, gilts, farrowing sows and dry sows were sampled. Weaner and grower finisher pigs originating from the breeding site were also sampled at their destination farm. Sixty individual faecal samples were collected from each epidemiological group (age class on farm). *Salmonella* was isolated from each individual pooled sample. Ten faecal samples were pooled for the quantification of *E. coli* (six pools for epidemiological group) on non-selective (MacConkey agar) and antibiotic selective (MacConkey agar with the addition of ciprofloxacin or cefotaxime). The proportion of *E. coli* resistant to these last resort antibiotic drugs was small, in particular in comparison with similar studies conducted in conventional pig farms (Taylor et al 2008). Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were also determined in a selection of *E. coli* from selective and non-selective culture. A descriptive analysis is about to be conducted in order to show the declining trend of resistance in the farm and also indicate whether the difference in resistance between the different epidemiological groups is significant.

NVI

Recent data from monitoring in broilers have demonstrated absence of cephalosporin resistant Enterobacteriaceae in Norwegian broiler production. A study in pigs will therefore replace the planned broiler study. It is expected that the overall resistance rates in Norwegian pigs are low with very low prevalence of resistance to CIA. The planned study will therefore focus on a combination of traditional culture-based approaches and metagenomics. We will select herds based on usage data (use of - versus no use - of tetracyclines and fluoroquinolones during the three years 2015, 2016 and 2017) in a defined region in Norway. Permission to contact farms based on usage data from VetReg (the Veterinary Medicines Register) was recently given. In mid-December, 10 farms of each category (usage vs non-usage) will be invited to participate. The first sampling will according to our plans take place in the winter 2019, then the farms will be sampled after 3, 6 and 9 months. A questionnaire to map relevant data and identify risk factors is developed. Samples for metagenomics will be taken at the first visit, samples for traditional culture-based methods (indicator *E. coli*) will be taken at all visits.

WVR

A questionnaire was sent out to all participating partners in this task to assess what type of farms will be visited during the project.

	Poultry	Pigs	Veal
NVI		X	
UCM		X	
APHA		X	
UoS	X	X	
ANSES			X
WBVR	X		X

Longitudinal sampling on broiler farms is ongoing. Prevalence of ESBLs is low, some farms are negative throughout the study so far. The last farm, number 5, has just been recruited, for which all samples were positive on the first two time points.

Due to the complex structure of the veal sector in the Netherlands, longitudinal sampling was not planned during the ARDIG project. In collaboration with Wageningen Livestock Research, a new project specifically aimed at longitudinal tracking of the health of individual animals will start through national funding. Through this project, longitudinal samples of animals from several farms will be made available for analysis. Sampling is due to start early 2019.

ANSES

Extended-Spectrum-Cephalosporins (ESC)-resistant Enterobacteriaceae have widely spread in all settings worldwide. Among others, ESBL/AmpC producers have frequently been identified in veal calves. We have set up two studies to investigate the trends in ESBL/AmpC prevalences and antimicrobial usages (AMU) in veal calves during the fattening process. In a first study, ten fattening farms were selected and visited twice. A total of 50 animals per farm were sampled for ESBL/AmpC carriage and other AMR phenotypes upon arrival and 5-6 months later before slaughter. The number and types of treatments during fattening were collected. ESBL-producing *E. coli* rates have significantly decreased in all farms (arrival: 67.7%; departure: 20.4%) whereas multidrug-resistant *E. coli* rates have significantly increased (arrival: 60.2%; departure: 67.2%). CTX-M-1 was the most frequently identified ESBL enzyme. The plasmid-mediated *mcr-1* gene was also identified occasionally. In parallel, levels of resistances to non-critically important antimicrobials were already high upon arrival but have still further increased over time until slaughter. Most ESBL producers were clonally unrelated suggesting multiple sources and not cross-contaminations among calves during transportation. Feeding milk containing antimicrobial residues to veal calves is hypothesized to explain the high ESBL loads in animals at the entrance on farms. A second study was then set up to get further insights into the dynamic of ESBL/AmpC spread over the fattening period. Three farms were visited 11 or 12 times at regular intervals of 15 days. A total of 15 calves per farm were sampled and processed as for the first study. The molecular investigations are on-going.

JRP2-WP2-T3: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in hospitals and care facilities (M1-M24)

UoS

The UoS is arranging the collection of *E. coli* isolates from human urinary tract infections (ten from hospital and ten from GPs per month) over a 12-month period starting in January 2019.

The UoS has gathered a set of *E. coli* isolates from human blood bacteremia cases. These have been collected through a local hospital over a 12-month period (July 2017-June 2018, around ten per month). AMR profile data and isolation date has also been collected. Patient information such as age, region, gender, AMR, source of infection and other potential risks factors will be provided once the appropriate ethics approval is in place (in the process of submission to IRAS).

IP

During the first twelve months period of the project we have defined the strategy for comparison of *E. coli* isolates circulating in participating countries. Following discussions during the consortium conference calls and by emails,

it has been decided that partners (IP, PHE, RKI, NVA, UoS) will collect from each month over one year, ten randomly selected and considered as independent *E. coli* isolates from urinary tract infection acquired in the community and ten acquired during hospital stay. Urinary tract infections have been chosen to be as much as possible representative of circulating isolates. We decided not to focus on ESBL producing isolates, considering that the already known over-representation of ST(Sequence Type)131 will be the main observation. We have also decided the minimal information that will be needed to be collected for each patient for subsequent analyses, like gender, age, date of isolation, ward, and so will not require ethical permission.

NVI

E. coli isolates from humans with UTI in a large centrally located hospital in Norway can be included in the study (the ten first isolates each month in 2019). Currently there are some uncertainties about funding for WGS of the isolates. The isolates will probably be sent us and stored at NVI, together with relevant data. Plans for further investigations of the isolates must be made at a later stage, depending on the possibilities for low-cost sequencing.

PHE

The 2019 prospective collection of urinary *E. coli* is planned and will provide collaborative short read and long read sequencing of isolates with multi-modal analysis of isolates to understand the circulation of bacteria, plasmids and resistance elements (e.g. transposon).

2.2.3. WP3. AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates

JRP2-WP3-T1: Detailed molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in human, animal, food and environment isolates from WP1 and WP2 (M6-M18)

UoS

The UoS has phenotypically characterized a set of 47 pathogenic avian *E. coli* isolates from local poultry veterinary practices (AMR profile). AMR profile of *E. coli* commensal isolates from pigs and poultry for longitudinal studies is currently in progress. The AMR profiles of pathogenic human isolates has been provided by the corresponding hospital microbiology laboratory. A subset of these collections will be selected for further characterization and WGS.

The UoS has analyzed the isolates (in a set of 245 *E. coli* strains from human urinary tract infections isolated in local hospitals) for the presence of ESBL (TEM/SHV/OXA, CTX-M, AmpC) and MCR genes by multiplex PCR. Genomic DNA from 96 multidrug-resistant isolates has been extracted and sent to the APHA for WGS. AMR genes, phylogeny, plasmid content, mobility genes, virulence genes, and other interesting characteristics will be analyzed from WGS data.

The UoS has prepared a questionnaire to facilitate the harmonization of methods and help the analysis of jointly-produced results in WP3. The questionnaire has been sent to all partners and responses gathered in a single report that has been distributed for discussion. The partners have a diverse and extensive collection of bacterial isolates which are being characterised using a variety of molecular and phenotypic assays. It is clear that varied methodologies for the analysis of isolates are being employed and these must be harmonised across the project to enable better comparisons to be made.

APHA

APHA have selected a subset of samples collected from one pig farm included for longitudinal study in WP2 for further molecular characterization by WGS. Representative *E. coli*, isolated on non-selective media and antibiotic selective media, from pooled pig faecal samples corresponding to multiple age classes and from environmental samples (seagulls), were chosen from time points one and two. From time-point 1 a total of 162 isolates from five pig age classes and one environmental source underwent WGS, with 142 passing QC for analysis; from time-point two, 96 isolates from four pig age classes underwent WGS, with 90 passing QC for analysis.

The WGS data in all isolates with sufficiently high quality data was analysed for presence of plasmid replicon types and AMR genes using the APHA SeqFinder with an in-house resistance and replicon database. Sequence type (ST) identification of isolates was performed using the Enterobase *E. coli* database and phylogenetic relatedness inferred using core genome SNP analysis. Preliminary results indicate that isolates identified from non-selective media display diverse STs, with the largest individual clonal complex being CC 10. In contrast, isolates identified from selective media show a lower diversity of ST with the dominant ST and complex differing according to antibiotic used. Isolates identified from media containing ciprofloxacin in time-points one and two are predominantly ST 744 (53.4% (n=31 ; T1) and 82.9% (n=29 ; T2) respectively) and CC 10 (24.1% (n=14 ; T1) and 17.1% (n=6 ; T2) respectively) and those identified from media containing cefotaxime are predominantly ST 88 (72.7% (n=16 ; T1) and 66.7% (n=6 ; T2) respectively) and ST 2721 (13.6% (n=3 ; T1) and 33.3% (n=3 ; T2) respectively).

Analysis of the AMR gene content of isolates from non-selective media from time-points one and two show an overall increase in the proportion of isolates possessing no resistance genes between the time-points, from 30.4% (n=17) to 56.5% (n=26) and a reduction in the proportion of isolates possessing resistance genes against four or more antibiotic classes from 9% (n=5) to 6.5% (n=3).

Among isolates across all media types, from both time-points, the most abundant replicon type was FII ; 40.2% of isolates in time-point one and 35.5% of isolates in time-point two harboured plasmids of this Inc-type. The second most abundant plasmid type in time-point one was identified as IncQ (22% of isolates), which was exclusively associated with isolates identified as ST 744 and appeared to be associated with the resistance genes *tetAB*, *bla*TEM-1b, *sul2* as well as *strAB*. However, in time-point two the second most abundant replicon type was instead ColRNAI (26.6% of isolates) followed by IncQ (24.4%). Interestingly, in time-point two the IncQ plasmid was identified in 21 ST 744 isolates with identical resistance gene content to time-point one, indicating a possible persistence of the IncQ-containing plasmid; and a single ST 88 isolate that possessed the same repertoire of resistance genes which likely indicates transmission of the IncQ plasmid to a different ST.

In both time-points the most frequently encountered beta-lactamase gene was TEM-1b, identified in 43 isolates from time-point one and 30 isolates from time point two. In time-point two only a single other beta-lactamase was identified, *bla*CTX-M-1, which was exclusively identified in ST 2721 strains from cefotaxime enriched media. However, in time-point one there was a greater diversity in the beta-lactamase genes identified which included CTX-M-15 (nine isolates), CTX-M-3 (three isolates), TEM-1 (two isolates) as well as Carbenicillin-3, CTX-M-27 and TEM-192 in only a single isolate, respectively.

For quinolone resistance, mutations in QRDR region of topoisomerase genes was most common. GyrA (83Ser-Leu, 87Asp-Asn) and ParC (80Ser-Ile) single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) were the most abundant in both time-point 1 and time-point two. For time-point one, six isolates only harboured the GyrA SNPs and five isolates harboured only ParC SNPs, whilst 44 isolates harboured both GyrA and ParC SNPs. In time-point 2, 25 isolates harboured both GyrA and ParC SNPs, and no isolates harboured SNPs in one gene only. The plasmid mediated

quinolone resistance gene *qnrS1* was identified in time-point 1 isolates only and appears to be encoded on an IncY plasmid that also contained the beta-lactamase gene CTX-M-15. This IncY plasmid was exclusively associated with ST 58 and identified in nine isolates. No plasmid associated quinolone resistance genes were identified in any isolates from time-point 2.

For macrolide resistance *mphA* was the most abundant resistance gene in both time-point 1 and 2, which in both time-points was most frequently associated with ST 744 isolates (95.2% time-point 1 and 92.6% time-point 2). In time-point 1 *mefB* was also identified in two ST 44 isolates ; however in time-point 2 no further macrolide resistance genes were detected.

Analysis of core-genome SNPs from all isolates from both time-points identified multiple instances of clones (defined as <20 SNPs) of strains present in pigs from different age classes, and instrains from the environment (gulls) and pigs. Within the isolates from time-point 1, a ST 744 clone was present in pigs from four age classes (dry, farrowing, weaner, and gilts), and multiple ST 744 clones were identified from gulls, dry, gilt and farrowing pigs. Similarly, two time-point 1 ST 88 clones were identified in gulls, farrowing, dry and weaner pigs. Multiple time-point 2 ST 744 isolates including from gulls, differing by <100 SNPs from ST 744 isolates from time-point 1, were also detected. It possibly indicates that the ST744 clone from time-point 2, recovered six months after time point 1, has evolved in the farm environment. Similarly, a single ST 88 isolate recovered from time-point 1 gull samples, differing from 3 ST 88 pig isolates from time point 2 by 100 SNPs, could indicate evolution of this clone. Taken together these results indicate possible persistence of clones within pigs and the farm environment. Future work includes the analysis and incorporation of the WGS results of time-point 3 as well as sampling, isolation, WGS and analysis of *E. coli* from a further time point in the first quarter of 2019. Furthermore the use of long-read Nanopore sequencing will be utilised for the complete identification of circulating plasmids from all time-points.

IP

During the first 12 months of the program, at the Institut Pasteur we have analyzed carbapenemase producing *E. coli* (CP-*Ec*) from the NRC collection by focusing on the ST410 lineage (WGS of 55 human isolates and three non-CP isolates from the ANSES collection). By combining the acquired genomic data with *E. coli* genome sequences from the NCBI and from Enterobase we showed that carbapenemase genes are frequently acquired in specific genetic backgrounds mutated in *ompC*, *ompF* or *ftsI* (Pbp3) and that other β -lactams than carbapenems might have contributed to the selection of the acquisition and fixation of the carbapenemase genes in *E. coli* (Patino-Navarrete et al., BioRxiv doi.org/10.1101/446195). Although CP-*Ec* isolates are extremely rare in farm animals in the participating countries they are more frequent in south east Asia and in some instance closely related to human isolates. Based on these first results we will further analyzed relation between CP-*Ec* isolates in humans and ESBL producing *Ec* from animal origins and for mutations in *ompC*, *ompF* and *ftsI*.

NVI

A collection of more than 260 cephalosporin resistant Enterobacteriaceae has been sequenced using short-read NGS. The strains were isolated from broilers between 2012 and 2016. For a more complete analysis a subset of isolates are currently sequenced using long-read sequencing (both MinION and PacBio). Plasmids (all IncI) in these isolates will be reconstructed and will subsequently be subjected to transfer and fitness studies.

ANSES

For the two studies carried out in calves, detailed molecular characterisation is currently on-going on ESBL/AmpC-producing Enterobacteriaceae using PCR, S1-PFGE, Southern blot and Illumina Technology. A specific search for

colistin resistance was also undertaken. The objective is to clarify the dynamic of the clones and plasmid types carrying the ESBL/AmpC/mcr determinants during the fattening process (longitudinal study) both within a single individual and across different individuals.

BfR

Escherichia coli isolates recovered from livestock and food in 2017, provided by the National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance (NRL-AR), were characterized for their phenotypic and genotypic resistance profile. The isolates were recovered from meat and feces of cattle and swine. Those matrices were specified by the German Zoonosis monitoring program and do change every year. Antimicrobial resistance was determined by broth microdilution according to CLSI guidelines. MIC values were evaluated using EUCAST epidemiological cut-off values. In our study the main focus was set on resistance against nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin. All isolates from 2017 with a MIC of ≥ 8 mg/L for nalidixic acid and/or a MIC of ≥ 0.25 mg/L ciprofloxacin were considered. In total, 452 *E. coli* isolates from the 2017-collection of the NRL-AR fulfill the requirement for further investigation. Of those isolates the DNA was extracted through a boiling method and stored at -80°C (Ehrt and Schnappinger 2003). Afterwards, the distribution of *qnr*-genes of the *E. coli* isolates was analyzed. All of the 452 *E. coli* isolates were screened for seven different *qnr*-variants, namely: *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrC*, *qnrD*, *qnrS*, *qnrVC*. Established PCR-methods were used for this purpose. The most frequent *qnr*-gene was *qnrS* with a total of 24.83% within all 452 investigated isolates. Furthermore, the most abundant *qnr*-positive isolates were gained from feces of cattle. Despite of *qnrS* the occurrence of the *qnr*-gene in the matrices is rather low, as showed in Table 1. Moreover, no isolate was found to be positive for *qnrD*.

Table 1: Distribution of *qnr*-variants among different matrices of isolates gained in the German national monitoring program

Matrix	<i>qnrA</i>	<i>qnrB</i>	<i>qnrC</i>	<i>qnrS</i>	<i>qnrD</i>	<i>qnrVC</i>
Pig, feces	4.21%	1.11%	<1%	8.87%	-	<1%
Pig, meat	<1%	-	-	<1%	-	<1%
Cattle, feces	3.33%	<1%	<1%	12.42%	-	1.11%
Cattle meat	<1%	-	-	1.11%	-	<1%
Other	<1%	2.66%	1.33%	2.22%	-	<1%
Total	8.20%	4.66%	2.22%	24.83%	-	2.22%

For further screening regarding the chromosomal relation of *qnr*-positive *E. coli* isolates XbaI-Pulsed-field-Gel-electrophoresis (PFGE) were conducted. Therefore, 190 *E. coli* isolates were further investigated (Guerra, Junker et al. 2004). With the results of the PFGE a phylogenetic dendrogram revealing certain relations between different strains was generated. Beside a high heterogeneity of the investigated isolates regarding their chromosomal structure, a few isolates did show certain similarities. A further step is the profounder analyzation of the generated data. Furthermore, the isolates were analyzed by S1-Nuclease PFGE to generate information on the plasmid content of the 190 *qnr*-positive *E. coli* isolates. This will also help to determine predominant plasmid-prototypes within *E. coli*. One purpose of conducting PFGE is the classification of *qnr*-positive *E. coli* isolates into

specific prototypes regarding their AMR, *qnr*, chromosomal and plasmid profile. Once, this is performed appropriate a prototype of each generated group is aimed to be sequenced. Therefore, long-read as well as short-read sequencing is anticipated. This will assure an in-depth analyzation of the whole sequence of each isolate, as well as their plasmid(s).

Altogether, with those comprehensive investigation of *qnr*-positive *E. coli* isolates a thorough and complex picture will be generated about the mobile genetic elements and their dissemination in commensal *E. coli* within the isolates from the German zoonosis monitoring program in 2017.

To assess the impact of *mcr*-carrying isolates on public health, the NRL-AR extended its phenotypic monitoring on the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance to a detailed characterization of colistin-resistant *E. coli* isolates. Therefore, an initial molecular screening was conducted using a conventional multiplex PCR for detection of the plasmid-mediated colistin resistance genes *mcr-1* to *mcr-5* (Rebelo, Bortolaia et al. 2018).

Since 2010, more than 15,000 *E. coli* isolates were investigated within the German monitoring programs by broth microdilution assays in terms of their antimicrobial resistance development. Thereof, ~700 isolates from various food and animal origins exhibit a minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) for colistin of ≥ 4 mg/L. Molecular determination of the *mcr*-gene prevalence revealed that the majority of these isolates (>80%) harbored the *mcr-1* gene. Additionally, we also identified some *mcr-4* (~2%) and *mcr-5* (<1%) carrying isolates. Up to now, isolates carrying *mcr-2* and *mcr-3* could not be detected indicating that these determinants may not be present in *E. coli* of German livestock. Our results showed that *mcr-1* carrying *E. coli* from German livestock and food products are highly prevalent in different matrices and time periods. Interestingly, we also found many *mcr-1* carrying *E. coli* among isolates before 2015, confirming that this determinant is not a novel phenomenon. The detection of *mcr-1* in *E. coli* within our culture collection dates back to 2010, five years earlier that the first discovery of this gene.

To answer the question on the heterogeneity of *mcr-1* carrying *E. coli*, selected isolates from different sources (i.e. turkey, chicken, pigs), isolated between 2012 and 2015, were characterized in detail. Comparisons of their antimicrobial resistance profiles showed that almost all isolates exhibited multiple resistances against various classes of antimicrobial substances. Besides colistin, the majority of the isolates exhibited also non-wildtype phenotypes against ampicillin, sulfamethoxazole and/or tetracycline.

To get an overview on the genetic diversity of *mcr-1* harboring *E. coli*, selected isolates were further molecularly characterized. Initial XbaI-PFGE profiling according to the PulseNet protocol (<https://www.cdc.gov/pulsenet/pathogens/protocols.html>) revealed a high heterogeneity of the isolates, because all of them exhibited diverse PFGE patterns. Based on the data we can exclude that the *mcr-1* carrying isolates of our analysis may be originated by the dissemination of a predominant *E. coli* clone via vertical gene transfer. As *mcr-1* is with some exceptions reported to be a plasmid-mediated mobile colistin resistance gene, further investigations on the genetic basis of this determinant were conducted by S1-PFGE plasmid profiling. S1-PFGE revealed that our selection of isolates harbored multiple extrachromosomal elements. Southern blotting and subsequent DNA-DNA hybridization showed that *mcr-1* was located on plasmid bands of different sizes.

Dissection of the *mcr-1* carrying *E. coli* genomes was performed by short read whole genome sequencing (WGS, MiSeq, Illumina). Our bioinformatic analysis revealed that a broad spectrum of commensal *E. coli* of different MLST-, phylo-, and serotypes can carry the *mcr-1* determinant. These data confirm that a broad spectrum of *E. coli* isolates may serve as a host or recipient for the acquisition of *mcr-1* carrying plasmids. The availability of WGS sequencing data allowed us further in silico analyses on the genetic basis of antimicrobial resistance determinants, virulence genes and mobile genetic elements (i.e. prophages, plasmids) that might be involved in the transmission of *mcr-1*. However, based on the prevailing MiSeq-WGS data the *mcr-1* carrying plasmid could

not be closed to complete circular genomes due to the presence of complex repetitive sequences and the high content of very similar transposase genes on the individual genomes. Sequence comparison based on *mcr-1* carrying sequence contigs revealed a close relationship to known plasmids of *E. coli*, *S. enterica*, *K. pneumoniae* and *S. flexneri*.

UCM

A student has been sent to Sanger Centre to develop pipeline/tool for analysis of hybrid long and short read sequences. Currently UCM using this pipeline to characterise isolates with methylase genes. The work will be longitudinal, and isolates (from WP1 and 2) have been sequenced with several techniques to determine the evolutionary history of the plasmids.

JRP2-WP3-T2: Characterisation of prevalent circulating plasmids and their transfer in vitro (M6-M18)

UoS

The UoS has set up *in vitro* chicken and pig gut models which are currently being validated to be used as transmission models of relevant mobile elements and AMR genes in the gut microbiome of food-producing animals.

WVR

A hybrid approach of short-read sequencing and long-read sequencing data of MCR plasmids in the Netherlands from 2010-2017 has been carried out. Genetic analysis of these MCR plasmids compared to global MCR plasmids is underway.

Incl1 plasmids contribute greatly to the spread of ESBL genes among Enterobacteriaceae. For Incl1 plasmids, the shufflon plays a role in the selection of recipient cells during conjugation. Shufflon activity was measured using MinION long-read sequencing. Activity of the shufflon was not seem affected by growth conditions but a strong bias for certain variants was shown to exist. A manuscript has been submitted for publication.

PHE

An emerging plasmid type encoding NDM has been detected in the UK, causing multiple geographically separated clusters in diverse bacteria belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae. Example plasmids from different plasmid 'clades' along with historical examples have been sequenced for outbreak investigation and comparison purposes, it has been agreed to make these plasmids available to WP3 partners (UoS), pending an MTA (in prep), in order for *in vitro* or model study's to examine plasmid fitness effects, transmission rates and transposition frequencies.

BfR

To determine the transferability of the *mcr-1*-carrying plasmids some of the isolates, representing prevalent prototypes of *mcr-1* plasmids, were used in filter mating studies with the azide-resistant *E. coli* strain J53 (Borowiak, Fischer et al. 2017). Transmission studies indicated that from all tested isolates *mcr-1* carrying plasmids could be transferred to the J53 recipient strain at 37°C.

Our findings indicate that *mcr-1* carrying *E. coli* isolates are widely disseminated in German livestock and food products of animal origin. In general, we suppose that the distribution of *mcr-1* associated colistin resistance is mainly forced by horizontal gene transfer (i.e. plasmid transfer), because of the high degree of diversity among

the investigated isolates (i.e. PFGE-pattern, MLST-type, serotype). Overall, at least three conserved plasmid prototypes were identified to be involved in the *mcr-1* dissemination of this study. Genetic analysis revealed that the location of the resistance on a potentially active transposon might further force the dissemination of the resistance determinant to other plasmids or to the chromosome of the bacteria. However, without further data on the diversity of *mcr-1* carrying isolates from human origins the impact of this resistance determinant for the human medicine is still unknown. Further investigations are necessary to reveal the potential missing links of *mcr-1* spreading via contact to colonized animals and/or the consumption of contaminated food products. Currently, there is an urgent need for drastic management strategies to curtail colistin resistance development and dissemination.

2.2.4. WP4: Project coordination and management.

JRP2-WP4-T1: Steering committee quarterly meeting (M1-M36)

There have been three teleconferences (TC) attended by the steering group following the kick-off meeting. This included a TC meeting in June, September and December 2018 where at least one member of each Institute attended. Each meeting was one and a half hours long with partners providing updates on progress, followed by general discussions.

JRP2-WP4-T2: Consortium members annual meeting (M1-M36)

A kick-off was held in early March 2018 where consortium members met and the PI went through the project outline; each member also provided an outline of their project plan. The next annual meeting is being planned in May 2019, the annual conference attended by most consortium members.

JRP2-WP4-T3: Reporting and communication (M1-M36)

All partners have been involved in the 9M and 12M reports, which have been delivered on time. Communication between PI, WPLs and other consortium members occur regularly. Evidence of communication is provided by response to the questionnaires by partners which has provided the basis for understanding of the work planned by each partner and how datasets, isolates, methodologies etc. may be harmonised.

2.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

2.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
ARDIG	D-JRP2-2.1	Assessment of criteria for inclusion of retrospective and prospective longitudinal studies.	2	6		<p>A questionnaire has been completed by all partners to assess the criteria for inclusion. For both the animal and human isolates to be used from retrospective studies the criteria is still under discussion and will be finalized when data from all the strain collections become available.</p> <p>For the prospective studies for the human isolates the criteria is that the first 20 E. coli isolated from urine from each hospital at each month over a year will be included. There are no criteria for the animal isolates and we will attempt to harmonise methods as much as possible across partners.</p>
ARDIG	D-JRP2-1.1	A report of AMR and AMU data (and data collection activities) in livestock and humans in the seven participating countries, and with indication to its quality, comparability and purpose.	12	12		This report will be submitted in a timely manner.
ARDIG	D-JRP2-2.2	Assessment of retrospective longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.	12	12		Partners have made an assessment and have been collecting the relevant data. The 12M report provides details.
ARDIG	D-JRP2-4.1	Annual communication to stakeholders	12	12		A 12M report providing details of the work performed in ARDIG will be circulated to UK policy holders.

2.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
ARDIG	M-JRP2-1	Two datasets on (1) AMR and (2) AB usage of the six participating countries.	12	yes		A questionnaire/survey has collected this information from the consortium members.
ARDIG	M-JRP2-2	Assessment of retrospective longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.	12	yes		This milestone has been met (see D-JRP2-2.2)
ARDIG	M-JRP2-3	Preliminary molecular characterization of AMR genes from isolates collected in WP1 and WP2.	12	no	24	All partners have started molecular characterisation of isolates. WP3 provides details of the work.

2.4. Publications and patents

None to report at this time.

2.5. Impact & relevance

The survey performed in WP1, and the report (D-JRP2-1.1), provides details of the available AMR and AMU data from all partners/countries; it also identifies data gaps, especially for comparisons between the Med and Vet components. The finalized report is not only helpful information for the participating countries on the types of data being collected and available, but also is anticipated to be helpful for EU policy. A manuscript for publication is expected to be prepared, which will also be sent to colleagues in ECDC and EFSA.

Harmonisation of approaches and methodologies is another important aspect of ARDIG. To facilitate this questionnaires have been designed in WP2 and WP3. As a result, there will be a prospective longitudinal study where Med partners from four different countries will be collecting human urinary tract isolates, and comparing results. Vet partners will also be performing longitudinal studies, where isolates will be purified from samples collected on farm from different livestock. In future, it is intended that molecular profiles, along with epidemiological data from human and livestock isolates, collected from different countries, will be compared to identify dominant profiles both within Med and Vet components, as well as different countries.

A workshop will be set up in future to help harmonise methods for analysis of molecular data, especially those derived from WGS, based on the results of a questionnaire for WP3. It is particularly important that quality thresholds for WGS data analysis, and databases of resistance genes, are harmonised so all partners can compare results with each other.

2.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of biological samples have been sought.	Ethics approval is not required as the animal samples will be collected from the farm environment rather than animals themselves or national surveillance activities. Human samples will be collected from hospital reference laboratories.
The applicants must specify whether the samples used for genetic analysis permit to identify the sample donors. If so, then an incidental / adverse finding policy must be prepared and available.	No personal or farm identifiers will be used so any sample owner will not be identified.
The applicants must document the safety mitigation measures in place to protect the staff.	All partners work in laboratories that perform risk assessments of reagents and experimental procedures, following the correct health and safety procedures.
The applicants must confirm the compliance with GDPR.	The applicants can confirm GDPR compliance.
The applicants must specify why the misuse issue has been identified in the ethical self-assessment, and how they will address this issue.	The applicants do not foresee any misuse of ethical or other data and results and believe this was a misunderstanding. All applicants will be vigilant and ensure that there is no misuse of data of any type.

<p>The applicants must confirm the application of 3Rs and the ethical approvals (approval letters, etc) for animal work at a national / institutional level level. The applicants must confirm the process for the application of the 3Rs across the whole programme of work to ensure 3Rs coordination across the programme (e.g. in-vivo mouse work, etc). Please elaborate.</p>	<p>The applicants can confirm the application of 3Rs. Partners who will undertake any animal work e.g. in vivo mouse work, will do so in a justifiable way with full ethical approval, applying the principles of 3Rs.</p>
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2.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	No
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information: /

2.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

Several members of the consortium are also part of the EFFORT project, and there was interaction of ARDIG partners at the EFFORT COGWHEEL Workshop and the EFFORT conference.

2.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	International Society for Plasmid Biology Meeting		
Date:	5-9 August 2018		
Place:	Seattle - US		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	Poster
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	150	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

2.10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

There will be at least one teleconference meeting per quarter for the ARDIG consortium to update partners on progress. The annual meeting will be held in May, alongside the EJP AGM, and the PI has already contacted the organisers to reserve a room for the ARDIG meeting.

3. RaDAR

3.1. Summary of the work carried out

In short, **WP1** (New genomic information to feed AMR transmission models) constructed a curated database of unique complete plasmid sequences (which is among the largest of its kind available) including a bioinformatic pipeline allowing for systematic classification of plasmids. **WP2** (Pharmacodynamics and transmission models)

has developed a model framework for colistin effect on *E. coli* within pig guts and a draft model framework has been developed for on farm transmission of ESBL *E. coli* in pig pens. **WP3** (*Transmission through the food chain*) developed infrastructure for a web-based risk assessment model inventory and adapted an existing Campylobacter model in order to model ESBL *E. coli* in the chicken production chain. **WP4** (Machine learning methods for quantification of risk and health effects) has selected the most appropriate machine-learning algorithm in order to set up an evaluation pipeline for AMR risk models. A review paper outlining the different risk questions related to AMR, interdisciplinary challenges in addressing them in a One-Health perspective, and how ML methods can be used for progressing beyond the status quo exists as a full draft and is under further development. **WP5** (The burden of disease caused by AMR exposure) formulated methodology for computing the burden of AMR that calculates AMR-attributable burden as excess burden (in contrast to excising ECDC models). The proposed approach has advantages (the burden of susceptible infection is treated as a counterfactual, so true excess BoD is estimated; there is no need for conversion of prevalence data) and disadvantages (requires data on incidence of resistant infection) compared with the recently published ECDC approach, but if the assumptions underlying each approach are valid and correctly specified, they should lead to the same result. Finally, **WP6** (Integration of information by Bayesian evidence synthesis) made a descriptive overview of available Dutch, and succeeded building up a prototype joint evidence synthesis network (risk assessment and epidemiological data) for the pork chain as a multi-level Bayesian model, which uses Dutch pork consumption data and dose-response data combined with epidemiological ESBL *E.Coli* carriage data in order to produce a joined consensus estimate on human carriage of ESBL *E. coli*.

3.2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

3.2.1. WP0: Coordination and communication

JRP3-WP0-T1: Coordination and project management

The RaDAR study was successfully started in January with a meeting at Schiphol airport. Immediately, there was a good vibe within the group and members were eager to start working on this important topic. After the kick-off meeting several WP focused teleconferences were held in order to get the WPs starting. Subsequently, this was followed-up by regular email contact. In general, there is good communication and interaction between partners. In June, a WP-leader TC was held. Information from the EJP management was provided by the project leader to the WP leaders (reporting, data management plan, etc). None of the partners reported financial problems (i.e. issues regarding co-funding). JRP3-WP3-T2-ST3 reports delay due to personnel resources. WP5 reformulated some of the tasks due to changing governmental emphasis regarding the co-funding emphasis.

JRP3-WP0-T2: Consortium meetings

JRP3-WP0-T2-ST1: Kick-off meeting

January 2018 Schiphol Airport, The Netherlands. Important first alignments and directions were consolidated.

JRP3-WP0-T2-ST2: Mid-term meeting

To be held on January 18th Schiphol Airport, The Netherlands. All WPs will report on their progress and the planning for next year will be discussed.

JRP3-WP0-T3: Annual reports

JRP3-WP0-T3-ST1: First annual report

3.2.2. WP1. New genomic information to feed AMR transmission models

The **main objective** of this work package is to develop new bioinformatics tool to retrieve information from genomic data that are relevant for modelling AMR risk and transmission. In order to control and therefore limit the dissemination of mobile antibiotic resistant genes, we need to identify the causative plasmids and follow their path from reservoirs to pathogens. To track and identify plasmids we need a robust plasmid classification method. **Systematic classification** would involve phylogenetic and functional information that reveal certain features about the organization and the relationships between them. More than one million of plasmid sequences are now publicly available in the NCBI nucleotide database and this number is increasing every week by new plasmid sequence submission. However, this huge data collection is not always reliably annotated to distinguish complete plasmids from plasmid fragments, such as gene or contig sequences. Therefore, retrieving complete plasmids for downstream analyses is challenging. Moreover, the classification and characterization of known plasmids is necessary to detect, isolate and identify newly isolated plasmids in the future.

JRP3-WP1-T1: Build collections of high throughput sequencing (HTS) data needed for project- specific milestones and deliverables

- **Construction of a curated plasmid Database from Complete Plasmid Sequences from NCBI.**
The initial retrieval of the putative complete plasmid accessions from NCBI was performed by using advanced filters. The last database was downloaded on June 12th and contains **22425 complete plasmids**, compiled from the NCBI nucleotide database. After applying well-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria a curated plasmid database consisting of 12084 unique complete plasmid sequences from the NCBI was constructed. The majority (94.5%) of the plasmids are circular and the size vary from 744 to 2555069 bp with a median at 53206 bp. Regarding the taxonomy, 21 bacterial phylums and 38 classes are represented. Plasmids were isolated from 126 countries with a frequency varying from one plasmid collected in 21 different countries to 1703 in the USA. This curated plasmid database will be maintained and enriched regularly by using an automated tool and this curated database will be implemented in our in-house pipeline along with other bioinformatics tool for plasmid *de novo* identification and characterization. A paper presenting the construction and content of the database is being written and will be submitted in the next weeks.
- **Plasmid typing and classification.**
All the plasmids from our curated database will be typed using MOB-typer, a tool from the MOB-suite software (<https://github.com/phac-nml/mob-suite>) for clustering, reconstruction and typing of plasmids from draft assemblies MOB-typer provides *in silico* predictions of the replicon family, relaxase type, mate-pair formation type and predicted transferability of the plasmid. A thorough k-mer based clustering analysis has been performed on the 12084 plasmid sequence to investigate the relationships between plasmid and host taxonomy

JRP3-WP1-T2: Develop an innovative automated bioinformatic pipeline integrating de novo plasmid reconstruction and generation of chromosome scaffolds

A bibliographic research on existing tools for plasmid reconstruction showed that recent bioinformatic developments can now perform *de novo* assembly from short reads whereas traditional methods were using the BLAST algorithm to compare with reference sequences. Programs for *de novo* assembly of plasmids include **cBar**, **PLACNET**, **Recycler**, and **PlasmidSPAdes**. In comparison to PLACNET that reconstruct the plasmid according to the homology of the contigs to reference sequences, the algorithm of recycler and plasmidSPAdes are independent of plasmid references. Artificial reads dataset was produced by ART to compare the plasmid reconstruction *de novo* (plasmidSPAdes) with the assembly using the BLAST algorithm (ABRicate) <https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>. Preliminary results showed that plasmidSPAdes is very efficient for plasmids bigger than 6kb whereas the mass screening of contigs Blast-based (ABRicate) has a low efficiency when the search stringency is high. The reconstruction will be followed by annotation and ORF extraction using Prokka and the identification of the reconstructed plasmid will be done by gene content comparison and plasmid network interaction.

JRP3-WP1-T3: Plasmidome: Biological annotation and risk assessment

To standardize the annotation of the sequences and to facilitate the gene content comparison, all the plasmids were annotated with the program Prokka using the same parameters. The gene content of every single plasmid will help us building a plasmid gene catalogue, which will be very useful for *de novo* identification and characterization.

JRP3-WP1-T4: Methods to identify genetic traits associated to AMR

The ResFinder database was downloaded from <https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/> and the antibiotic resistance genes retrieved will be used to mine our curated database and *de novo* plasmid assembly.

3.2.3. WP2. Pharmacodynamics and transmission models

JRP3-WP2-T1: On-farm transmission models

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST1: PK/PD model to assess relationship between animal exposure and change in antimicrobial resistance

A reference database has been updated with recent publications which have been reviewed and used to inform the development of the PK/PD gut model. A document outlining inputs and outputs and an initial simple model framework has been shared with WP2 consortium members. This informs plans of how best to link up with the on-farm model in sub-task 2.1.3.

The PKPD models will consider *mcr-1-E. coli* in pigs treated with colistin because the PK is quite simple (no absorption after oral use, see figure 1 below) and also ESBL *E. coli* in pigs treated with a cephalosporin drug. For each model, a sensitive and a resistant *E. coli* population are included. The choice of model structure was based on literature analysis but also on internal *in vitro* data (Time kill curves). A global sensitivity analysis will be performed to assess the influence of each parameter within these PKPD models.

Figure 1: Proposed PKPD model for colistin effect on *E. coli* within pig guts (blue: PK or PD parameters)

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST2: Assess relative importance of AMU and clonal dissemination for resistance occurrence

Thanks to the recent results from the EFFORT project (Sarrazin, *et al.* (2018), Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy), different case-scenarios will be simulated according to real on-farm usages. In link with the on-farm transmission model (sub task 2.1.3), the impact of AMU for one entire batch or only one box of pigs on the spread of resistant bacteria will be assessed. Moreover, the impact of duration of treatment (due to different diseases or target) will be studied. This task will also depend on the results of the sensitivity analysis from the previous task.

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST3: Development of on-farm transmission model

A draft model framework has been developed building on ideas from previous models identified in the literature review. The proposed model will consider ESBL *E. coli*. The literature review did identify some models that can deal with multiple resistances, but due to the added complexity in this model, it was considered that it would be a step too far to consider here. This would be a potentially useful addition to consider in the future. A document outlining the framework has been circulated among relevant experts at APHA for feedback and discussions have been had with RaDAR partners at a WP2 teleconference.

The proposed model is made up of two components; a between pig model (farm model) and a within pig model (pig gut model), the latter of which will be based on the work from JRP3-WP2-T1-ST1. The main purpose of the farm model is to simulate the management practices of the pig farm, the use of antimicrobials, the level of bacteria in the pens/farm environment and the behaviour of the pigs including ingestion of bacteria from the environment over time. The proposed farm model is an individual based stochastic model with detailed management practices built in. The susceptible and resistant bacteria create an environmental reservoir of infection which the pigs come into contact with. The level of resistant bacteria shed by each pig comes from the pig gut component of the model and the consumption

of bacteria is fed back into the pig gut model. A summary of the transmission in one pen of the farm component of the model is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of transmission dynamics in a pen from the farm component of the model. Interactions between this model and the pig gut model are highlighted in green (uptake, $U_{S/R}$) and red (excretion, $V_{S/R}$). The $\beta_{xc}(j, t)$ parameters indicate cross-contamination rates between pens.

JRP3-WP2-T1-ST4: Scenario analysis to assess hypothetical on-farm intervention measures

Work on this sub-task has not begun in earnest yet. A meeting with policy colleagues is arranged for January 2019, where practical on-farm intervention measures will be discussed.

JRP3-WP2-T2: Models for transmission between livestock and human populations

JRP3-WP2-T2-ST1: Development of mathematical models for source-attribution

Work has not begun on Task 2.2 yet due to awaiting appointment of a PhD student to work on the project.

3.2.4. WP3. Transmission through the food chain

JRP3-WP3-T1: Inventory of available exposure assessment models and related data and transfer to FSK Standard

T1 aims to review available methods to model the change of prevalence and concentration of bacteria with phenotypic resistance or specific resistance determinants along the food chain for exposure assessments and to increase accessibility and exchangeability of these models. To achieve this, available models and models developed during the project are translated into a standardised format, the Food Safety Knowledge (FSK)

Framework, which aims at facilitating access and exchange of models. The easy access to available models will support rapid assessments when new patterns arise or specific measures need to be assessed. The work will enable rapid exchange of models and information between researchers, countries and public & animal health institutes in the future.

To achieve this, the following steps are taken:

- Technical implementation of the framework / inventory for exposure assessment models (JRP3-WP3-T1-ST1)
- Collection of models suitable for storage in the inventory and translation of models (and related metadata) into a standardised format according to the Food Safety Knowledge Framework (JRP3-WP3-T1-ST2)

JRP3-WP3-T1-ST1: Inventory of available exposure assessment models

The structure and technical implementation of the inventory for exposure assessment models is based on the idea to provide a web-based tool for accessing and exchanging models of EJP-partner. Since models are developed in various programming languages and tools, a standard for describing models is desirable in order to achieve easy reuse of models. As a standard for describing models we use the Food Safety Knowledge (FSK) Framework [1]. The FSK framework can be used to execute models and display results language-independently. It requires that the model meta data (i.e. data about the model, like names of dependent and independent variables used in the model, units used, information about the authors, references etc.) is provided as well as the program code. These two components are stored as so called FSK files. The FSK standard allows modellers and risk assessors not knowing the original language in which models have been implemented to still use them. This is accomplished by using the free and open source software called KNIME [2]. Users can install KNIME and use it to run models stored in FSK files. The main drawback however is that the FSK standard currently only supports the programming language R. Support for Matlab and Python is planned but yet not provided.

Based on already existing features of the RAKIP model repository [3] and in order to improve them further the following list contains the key and desirable features for the RaDAR inventory:

1. Save and display models and model results
2. Change model parameter and execute models
3. Upload new models from FSK files
4. Upload new models from R files
5. Sort and display models filtered by details:
 - a. Bacterial species
 - b. Phenotype of bacterial species
 - c. Resistance traits
 - d. Animal species
 - e. Processing steps
 - f. Transmission pathways (foodborne, direct contact)
 - g. Spread (horizontal vs vertical)
 - h. Risk factors
 - i. Regional / national patterns for food processing
6. Dynamic search for models and model details

7. Different layout for authorized users
8. Simple and intuitive user interface (UI)
9. Store assessments of models by users
10. Notifications on new model or comments
11. Dynamic plots / charts
12. Guide to create FSK file
13. Display model code in browser

After discussing advantages and disadvantages of different concepts for implementation, we've decided on a fat client concept based on the Typescript framework Angular hosted by a Jenkins server, a KNIME server and a database to save model metadata, since this provides more flexibility in implementing future features and a better UI. Both servers are hosted by BfR. The concept is described in figure 3: The user can visit the inventory through a web browser. The model results and additional model information are stored in the database, which are displayed in the browser and can be downloaded as FSK files. When uploading a new model, the files needed to create the FSK file are stored in the database. Angular sends a HTTP request containing the location of the needed files to a KNIME server by using its REST API. A workflow on the KNIME sever processes the data from the request, loads the files, creates a FSK file, executes the FSK file and sends a HTTP response with the plot figure and FSK file back to Angular, that stores the results and metadata in the database.

Figure 3: Illustration of the model inventory concept

Until this moment most key features have been implemented: Uploading models from FSK and R files is already possible, as well as displaying the models and model results. A KNIME workflow for executing models with changed parameters within the web browser has been developed, but yet not implemented

into the web application. An interface for sorting, filtering and searching has also been designed, but is unused. Further features are not implemented yet.

[1]. DE ALBA APARICIO, Miguel, et al. FSK-Lab–An open source food safety model integration tool. *Microbial Risk Analysis*, 2018.

[2]. KNIME home page, www.knime.com

[3]. RAKIP model repository, https://services.d4science.org/web/rakip_portal

JRP3-WP3-T1-ST2: Transfer of available exposure assessment models developed in R (or matlab) to FSK Standard for at least one type of AMR bacteria and at least one animal (chicken, pig or mussels)

RaDAR partners have been asked to provide information of available models or data which could be suitable for the inventory. With one exception there are no freely available models in R (or matlab) among partners but availability of the models would require material transfer agreements. The one exception is a model on the spread of ESBL/AmpC *E.coli* in the broiler production chain (<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/risa.13145>). This model will be transferred into FSK.

JRP3-WP3-T2: Exposure assessment models for different production chains

Building on work in T1 and in collaboration with WP2, generic models are developed and implemented where different exposure pathways as well as different food chains can be evaluated and compared with respect to risk.

JRP3-WP3-T2-ST1: Exposure assessment model for the chicken production chain

Work on the chicken production chain model started by adapting a model that originally simulated cross contamination of chicken carcasses in the slaughter line for *Campylobacter*. Data on *E.coli* contamination along the processing steps in different slaughterhouses were used to adapt the model parameters from *Campylobacter* to *E. coli*. In the next step we plan to automatize the adaptation of model parameters based on data. One approach we are about to try out is based on Bayesian updating of model parameters using data, along the lines of <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2010.01379.x>. Furthermore we are developing a graphical interface which allows to incorporate reduction of contamination at several stations along the broiler processing process. This in turn should help to assess the effect of reduction on the final contamination and in the end on the exposure. This model is also going to be transferred into the FSK standard.

For the primary production (hatchery, transport, fattening at farm) another model will be developed. Currently, we adapt the model on the spread of ESBL/AmpC *E.coli* in the broiler production chain (mentioned above in **JRP3-WP3-T1-ST2**) in such a way that it not only estimates prevalences of ESBL/AmpC *E.coli* among flocks and among animals in one flock but also estimates how large the corresponding colonisation of animals with ESBL/AmpC *E.coli* is. That includes the external colonisation on the outside of the birds as well as the number of bacteria in the faeces.

JRP3-WP3-T2-ST2: Exposure assessment model for the pork production chain

Work on the pork production chain model has started, and several lines of research are currently pursued. This work has been carried out with Yeru Wang from China National Center for Food Safety Risk Assessment, Division of Microbial Risk Assessment. She visited RIVM for several months and was funded by a separate grant. In collaboration with Yeru Wang we have performed a literature search for QMRA models of *E. coli* in the pork chain, and relevant parameters as input for the model. This resulted in several spreadsheets of quantitative data sources. Furthermore a conceptual model was established, building on the existing EFSA Salmonella in Pigs model. However, the structure was modified in close collaboration with WP6 to facilitate integration in a larger Bayesian Evidence Synthesis framework. This was the groundwork necessary to start the implementation phase of the model in 2019.

JRP3-WP3-T2-ST3: Exposure assessment model for the mussel production chain

Carrying out the mussel experiments have been delayed due to severe delays in hiring key laboratory personnel resources. In the meantime, the original plans and protocols have been improved and expanded, field logistics made ready and existing related datasets assessed.

3.2.5. WP4: Machine learning methods for quantification of risk and health effects

The development of antibiotic resistance is a complex process influenced by a multitude of risk factors, and this process is still not understood in all parts. It is undoubted that the occurrence of multiple resistance patterns is a key feature of antibiotic resistance and the aim of risk factor analysis should be the disclosure of resistance patterns and potential risk factors. Perhaps, we might not have understood the process of antimicrobial resistance, because we have not used the appropriate statistical methods for the analysis of our observation. In order to contribute to the understanding of antimicrobial resistance, a repository of state of the art statistical methods collectively referred to as ‘machine learning’ methods will be compiled. The aim of this WP is the systematic identification and recording of the known methods and their comparison

JRP3-WP4-T1: Add state of the art ML models for risk profiling to an inventory of exposure risk assessment models

The R environment contains a large amount of modern and sophisticated ML routines, suitable for any application. Nevertheless, the direct use of all this ML routines is challenging, as these routines do not share a common interface/access nor workflow. Luckily the R-package *caret* provides us with a standardized interface and also workflow, to access and work in a standardize manner with the ML routines for classification and regression of more than 40 R packages. Additionally, *caret* makes it easy to support multiprocessing for almost all used routines.

The caret Package and its use is specified in the manual <https://topepo.github.io/caret/index.html> or in the book *Applied Predictive Modeling*, by Max Kuhn and Kjell Johnson.

Epidemiological studies are essentially classification problems. Classification problems itself consists of the following problems:

Over- and Underfitting; variance and bias trade-off

- linear vs. non-linear classification
- parametric vs. non-parametric classification

- High dimension low sample size problems
- Feature selection & Feature Importance
- Hyperparameter optimization
- Probability prediction & calibration

In ML the main focus is on the prediction, but in epidemiology studies the main focus is mainly in the determination of risk factors and their contribution to the problem at hand. As a result, feature selection and feature importance (feature aka co-variable, predictor) is of utter most interest for this work. For the selection, methods of subset selection, such as forward and backward selection, are the classical known methods with their known problems. More modern approaches as the Lasso (or L1) and the Elastic-Net regularizations, or feature selection via genetic algorithms or simulated annealing are not considered in the literature for the data analysis of epidemiologic studies so far.

If we want to estimate risk factor via Lasso or Elastic-Net regularizations, optimizing hyperparameter becomes very important, as these parameters will also influence which set of risk factors someone will obtain. Hyperparameter are parameter of a ML model, which cannot be estimated during the model training. For their estimation other methods known as grid, random search or more sophisticated methods like Bayesian optimization are necessary. Especially for the Bayesian optimization we engaged a Master student.

As we do not want to push a certain ML algorithm in front of all others, we screened all in *caret* available ML routines that are able to produce a probabilistic or probabilistic-like output, in total 149 routines. We found more than 100 routines that fitted our data. With that we also take a look on less famous ML routines, such as distant weighted discrimination or Gaussian processes. We investigate the found ML routines for their predicted risk factors and ability to predict the right risk.

Data

- Fromm et al., Prev. Vet. Med., 117, 2014 (fattening pig herds and MRSA)
- Hille et al., Pred. Vet. Med., (pig herds and ESBL)
- Colubri et al., PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 10, 2016 (Ebola survival)

JRP3-WP4-T1-ST1: Definition of the aims and requirements for literature research

- Selected suitable ML benchmark data sets, simulated data sets (in silico data sets) with known effect size, variability and interdependence (correlation), and AMR data sets provided by partners within RaDAR and other EJP projects. Some of these data AMR data sets will be provided in the future. In addition, a list of requirements for real data records will be finalized which is expected to guide our partners in the selection of suitable data sets.
- Evaluated the R-Package *caret*: The *caret* package (short for *_C_lassification _A_nd _RE_gression _T_raining*) is a set of functions that attempt to streamline the process for creating predictive models. The package contains tools for: data splitting, pre-processing, feature selection, model tuning using resampling, variable importance estimation as well as other functionality. The *caret* package will be used to set up an evaluation pipeline.
- Evaluation of the usability of ML for Small Data
- A review paper outlining the different risk questions related to AMR, interdisciplinary challenges in addressing them in a One-Health perspective, and how ML methods can be used for progressing beyond the status quo exists as a full draft and is under further development.

JRP3-WP4-T1-ST2: Decision on the model inclusion criteria

- Defined scores for quality assessment of ML result are under development
- Evaluated ML model robustness according to e.g. data splitting is under development.

JRP3-WP4-T1-ST3: Decision on how the models are to be represented (described for the end user) and development of a template

JRP3-WP4-T1-ST4: Repository setup including setup of a Github repository

Building a separate repository may be deemed superfluous given the existence of the Caret methods library on Github (<http://topepo.github.io/caret/index.html>) for which model evaluation manuals are readily available and a paper evaluating model performance on AMR risk models

3.2.6. WP5: The burden of disease caused by AMR exposure

We have modified these goals to take into consideration available personnel resources for WP5 and recent developments in the field [1]. Instead of producing actual, EU-wide, estimates for the disease burden of infection with resistant forms of two bacteria, this task will now concentrate on developing a suitable methodological framework for computing resistance-attributable disease burden, and comparing this methodology against other approaches. We also included source attribution into this WP (redesigned T2).

JRP3-WP5-T1: Identify data gaps and define target questions for SEJ (Structured Expert Judgment)

This task is redesigned to “**methodological framework for AMR burden**”.

We designed a new burden of disease (BoD) approach suitable for estimating the *excess* BoD associated with AMR bacterial infection. By ‘excess BoD’ we mean mortality and morbidity (computed as DALY) associated with resistance, over and above the mortality and morbidity associated with the same – but antimicrobial-susceptible – bacterial infection. We illustrate this approach for a single infection site (urinary tract) and a single bacterial agent (*E. coli*; extended spectrum beta-lactamase [ESBL]-producing compared with non-ESBL producing *E. coli*). We designed a methodology approach for estimating the BoD of urinary tract infection caused by antibiotic-susceptible and resistant *E. coli*. We modify an existing outcome tree (OT) describing the clinical progression pathway for UTI, and describe the separate transition parameters, disability durations, and disability weights that are needed to fully quantify the health consequences of infection with both susceptible and resistant versions of the same bacterial agent (Fig. 4). We have chosen the DALY as composite measure of departure from ideal health, and adopt the ‘incidence-based’ approach rather than a ‘prevalence-based’ approach to DALY computation. To arrive at a valid estimate of the *excess* BoD of UTI attributable to AMR, we propose to use a counterfactual approach. This involves simply subtracting the total BoD that is expected for antibiotic-susceptible UTI (using the ‘susceptible’ version of the OT), for the same number of incident cases, from the BoD computed using the ‘resistant’ version of the OT. A basic assumption of this approach is that the resistant form of UTI will lead to greater BoD, which may be driven by greater mortality risk, longer disability durations, and higher risks of developing long-term sequelae. Note that an eventual further step is required, for the purposes of RaDAR, to distribute/attribute the estimated excess BoD to various transmission routes, including the food chain.

[1]. Cassini, A., Högberg, L. D., Plachouras, D., Quattrocchi, A., Hoxha, A., Simonsen, G. S., ... & Ouakrim, D. A. (2018). Attributable deaths and disability-adjusted life-years caused by infections with antibiotic-resistant bacteria in the EU and the European Economic Area in 2015: a population-level modelling analysis. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*.

Fig. 4. Proposed outcome trees(s) for UTI, for antimicrobial-susceptible (upper panel) and antimicrobial-resistant (lower panel) infection. Transition probabilities (P) stratified by type of infection ([S]usceptible or [R]esistant) are indicated for several transitions, as are disability durations (DD).

Comparison of AMR burden methods

We compared the proposed method for estimating AMR-attributable BoD with the 'ECDC method' [1] in terms of data needs, assumptions required, and limitations/points of concern. Table 1 shows the data needs and differences in how DALY parameters are arrived at between the ECDC method and the proposed method for computing AMR-attributable BoD. The principal difference between methodologies concerns the type of 'input' data. The proposed approach requires directly measured incidence; in contrast the ECDC method applies the Rhame-Sudderth formula to convert point prevalence and information on days spent in hospital to incidence. The second main difference between the two approaches concerns the pre-calculation of AMR attributable mortality and duration (i.e., LOS).

For valid estimation of BoD *attributable* to AMR, it seems clear that the relevant steps of the BoD methodology must correctly attribute morbidity and mortality to resistant infection only. Control groups on which the calculation of attributable risk/effect sizes (progression and mortality probabilities, disability durations) depends must represent only patients with susceptible infection, and not uninfected patients. A fundamental limitation of the ECDC method is that incidence is not measured directly; instead the Rhame-Sudderth formula is applied to convert point-prevalence to incidence. This formula can lead to over- or under-estimation of true incidence, and although frequently used, its non-established validity raises questions about conclusions drawn regarding absolute incidence (as opposed to trend analyses or comparisons across countries, for which the formula's approximation to incidence appears more suitable). All methods suffer from confounding bias in the estimation of AMR-attributable burden, as patient characteristics (e.g., age, presence of co-morbidities, frailty, immunosenescence) can differ between those persons who acquire resistant form of bacterial infection and those who do not, and even if statistical adjustment could be straightforwardly integrated within the DALY computation, it would still be insufficient to correct for such differences due to unmeasured factors. Finally, when calculating attributable risks from longitudinal study data (for transition probabilities between health outcomes) or attributable mortality, it is vital to consider the impact of competing risks, such as discharge from hospital, death, or development of a complication that precludes observation of the health outcome of interest. The potential for erroneous transition probability calculations (usually over-estimated) is particularly high for patient populations at high risk of such competing events. It is not clear whether the reviewed studies used as basis for the ECDC transitions take competing risks into account, but the proposed BoD approach will apply appropriate methods when inferring the transition probabilities.

Table 1. Comparison of data requirements and assumptions for estimation of the burden of disease associated with AMR, comparing the ECDC approach (Cassini et al., 2018) with the proposed approach (see Methods). Note. AMR = antimicrobial-resistant; AMS = antimicrobial-susceptible; DALY = disability-adjusted life-years.

Data/assumption/parameter	ECDC	Proposed method
DALY approach	Incidence- and hazard-based; outcome tree starting with symptomatic infection	Incidence- and hazard-based; outcome tree starting with symptomatic infection
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Cannot use prevalence data directly	Cannot use prevalence data directly
Type of AMR case data	Point-prevalence survey for resistant bloodstream infection (BSI), adjusted for PPS coverage, converted to incidence using Rhamme-Sudderth formula [14]	Incidence data for resistant infection, obtained from yet-to-be-determined sources
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Catchment popul. size based on expert opinion. Known issues with validity of Rhamme-Sudderth formula	Most appropriate data type, but availability of suitable data may be problem
Conversion of incidence of BSI site infection to site of interest	Conversion factor based on ratio of cumulative incidence of BSI to site of interest, aggregating over all EU/EAA	Conversion not required
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Validity of conversion factor for individual countries questionable, as estimated incidence in all EU/EAA used	N/A
Definition of outcome tree (OT)	Developed from literature review and finalised by co-authors of HAI study [2]	Expert review and possible modification of ECDC-developed OT
<i>Limitations/comments</i>		
Transition probabilities	Literature review	Ideally setting-relevant longitudinal studies; if not available then systematic literature review and meta-analysis of progression risks, using pre-specified study inclusion criteria
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	No synthesis of evidence via meta-analytic or related methods; diverse study populations/settings combined	Required for two patient populations: those with AMR and those with AMS infection
Mortality/case-fatality	Attributable mortality risk (to adjust for comorbidities); from literature review	Ideally setting-relevant longitudinal studies; if not available then meta-analysis of published studies. Case-fatality adjusted for co-morbidities
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Derived from literature review that did not distinguish between uninfected and AMS comparator groups	Required for two patient populations: those with AMR and those with AMS infection
Disability durations	Attributable length of stay (LOS) in hospital, to adjust for comorbidities; from literature review	Ideally setting-relevant longitudinal studies; if not available then meta-analysis of published studies measuring length of stay. LOS adjusted for co-morbidities
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Derived from literature review that did not distinguish between uninfected and AMS comparator groups	Required for two patient populations: those with AMR and those with AMS infection
Disability weights	Adjustment for internal co-morbidity using multiplication method [15]	Adjustment for internal co-morbidity using multiplication method [15]
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Validity of multiplicative function	Validity of multiplicative function
Life expectancy (LE)	As published in GBD-2010 [17]	WHO projected LE for 2050 [18]
<i>Limitations/comments</i>	Description not present! (A. Cassini p.c.)	

JRP3-WP5-T2: Defining the seed questions

To be redesigned to “**Application of burden framework to UTIs**”. To be conducted in 2019.

JRP3-WP5-T3: Identifying, enrolling and interviewing the experts

Re-designed to “**Source attribution of AMR for attribution of disease burden to sources**”

Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase (ESBL) and plasmid-mediated AmpC (pAmpC) are enzymes produced by *Escherichia coli* (ESBL/pAmpC-EC) and other bacteria conferring resistance to important β -lactam antibiotics. ESBL/pAmpC-EC are increasingly reported in animals, food, the environment, community-acquired and healthcare-associated human infections following widespread antibiotic (mis)use, globalization, farming activities, and fecal pollution. Community-acquired ESBL/pAmpC-EC infections are usually preceded by asymptomatic carriage, with zoonotic (animal/food), environmental and anthroponotic sources remaining largely unquantified. Here we start to develop a methodology to estimate contributions of several putative sources to community-acquired ESBL/pAmpC-EC intestinal carriage through the application of an established source attribution model for foodborne pathogens based on nationally representative ESBL/pAmpC-EC gene frequencies, prevalence and exposure data. We made modifications to existing source attribution models by including bi-directionality of transmission and including humans as a source itself. The attribution will be based on ESBL genotypes encountered in human carriage and different livestock reservoirs and the environment. In addition, exposure weights based on exposure assessments are used to weigh transmission routes.

3.2.7. WP6: Integration of information by Bayesian evidence synthesis

JRP3-WP6-T1: Collect current status data

We made a descriptive overview of available Dutch data relevant for risk assessment and epidemiological calculations. For risk assessment, this will comprise of ESBL *E. coli* prevalence data but also data that describe the human exposure intensity to ESBL *E. coli*. For epidemiology, data relate to the distribution of ESBL genes of plasmids in the human population and in the respective reservoirs. Also, risk factors and epidemiological metadata are described.

JRP3-WP6-T2: Build evidence synthesis network for current status database

We built up a prototype evidence synthesis network for the pork chain as a multi-level Bayesian model, where parameters have initial prior distributions whose parameters in turn have prior distributions. This evidence synthesis model aims to estimate human carriage of ESBL-producing *E. coli* (EEC) in the Netherlands that is attributable to pork. This allows to manage the level of desired uncertainty and also to find the most representative values for some priors, e.g., uncertainty in the estimated average values on top of the spread around that estimated value. The code to perform the calculations is being written in R for JAGS. First, we built a network inspired by the analysis done by Evers & Bouwknecht (2016) and using the data of this tool. By means of the QMRA analysis there and Markov chain Monte Carlo simulations, we calculated posterior distributions for doses to which the population is exposed yearly. Information on the distributions is given as averages and for our code, we introduced Poisson and normal spreads as first attempt to deal with point estimates. We used a dose-response relation model based on a Beta-Poisson function, where the function parameters are loosely constrained and informed by data from challenge studies. For the Epidemiology side, we used information on

duration of carriage (distributions from Teunis et al., 2018) and ESBL carriage attribution to pork (expert opinion) to estimate distributions of incidence per year and prevalence. We joined the two approaches by using the so called zero-crossing method, where the estimated incidence of carriage from both QMRA and Epidemiology approaches is forced to be the same within a given standard deviation. Clearly, the two sub-models/approaches arrived at widely diverging estimates of human ESBL EC carriage attributable to pork (differing by three orders of magnitude), which suggests that one or both of the sub-models contains a heavily biased data source(s), or one or more of the assumptions underlying the connections between parameters (i.e., the models or part of them) are incorrect. Using the zero-crossings method to 'join' the two models was useful for diagnosis. It suggested two points of conflict: the ESBL-carriage fraction attributable to pork consumption in the EPI sub-model, which remains very uncertain; and the dose-response part of the QMRA sub-model not be appropriate for our purpose. This already indicates the major datagaps in our understanding and should be focus of more intense study (i.e. level of consumption/exposure to pork; and the ESBL EC dose-response). So far, we identified ESBL carriage attribution to pork and the dose-response relation as the culprits of a difference of three orders of magnitude between the posterior distributions for yearly ESBL carriage as calculated independently by the Epidemiology approach and by the QMRA approach.

JRP3-WP6-T3: Update evidence network for information developed in the other work packages

This work will start in 2019. The eventual aim is to integrate information from all exposure pathways and all health effects and in multiple countries, but to make the initial problem tractable we focus only on ESBL E. coli in humans attributable to pork consumption in the Netherlands. In addition, the WMRA part of the model will be extended to use information 'further back' in the pork production and consumption chain, and point estimates for certain parameters must be replaced with the data they are derived from (WP2 and WP3).

Fig. 5. Posterior density of for the number of yearly pork-attributable ESBL E .Coli carriages computed by both sub-models independently (EPI decoupled and QMRA decoupled) and the combined model using the zero-crossing method (Coupled model). The ratio of predicted carriage in the lower panel, defined as $\log_{10}\text{Ratio} = \text{NCarrQMRA}_{\text{pork}}/\text{NCarrEPI}_{\text{pork}}$, shows the difference between the model predictions.

3.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

3.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
RaDAR	D-JRP3-0.1	First annual report	12	12		Submitted in December 2018
RaDAR	D-JRP3-1.1	Establishment of a database of synthetic, reference and genomic data	12	12		Described in WP1-T1, paper will be submitted soon.
RaDAR	D-JRP3-1.3	Automated assembly pipeline integrating de novo plasmid reconstruction	12	12		Described in WP1-T2
RaDAR	D-JRP3-4.1	Model repository of state of the art ML methods for risk profiling available	12	12		<p>This deliverable has been fulfilled with online R-package; it is largely existing but has been added by us in order avoid duplication.</p> <p>We are using the R-Package caret, which provides an interface to a large amount of ML-Routines: https://topepo.github.io/caret/index.html</p> <p>The available Routines can be seen here: https://topepo.github.io/caret/available-models.html</p>

3.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
RaDAR	M-JRP3-1	Kick-off meeting and report	1	yes		Described in WP5-T1
RaDAR	M-JRP3-2	Identification data gaps and SEJ (Structured Expert Judgment) target questions	3	yes		Reference databases have been updated with recent publications
RaDAR	M-JRP3-3	Complete literature reviews of previous PK/PD and on-farm models (ANSES, APHA)	5	yes		Delayed due to awaiting appointment of PhD student
RaDAR	M-JRP3-4	Complete literature reviews of AMR transmission modelling (CVI, NCOH, RIVM)	5	Yes (12)		
RaDAR	M-JRP3-5	Defined seed questions	6	yes		
RaDAR	M-JRP3-6	Database of available data	6	yes		Model frameworks have been developed. A draft report on the framework for the on-farm model is currently in internal review with APHA and our national funders VMD.
RaDAR	M-JRP3-7	Develop model frameworks for PK/PD and on-farm model (ANSES, APHA)	8	yes		successfully held
RaDAR	M-JRP3-8	Mid-term meeting and report	12	no	13	Described in WP3-T1
RaDAR	M-JRP3-9	Structure for inventory of models and related data developed	12	12		Described in WP4-T1-ST4
RaDAR	M-JRP3-10	Repository filled with models on Github	12	12		Described in WP6-T2
RaDAR	M-JRP3-11	Functional consensus evidence network	12	12		Described in WP5-T1

3.4. Publications and patents

3.5. Impact & relevance

Antimicrobial resistance threatens the effective prevention and treatment of an ever increasing range of infections. It is an increasingly serious threat to global public health that requires action across all government sectors and society. Furthermore, resistance mechanisms emerge and spread globally. Containment of AMR spread is part of the EC action plan against the rising threats from AMR, and improvement of attribution and risk assessment activities should be encouraged according to EFSA. Circulation of antibiotic resistant bacteria in food and the environment and the resulting exposure of human beings to these bacteria may be significant. In general, information on the overall exposure to AMR from food and the environment is scarce. Therefore, efforts are needed to fill data gaps and systematically integrate data into consensus estimates for sources attribution, risks of exposure and disease burden. The relationship between environmental exposure to ARB and health impact is very complex. The current knowledge of this complex relation is very limited. A major reason for the lack of well-developed analyses might be the complexity of these approaches and their data requirements, and their interdisciplinary nature. This project will generate consensus estimates for sources attribution, risks of exposure and disease burden of AMR by integrating available data from various sources. Importantly we will deliver new methodology regarding approaches to AMR risk assessment, source attribution and disease burden that can contribute to a level of harmonisation across EU Ms. The most important aim of the RaDAR project is to adapt existing and produce new modelling methodologies to improve our understanding of the complex AMR problem. These include repositories of genomic data that can subsequently be used by other projects for various research questions (WP1), risk assessment and transmission models and frameworks (WP2 and WP3), comparison and evaluation of statistical methods used in the field of AMR research and suggest best practices (WP4), the (further) development of methods to estimate the burden of disease of AMR (WP5), and to develop methodology to integrate risk assessment and epidemiological models in order to identify datagaps (i.e. uncertainty) and to produce consensus estimates of risk (i.e. AMR carriage in humans) by data integration (WP6). All these activities have a strong focus on developing these methodologies rather than actually providing true answers, which very much depend on the data available and likely vary between countries. This provides the EJP network (and beyond) with state-of-the-art innovative model frameworks that can subsequently be applied in various contexts with the benefit that harmonized frameworks are used.

3.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

No ethical recommendations were given for the RaDAR project.

3.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No

Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information: /

3.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

In WP2, data of the EFFORT project will be used (Sarrazin, et al. (2018), Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy –). Different case-scenario will be simulated according to real on-farm usages in order parameterize the on-farm transmission models to be used for case-scenarios according to real on-farm usages.

3.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

No scientific dissemination so far in year 1. The progress so far has been disseminated to national policy makers who are highly interested in the RaDAR project which aligns with the governmental programs.

3.10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

Different members of the radar consortium will attend the annual meeting of the EJP One Health in Dublin, Ireland. In addition, RaDAR plans an open symposium at the end of the two year project which aims at dissemination of the produced methodologies to the EJP consortium and beyond.

4. MAD-Vir

4.1. Summary of the work carried out

The MAD-Vir project is progressing as planned. The project started with a Kick-off meeting held at SSI in Copenhagen (the 2nd of February 2018). In the initial project proposal, the microarray technology was only to be implemented at INIA, Spain and APHA, UK, however PIWET, Poland was very interested in learning the technology and because they already had all the microarray equipment and were able to finance the technology transfer without any additional costs to the project, it was decided to expand the technology transfer to PIWET also.

It was also decided that each partner in the project should select different samples from their biobanks to be tested at SSI with the PanVirus microarray (PanVirus array v2). A common sample pre-treatment/inactivation protocol was presented by SSI and it was decided that all participant should follow this protocol. For the 1st round of analysis SSI received 14 samples from PIWET, 5 samples from INIA, 10 samples from IZSAM, 16 samples from OIK, 8 samples from ANSES, 3 samples from VRI and 10 samples from IZSLER to be tested for virus with the PanVirus microarray. University of Surrey and APHA did not send samples to be tested in the 1st round (Table 1).

The 1st round of analysis detected 87% (52/60) of the samples tested (Figure 1). The samples that were not detected by the microarray were predominantly positive for West Nile virus (WNV) lineage 2, which indicated that probes for WNV lineage 2 on the PanVirus array v2 needed optimization. In addition, the testing showed that probes for Meaban virus were not present on the PanVirus array v2. A new version the PanVirus array v3 was designed and the non-detected samples were re-analyzed. The re-analysis detected the correct virus in 7 of the 8 samples (Figure 1) which in total give a 98% (59/60) detection of the samples from the 1st round.

On September 20th, a teleconference was held and all MAD-Vir partners participated with the exception of IZSAM. At the teleconference, it was decided to begin the 2nd round of analysis at SSI. All samples in the 2nd round were to be analyzed blindly; i.e., the investigators (SSI) should have no information about the virus present in the sample. For the 2nd round of analysis SSI received 25 samples from PIWET, 20 samples from INIA, 20 samples from OIK, 20 samples from ANSES, 20 samples from VRI, 20 samples from UoS, 17 samples from APHA and 46 samples from IZSLER to be tested for virus with the PanVirus microarray (Table 1). IZSAM has not yet sent samples for testing in the 2nd round. The microarray analysis of the samples from the 2nd round is ongoing.

4.2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

4.2.1. WP1. Coordination and management

Project management and coordination of the project is proceeding according to the plan.

4.2.2. WP2. Sample collection

Each partner in the project has selected different samples of interest from their biobanks to be tested with the PanVirus microarray in the 1st round and 2nd round at SSI. A common standardized sample pre-treatment/inactivation protocol was followed when possible.

To this date SSI have received 327 samples for testing, PIWET has tested 21 samples and INIA has tested 3 samples (Table 1). The samples are from wild life (rabbit, wild boar, duck, pheasant, stork, tortoise, hare, pigeon, springbook, deer, crow, *pteropus vampyrus*, partridge, eagle, owl, hedgehog and mouse), farm animals (sturgeon, trout, salmon, cat, goat, cow, chicken, horse, turkey, pig, sheep, and elephant), aedes, ticks, other insects and human samples (Supplementary Tables 1-4).

Table 1: Number of samples analyzed by PanVirus microarray

INSTITUTE	NO. OF SAMPLES			
	SSI 1 st round	SSI 2 nd round	PIWET 1 st round	INIA 1 st round Total
PIWET	14	25	21	60
INIA	5	20		28
IZSAM	10	0		10
OIK	16	20		36
ANSES	8	20		28
VRI	3	20		23
IZSLER	12	46		58
UOS	0	20		20
APHA	0	17		17
SSI	43	28		71
			3	
TOTAL	111	216	21	351

4.2.3. WP3. Diagnostic and surveillance

JRP5-WP3-T1: Technology transfer

SSI has made arrangements with Agilent Technologies so that INIA, APHA and PIWET can directly order the non-commercial custom made SSI PanVirus microarray v2 design and the new PanVirus microarray v3.1.

All standard operating procedures (S.O.Ps), microarray files for scanning and data analysis have been standardized and distributed to INIA, APHA and PIWET.

MWR (SSI) has visited the three reference Institutes and implemented the PanVirus microarray technology (INIA; 15th to 25th of April 2018, PIWET; 10th to 20th of June 2018, APHA; 25th to 26th of June 2018). Training in sample preparation, microarray technology and data-analysis have been performed at each Institute. The visit at APHA was shorter because APHA already knew the microarray technology and did not find it necessary to be trained in the technology. APHA has also shared its protocol with SSI to be compared at some point during the course of the project.

JRP5-WP3-T2: QA-validation

SSI has sent 12 virus positive samples (purified or non-purified inactivated samples) to INIA, PIWET and APHA for ring-testing (Table 2). All the samples were Quality Control for Molecular diagnostics (QCMD) samples from different test panels.

TABLE 2: RING-TEST OF SELECTED SAMPLES FROM DIFFERENT QCMD TEST PANELS

SAMPLE NO.	Virus content	Virus type	Ring-test no.1			
			SSI	PIWET	INIA	APHA
1	Zika virus	RNA	+	+	+	+
2	Chikungunya virus	RNA	+	+ ^{1,2}	+	+
3	Dengue virus type 2, West Nile virus, Yellow fever virus	RNA	+	+	+	+
4	Measels virus	RNA	+	+	+	+
5	Varicella Zoster virus	DNA	+	-	+	-
6	Cytomegalovirus	DNA	+	+ ³	+	-
7	Adenovirus type 1	DNA	+	+	+	-
8	Human herpes virus type 1	DNA	+	+	+	-
9	Parechovirus type 1	RNA	+	+	+	+
10	Mumps	RNA	+	+	+	+
11	Epstein-Barr virus	DNA	+	+ ^{1,3}	+	-
12	Human herpes virus type 2	DNA	+	+	+	-

¹very low signal

²low/strong signal during second testing

³low signal during second testing

In the ring-test INIA detected 12/12 samples, PIWET 11/12 samples and APHA 6/12 samples. APHA is not using the Standardized S.O.P that has been optimized to the SSI PanVirus array; instead, they are using their own protocol and data analysis method, which is not sensitive enough for DNA virus. APHA were aware of their protocol shortfall and they have since then modified several likely contributing factors and will re-test the samples using their new modified protocol. APHA has expressed that they will not use the Standardized S.O.P due to the cost of reagents and analysis time. Because of this, the PanVirus array cannot be harmonized among all partners but only among partners that use the Standardized S.O.P (developed for the PanVirus microarray).

Twelve new ring-test QCMD samples will be distributed among the participants in the beginning of 2019.

As an additional quality control the molecular EQA on yellow fever virus (YFV) organized by EVD-LabNet EVD-LabNet was tested at SSI using the PanVirus array v2 (Table 3).

Table 3: Testing of the molecular EQA on yellow fever virus (YFV)

QCMD-SAMPLE	Material	Virus content	Copies/vial	Detection by RT-PCR	Detection by PanVirus array v2
YFV 1	plasma	YF strain 17D	5,4x10 ³	+	+
YFV 2	Plasma	YF strain American	3,5x10 ⁴	+	+
YFV 3	Plasma	YF strain American	3,4x10 ³	+	-
YFV 4	Plasma	Zika, WNV, DENV	unknown	+,+,+	+,+,+, (+)
YFV 5	Urine	YF strain American	3,5x10 ⁵	-	-
YFV 6	Plasma	YF strain American	4,7x10 ⁶	+	+
YFV 7	plasma	Neg. ctrl		-	-
YFV 8	Plasma	YF strain American	2,8x10 ⁶	+	+
YFV 9	Plasma	YF strain American	2,8x10 ⁵	+	+
YFV 10	Urine	Neg ctrl		-	-
YFV 11	Urine	YF strain Africa	2,3x10 ³	-	-
YFV 12	Plasma	YF strain Africa	4,8x10 ⁵	+	+
YFV 13	Plasma	YF strain Africa	3,7x10 ³	+	+
YFV 14	Plasma	YF strain 17D	6,5x10 ⁴	+	+
YFV 15	Plasma	YF strain Africa	4,9x10 ⁴	+	+

The PanVirus array v2 performed similar to the in-house YFV RT-PCR assay and virus were detected in all samples except the urine samples (Table 3). The urine samples were negative in both assays, which could indicate that the integrity of these samples have been compromised during storage in the freezer. The PanVirus array also detected Parainfluenza 5 virus (PIV-5) in the Zika, WNV, and Dengue virus (DENV) positive sample (Supplementary Table 4). The presence of PIV-5 has not yet been confirmed.

In conclusion the PanVirus array v2 performed very similar to the in-house YFV RT-PCR assay and an additional virus was identified in one of the samples.

JRP5-WP3-T3: Analysis of samples

One hundred and eleven samples were included in the 1st round of testing at SSI (Figure 1 and supplementary Table 1), 21 samples at PIWET (Supplementary Table 2) and 3 samples at INIA (Supplementary Table 3). Of the 111 samples tested at SSI, 72 of the samples were expected to contain a known virus and 39 of the samples had an unknown viral content. The presence of virus could only be confirmed by PCR in 60 of the 72 samples with known viral content. The SSI and OIK confirmed the lack of virus present for five of the samples, which indicate a degradation of the samples while stored in the freezer (poor sample quality). The integrity of the remaining undetected samples remains unknown. The PanVirus v2 array detected the correct virus in 52 of the 60 confirmed virus positive samples with confirmed known viral content (87%)(Figure 1).

Of the PCR confirmed samples, the PanVirus v2 array did not detect 4 WNV virus lineage 2 samples, 1 Avian laringotracheitis sample, 1 Lassa virus strain av 2 sample and 1 TBE sample (Supplementary Table 1). These results showed that the probes on the PanVirus array v2 for WNV and Lassa virus needed to be optimized.

A new updated version of the microarray (PanVirus array v3) was designed which is based on the PanVirus array v2 and contain updated WNV and Lassa virus probes and the addition of probes for Meaban virus (not present on the PanVirus array v2). This new version also have probes for all new virus present in Genbank (June 2018) in addition to several specific probes for different fish virus isolates.

All the samples that were not detected by the PanVirus array v2, but confirmed positive by PCR, were re-analysed by the PanVirus array v3 (Figure 1) and all except the sample positive for Avian laringotracheitis were detected (Supplementary Table 1). In summary 98% (59/60) of the PCR positive samples in the 1st round were detected positive by the PanVirus array.

Figure 1: Overview of the results from the 1st round of analysis

Of the 39 samples with an unknown viral content, virus was identified in 13 of the samples using the PanVirus array v2 (Figure 1 and Supplementary Table 1). Many of these findings were confirmed by PCR (data not shown). However, validation of microarray results for unknown samples can be challenging and APHA has provided its willingness and support in validating new findings of microarray if the viruses fall within APHA remit and expertise.

Porcine Kobuvirus, Porcine enterovirus and porcine circovirus was identified in a blood sample from a wild boar, avian hepatitis B virus was identified in homogenates from internal organs from a stork. Human parainfluenza virus 3 and JC virus were identified in a human patient, and another patient was positive for VZV and JC virus. Uukuniemi virus and Blacklegged tick virus like virus were identified in a homogenized pool of Danish Ixodus ricinus ticks. The finding of Uukuniemi virus and Blacklegged tick virus like virus in Danish ticks is novel and a manuscript has been submitted to the Journal "Tick and Tick borne disease".

Thirty-two of the samples with known virus content also contained additional virus. For example: Exogenous mouse mammary tumor virus, Murine leukemia virus, Murine type C retrovirus and Spleen focus forming virus were identified in samples from WNV and Eyach virus isolates grown in mouse brain. DNase treatment of these samples showed that these virus originate from the endogenous retrovirus integrated into the mouse genome. Ovine enzootic nasal tumour virus, Jaagsiekte sheep retrovirus, Enzootic nasal tumour virus of goats were additionally identified in whole blood from Sheep. In two samples from Insect homogenate Ngewotan virus JKT9982, Nam Dinh virus, Houston virus, Hana virus, Dak Nong virus, Alphamesonivirus 1, Cavally virus were also identified. In an Astrovirus positive sample from the intestinal content from a turkey Rotavirus, Avisivirus and Gyrovirus were also identified. In a HEV positive fecal sample swine pasivirus 1, posavirus 1, porcine teschovirus, porcine stool associated circular virus, porcine kobuvirus, porcine enterovirus, porcine astrovirus, Parechovirus like virus, wild boar astrovirus were also identified. In a pool of organs from chicken and in a bovine fecal sample, several additional virus were identified. Many of these additional findings have been confirmed by PCR (Supplementary Table 1).

The results from the 1st round of analysis showed a great potential for using microarray as a screenings tool for unbiased identification of unexpected virus.

The 2nd round of analysis is currently ongoing and 129 of 216 samples have been analyzed (Table 1 and Supplementary Table 4). In the 2nd round the samples are analyzed blindly; i.e., the investigators (SSI) have no information about the virus present in the sample. Of the 20 samples received from VRI, 17 contained a known but blinded viral content. The PanVirus array detected the correct virus in all 17 samples (confirmed by VRI)(Supplementary Table 4). The correct identity of the remaining analyzed blinded samples are still blinded to SSI (to be continued).

4.2.4. WP4: Data Sharing

The common EJP website (<https://onehealthejp.eu>) is used for the MAD-Vir project. A private MAD-Vir group has been generated and all microarray results regarding the 1st round of testing has been uploaded to this group and shared between the MAD-Vir partners. Results regarding the 2nd round will be uploaded as soon as the analysis is finished. Other documents such as minutes, newsletters, summary reports, deliverables etc. are also present in the MAD-Vir group. All MAD-Vir partners have joined the EJP website.

4.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

4.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
MAD-Vir	D-JRP5-1.1	Kick-off meeting	6	29 th of June 2018		Deliverable available on MAD-Vir group of the OHEJP website.
MAD-Vir	D-JRP5-3.1	Implementation of MAD-VIR to INIA and APHA	6	29 th of June 2018		Deliverable available on MAD-Vir group of the OHEJP website.
MAD-Vir	D-JRP4-3.2	QA-validation of MAD-VIR to INIA, APHA and PIWET	12	17 th of October 2018		Described in 4.10. Communication and dissemination activities.
MAD-Vir	D-JRP4-3.3	MAD-VIR microarray analysis of minimum 500 samples	12	31 st of December 2018		Described in WP3-T2

4.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
MAD-Vir	M-JRP5-1	Collection of samples (minimum 750 samples)	12	yes		All partners have Biobanks/collections with samples of interest to be analyzed with the PanVirus array. A minimum of 750 samples has already been collected but not analyzed. Only 500 were to expected to be analyzed within month 12 (see D-JRP4-3.3)

4.4. Publications and patents

Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, Fuursted K, Nielsen HV, Andersen LOB, Bødker R, Fomsgaard A. Field samplings of *Ixodulus ricinus* ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV) micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark demonstrate an apparent disappearance of TBEV but a plenitude of other virus and bacteria. Submitted to Tick and Tick borne diseases 2018

4.5. Impact & relevance

The microarray technology implemented at PIWET, Poland and INIA, Spain have strengthened and improved a diagnostic platform currently employed in the institutes for detection of viral infectious diseases in animals. The knowledge and practical skills on microarray technique directly benefit a sustainable development of a diagnostic capacity of the institutes. Improved understanding in application of microarray-based techniques has provided a robust framework for future collaboration and research activities.

MEDILABSECURE (CoE Project 037 Ct Nº IFS/2013/330 961) (www.medilabsecure.com): INIA coordinate the animal virology network of the «One-Health» based MedilabSecure project, incorporating (in addition to animal virology) human virology, entomology and public health networks from 19 non-EU countries in the Mediterranean and Black Sea regions, aiming at improving diagnostic capacities and integrated surveillance for better response against emerging zoonotic diseases. The MAD-VIR project can assist in these efforts providing PanVirus analysis. CON 16-116 ; Experiments carried out in this project funded by the FNC “Fédération Nationale des Chasseurs de France” have yielded samples in grey partridges experimentally infected with flavivirus that are being used for the MAD-VIR objectives. CON 16-060 ; Experiments carried out in this project funded by the FNC “Fédération Nationale des Chasseurs de France” have yielded samples infected with flavivirus in European turtle dove that will be used for MAD-VIR objectives. RTA2015-00002-C02-01-E. Analysis of new West Nile virus encephalitis outbreaks in Spain and its geographical expansion. Field samples obtained in this national project are being evaluated with MAD-VIR microarray technology.

4.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm the national ethical approval for patient access and any adverse effect protocol as appropriate	<p>The MAD-Vir participants confirm that National ethical approval has been obtained.</p> <p>In Czech Republic (VRI) human patients has signed informed consent for the analysis.</p> <p>In accordance with the Hungarian Scientific and Research Ethics Committee; The Chief Medical Officer of Hungary approved the use of human samples and sending them to the SSI.</p> <p>All information regarding the diagnosis of HIV has been removed from analysis.</p>

<p>The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of biological samples have been sought</p>	<p>The MAD-Vir participants confirm that ethics approvals for the use of biological samples has been obtained.</p> <p>In accordance with the Hungarian Scientific and Research Ethics Committee; The Chief Medical Officer of Hungary approved the use of biological samples and sending them to the SSI.</p> <p>ANSES – Protocol evaluated by ANSES/ENVA/UPE ethic committee in February 2018, with a positive evaluation</p>
<p>The applicants must document the safety mitigation measures in place to protect the staff.</p>	<p>All samples are inactivated or purified before shipment. Inactivation is performed according to (Rosenstierne et al. 2016; Vinner et al., 2009)</p> <p>Samples provided by ANSES Animal Health Laboratory are handled in a BSL-3 laboratory, Icube ZO, conceived for the handling of class 3 zoonotic viruses. SOPs pertaining to the functioning of this BLS-3 are available upon request.</p> <p>The INIA-CISA group works in a high-biosecurity (BSL-3) laboratory compliant with the biosafety and biosecurity rules of the INIA-CISA (Biosafety Reference Laboratory for FAO). Biorisk assessment of the different pathogens used in the project has been evaluated by INIA-CISA Biosafety & Biocontainment service.</p>
<p>The applicants must confirm the compliance with GDPR.</p>	<p>The MAD-Vir participants confirm the compliance with GDPR.</p> <p>Data sharing between MAD-Vir participants is anonyms and coded with the name of the Institute and a consecutively number.</p> <p>All sample data in results sheet in the private group “MAD-Vir” at the OHEJP website are anonyms coded with the name of the Institute and a consecutively number.</p>

<p>The applicants must confirm the application of 3Rs and the ethical approvals (approval letters, etc) for animal work at a national / institutional level. The applicants must confirm how they will apply the 3Rs across the programme of work (e.g. clarify the sampling contribution in terms of numbers or endpoints, etc - Reduction management protocols for the programme, as well as the standard project level). Please elaborate. As appropriate this should include 3R protocols for feral / wild animals as well as laboratory animals (e.g. IZSLER).</p>	<p>The MAD-Vir applicants confirm that the application of 3Rs and the ethical approvals for animal work at a national / institutional level has been obtained.</p> <p>The samples from IZSLER included in the MAD-VIR project all come from diagnostic routine work that has been performed at Veterinary Public Institute to support the institutional stakeholders. None of the tested samples were obtained from experimental animals or experimental infections. Anyhow, even in such cases, all the experiments with animals should be previously authorized by Ministry of Health in agreement with the National Law “DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 4 marzo 2014 , n. 26”, which is the application of the European Law 2010/63/UE.</p> <p>Animal samples from INIA-CISA used for this project have been obtained from experimental procedures performed at the group’s lab (INIA-CISA). These procedures were approved and supervised by the Ethics and Animal Welfare Committee of the Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA) in strict accordance with the guidelines of the European Community 86/609/CEE.</p>
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4.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	NO
Delay in work plan execution	NO
Conflicts within the consortium	NO
Lack of commitment of partners	YES
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	NO
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	NO
Potential entry/exit of partners	NO
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information: In order to overcome the lack of commitment from the partners we have and will continue to intensify communication and correspondence to the partners.

4.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

MEDILABSECURE (www.medilabsecure.com), as described earlier

The Danish virology society (www.virologi.dk)

4.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	Press release		
Date:	April 20 th 2018		
Place:	www.SSI.dk		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release	yes	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	yes	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Implementation of PanVirus microarray at INIA</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>April 16th-25th 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>INIA, Valdeolmos, Spain</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Implementation of PanVirus microarray at PIWET</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>June 11th-20th 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>PIWET, Pulawy, Poland</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Oral presentation at PIWET (a scientific meeting gathering the institute employees and members of the Polish Society of Veterinary Sciences)</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>June 14th 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>PIWET, Pulawy, Poland</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Implementation of PanVirus microarray at APHA</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>June 25th 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>APHA, , Addlestone, UK</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Poster at the Danish Virology society</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>November 22nd 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

4.10. *List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year*

A MAD-Vir satellite meeting will take place at the 1st ASM in Dublin, Tuesday the 21st of May 2019 (face to face and tele conference combined)

Supplementary Table 1: 1st round at SSI

No	Name	Species	Material	Virus present	Array result	PCR Ct before/after WTA
1	ANSES 1	Turdus merula	brain	Usutu virus, Africa 2 lineage	Usutu virus	Usutu RT-PCR 22/18
2	ANSES 2	Caballus equi	brain	WNV, lineage 1a, Western Mediterranean clade	Negative	WNV RT-PCR no ct/no ct
3	ANSES 3	Caballus equi	brain or isolate	WNV, lineage 2	Negative	WNV RT-PCR no ct/no ct
4	ANSES 4	Ornithodoros maritimus soft tick	isolate	Meaban virus	Negative (PanVirus array v2)	No PCR assay at SSI
					Meaban virus (PanVirus array v3)	
5	ANSES 5	Tottori isolate	isolate	Japanese encephalitis virus, genotype 3	Japanese encephalitis virus, <i>Aedes pseudoscutellaris</i> reovirus, <i>Aedes albopictus densovirus</i> , <i>Aedes albopictus densovirus 2</i>	JEV RT-PCR 13/6
6	ANSES 6	Caballus equi	brain	Avian rotavirus	Avian rotavirus A, Turkey rotavirus A, Pheasant rotavirus A	Hum. Rotavirus RT-PCR no ct/no ct
7	ANSES 7	Cell culture	isolate	VEEV	VEEV	VEEV RT-PCR 16/4
8	ANSES 8	Ixodes ricinus	brain	Eyach virus	Eyach virus, <i>Exogenous mouse mammary tumor virus</i> , <i>Murine leukemia virus</i> , <i>Murine type C retrovirus</i> , <i>Spleen focus forming virus</i>	No PCR assay at SSI
9	INIA 1	Partridge	blood (dilution 1:10)	Usutu Virus	<i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus</i>	Usutu RT-PCR no ct/no ct

			in BA1 medium)			
10	INIA 12	Partridge	blood (dilution 1:10 in BA1 medium)	WNV Lineage 2	WNV lin 2	WNV RT-PCR 25/26
11	INIA 3	Partridge	blood (dilution 1:10 in BA1 medium)	WNV Lineage 1	WNV lin 1, Kunjin virus	WNV RT-PCR 27/27
12	INIA 59 (1#)	Mouse	brain, macerated in PBS (1:10)	WNV Lineage 1	WNV lin 1, Kunjin virus, <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Spleen focus forming virus</i>	WNV RT-PCR 28/34 Sample was tested with (#2) or without (1#) Dnase treatment after NA purification in order to verify the presence of endogeneous retrovirus
	INIA 59 (2#)				WNV lin 1	
13	INIA 63 (1#)	Mouse	brain, macerated in PBS (1:10)	WNV Lineage 2	WNV lin 2, <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Spleen focus forming virus</i>	WNV RT-PCR 23/24 Sample was tested with (#2) or without (1#) Dnase treatment after NA purification in order to verify the presence of endogeneous retrovirus. BUT the DNase treatment also removed the WNV signal !
	INIA 63 (2#)				negative	
14	ISZAM 4	Culex pipiens	supernatant of insect homogenate	Usutu virus	<i>Alphamesonivirus 1,</i> <i>Cavally virus,</i> <i>Ngewotan virus (JKT9982),</i> <i>Houston virus,</i> <i>Nam Dinh virus,</i> <i>Hana virus,</i> <i>Dak Nong virus</i>	Usutu RT-PCR no ct/no ct
15	IZSAM 1	Sparrow-hawk	supernatant of brain homogenate	West Nile virus, lineage 2	Negative (PanVirus array v2)	WNV RT-PCR 27/14
					WNV lin 2 (PanVirus array v3)	
16	IZSAM 2	Culex pipiens			<i>Ngewotan virus (JKT9982),</i>	WNV RT-PCR

					<p><i>Nam Dinh virus,</i></p> <p><i>Houston virus,</i></p> <p><i>Hana virus,</i></p> <p><i>Dak Nong virus,</i></p> <p><i>Alphamesonivirus 1,</i></p> <p><i>Cavally virus</i></p> <p>(PanVirus array v2)</p>	26/no ct
			supernatant of insect homogenate	West Nile virus, lineage 2	<p><i>Ngewotan virus (JKT9982),</i></p> <p><i>Nam Dinh virus,</i></p> <p><i>Houston virus,</i></p> <p><i>Hana virus,</i></p> <p><i>Dak Nong virus,</i></p> <p><i>Alphamesonivirus 1,</i></p> <p><i>Cavally virus</i></p> <p>(PanVirus array v2)</p>	
					<p>Ngewotan virus JKT9982,</p> <p>Negev virus,</p> <p>Nam Dinh virus,</p> <p>Houston virus,</p> <p>Dianke virus,</p> <p>Cavally virus,</p> <p>Alphamesonivirus 1,</p> <p>WNV lin 2</p> <p>(PanVirus array v3)</p>	
17	IZSAM 3	Crow	Supernatant of brain homogenate	West Nile virus, lineage 2	<p>Negative (PanVirus array v2)</p> <hr/> <p>WNV lin 2</p> <p>(PanVirus array v3)</p>	<p>WNV RT-PCR</p> <p>32/no ct</p>
18	IZSAM 5	Blackbird	Supernatant of brain homogenate	Usutu virus	Usutu virus	<p>Usutu RT-PCR</p> <p>22/not analyzed</p>
19	IZSAM 6	Sheep	Whole blood	Bluetongue virus, serotype 3	<p>Bluetongue virus,</p> <p><i>Ovine enzootic nasal tumour virus,</i></p> <p><i>Jaagsiekte sheep retrovirus,</i></p> <p><i>Enzootic nasal tumour virus of goats</i></p>	No PCR assay at SSI

20	IZSAM 7	Sheep	Supernatant of spleen homogenate	Bluetongue virus, serotype 4	Negative	No PCR assay at SSI
					Negative	
21	IZSAM 8	Culicoides imicola	supernatant of insect homogenate	Bluetongue virus, serotype 4	Bluetongue virus, <i>Caribou feces associated gemycircularvirus</i>	No PCR assay at SSI
22	IZSAM 9	Pteropus vampyrus	Supernatant of tissue culture	Pteropine Orthoreovirus	Pteropine Orthoreovirus, Melaka orthoreovirus, Pulau reovirus, Kampar orthoreovirus, Cangyuan orthoreovirus	No PCR assay at SSI
23	IZSAM10	Springbook	Serum	Rift valley fever virus	Rift valley fever virus	RVF RT-PCR 30/16
24	IZSLER 10	CAT	Intestinal content	PARVOVIRUS	Canine parvovirus, <i>Feline astrovirus 2,</i> <i>Feline leukemia virus</i>	Hum parvovirus PCR no ct/no ct Hum astrovirus RT-PCR 26/19
25	IZSLER 13	TURKEY	intestinal content	ASTRO +	<i>Turkey rotavirus A (all segments),</i> Turkey astrovirus, Turkey astrovirus 3, Turkey astrovirus 2, Turkey astrovirus 1, <i>Pheasant rotavirus A (5 segments),</i> <i>Avastovirus 1,</i> <i>Turkey avisivirus,</i> <i>Avian rotavirus (6 segments),</i> <i>Gyrovirus GyV7</i>	Hum astrovirus RT-PCR No ct/no ct Hum rotavirus RT-PCR No ct/no ct
26	IZSLER 15	BOVINE	Skin proliferative lesions	PARAPOX+++ PAPILLOMA +++	Pseudocowpox virus, orf virus, <i>Bovine papular stomatitis virus,</i> Bovine papillomavirus 2, Bovine papillomavirus 13	Parapox PCR 16/20
27	IZSLER 16 (1#)	HARE	Liver	LAGOVIRUS (EBHSV)	European brown hare syndrome virus	No PCR assay at SSI

28	IZSLER 16 (2#)	HARE	Liver	LAGOVIRUS (EBHSV)	European brown hare syndrome virus	Sample was tested with (#2) or without (1#) Dnase treatment after NA purification in order to verify the presence of endogeneous retrovirus
29	IZSLER 21	PIGEON	Intestinal content	ADENOVIRUS	Pigon adenovirus 1	Hum adeno PCR No ct/no ct
30	IZSLER 29 (2#)	CHICKEN	pool of organs	BIRNAVIRUS (INFECTIOUS BURSAL DISEASE VIRUS)	Y73 sarcoma virus, Turkey parvovirus, Rous sarcoma virus, Infectious bursal disease virus, Fowl adenovirus D, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 3, Fowl adenovirus 2, Fowl adenovirus 11, chicken parvovirus, Caribou feces associated gemycircularvirus, avian Sarcoma virus, Aviam myelocytomatosis virus, Avian leukosis, Avian leukemia virus, Avian adeno associated virus	No IBDV PCR assay at SSI hum ADV PCR no ct/no ct Sample was tested with (#2) or without (1#) Dnase treatment after NA purification in order to verify the presence of endogeneous retrovirus
31	IZSLER 29 (1#)	CHICKEN	pool of organs	BIRNAVIRUS (INFECTIOUS BURSAL DISEASE VIRUS)	Y73 sarcoma virus, Turkey parvovirus, Rous sarcoma virus, Infectious bursal disease virus, Fowl adenovirus D, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 3, Fowl adenovirus 2, Fowl adenovirus 11, Chicken parvovirus,	

					<p><i>Caribou feces associated gemycircularvirus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian Sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian leukosis,</i></p> <p><i>Avian leukemia virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian adeno associated virus</i></p>	
32	IZSLER 3	BOVINE	Faeces	ROTAVIRUS & CORONAVIRUS	<p><i>Sewage associated gemycircularvirus,</i></p> <p>Porcine rotavirus C,</p> <p><i>Porcine hemagglutinating encephalomyelitis virus,</i></p> <p><i>Nebovirus,</i></p> <p>Human coronavirus OC43,</p> <p>Equine coronavirus,</p> <p>Camel coronavirus HKU23,</p> <p>Bovine rotavirus,</p> <p><i>Bovine kobuvirus,</i></p> <p><i>Bovine hungarovirus,</i></p> <p>Bovine coronavirus,</p> <p><i>Bovine calicivirus (lena)</i></p>	<p>Hum rota RT-PCR</p> <p>18/12</p> <p>Hum calici RT-PCR</p> <p>no ct/no ct</p> <p>hum sapo RT-PCR</p> <p>no ct/no ct</p> <p>hum coronavirus OC43 25/16</p>
33	IZSLER 31	CHICKEN	pool of organs	HERPES (AVIAN LARINGOTRACHEITIS)	<p><i>Y73 sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>UR2 sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Rous sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian leukosis virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian leukemia virus</i></p> <hr/> <p><i>Y73 sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>UR2 sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Rous sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian sarcoma virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian leukosis virus,</i></p> <p><i>Avian leukemia virus</i></p>	No PCR assay at SSI

34	IZSLER 5	CHICKEN	Skin lesions (crusts)	ORTHOPOXVIRUS	<i>Avian Leukemia virus</i> <i>Avian leukosis virus</i> <i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus,</i> Fowlpox virus Penguinpox virus Pigeonpox virus, <i>Reticuloendotheliosis virus,</i> <i>Rous sarcoma virus</i>	No PCR assay at SSI
35	IZSLER 8	PIGEON	Intestinal content	REOVIRUS-LIKE	<i>Pigeon circovirus,</i> <i>Columbid circovirus,</i> <i>Human papillomavirus type 10,</i> <i>Avian carcinoma virus,</i> Chicken rotavirus G	No PCR assay at SSI
36	OKI 15	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	WNV lin 2, <i>JC virus</i>	WNV RT-PCR 31/32 JC PCR 34/17
37	OKI 18	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	<i>JC virus</i>	WNV RT-PCR no ct/no ct JC PCR 26/15
38	OKI 2	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	WNV lin 2	WNV RT-PCR 32/16
39	OKI 24	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	negative	WNV RT-PCR no ct/no ct
40	OKI 25	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	<i>BK virus</i> (PanVirus array v2)	WNV RT-PCR 38/19 BK PCR 30/21
					<i>BK virus</i> (PanVirus array v2)	
					WNV lin2, <i>BK virus</i> (PanVirus array v3)	
41	OKI 30	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	WNV lin2	WNV RT-PCR 26/14

42	OKI 35	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	WNV lin2	WNV RT-PCR 28/17
43	OKI 39	Human	urine	West Nile virus (lineage 2)	WNV lin2	WNV RT-PCR 25/11
44	OKI 53	Human	Serum	Unknown	negative	
45	OKI 54	Human	urine	Unknown	negative	
46	OKI 58	Human	Serum	Unknown	<i>Human herpesvirus 3 (VZV), JC polyomavirus, Micro Torque teno virus HD1, Micro Torque teno virus HD14 1, Micro Torque teno virus HD14, Torque teno virus 16, Torque teno virus</i>	Different samples from the same patient were pooled together on the same array. OKI 58 VZV PCR No ct/no ct
47	OKI 59	Human	urine	Unknown	<i>Human herpesvirus 3 (VZV), JC polyomavirus, Micro Torque teno virus HD1, Micro Torque teno virus HD14 1, Micro Torque teno virus HD14, Torque teno virus 16, Torque teno virus</i>	JC PCR No ct/ no ct OKI 59 VZV PCR 34/13 JC PCR 31/14
48	OKI 65	Human	Serum	Unknown	Negative	
49	OKI 66	Human	urine	Unknown	Negative	
50	OKI 81	Human	Serum	Unknown	Negative	
51	OKI 82	Human	urine	Unknown	Negative	
52	PIWET 1	Wild boar	serum	Unknown	<i>Porcine Kobuvirus, porcine enterovirus, Porcine circovirus</i>	EV RT-PCR 29/12
53	PIWET 10	Horse	serum	Unknown	Negative	
54	PIWET 11	Tortoise	internal organ homogenate (respiratory tract)	Unknown	Negative	
55	PIWET 12	Tortoise	internal organ homogenate	Unknown	Negative	

			(respiratory tract)			
56	PIWET 13	Stork	Homogenized internal organs	Unknown	<i>Duck Hepatitis B Virus,</i> <i>Heron Hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>parrot hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>Ross goose hepatitis b virus,</i> <i>Sheldgoose hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>snow goose hepatitis B virus</i>	Hum HBV RT-PCR no ct/no co
57	PIWET 14	Stork	Homogenized internal organs	Unknown	<i>Heron Hepatitis B virus</i>	Human HBV RT-PCR no ct/no ct
58	PIWET 2	Wild boar	liver	HEV gt 3	<i>Swine hepatitis E virus</i>	HEV RT-PCR 29/33
59	PIWET 3	Wild boar	liver	HEV gt 3	<i>Swine hepatitis E virus</i>	HEV RT-PCR 31/22
60	PIWET 4	Pig	feces	HEV gt 3	<i>Swine hepatitis E virus</i> <i>Wild boar astrovirus,</i> <i>porcine astrovirus,</i> <i>Porcine bocavirus,</i> <i>porcine enterovirus,</i> <i>porcine kobuvirus,</i> <i>rotavirus,</i> <i>Posavirus 1,</i> <i>pig sapovirus</i>	HEV RT-PCR 26/18 Rota RT-PCR 27/27 EV RT-PCR 25/18 Hum astro RT-PCR no ct/no ct Hum sapo RT-PCR no ct/no ct
61	PIWET 5	Pig	feces	HEV gt 3	<i>Swine hepatitis E virus</i> <i>swine pasivirus 1,</i> <i>posavirus 1,</i> <i>porcine teschovirus,</i> <i>Porcine stool associated circular virus,</i> <i>porcine kobuvirus,</i> <i>porcine enterovirus,</i> <i>porcine astrovirus,</i> <i>Parechovirus like virus,</i> <i>wild boar astrovirus</i>	HEV RT-PCR 28/19 Rota RT-PCR 27/22 EV RT-PCR 27/19 Hum astro RT-PCR no ct/no ct

62	PIWET 6	Rabbit	serum	HEV ra gt	Negative (PanVirus array v2)	HEV RT-PCT
					Negative (PanVirus array v3)	No ct/no ct
63	PIWET 7	Pig	feces	G4P6 RVA	<i>Sewage associated gemycircularvirus 5,</i> <i>Porcine parvovirus 2,</i> <i>Porcine kobuvirus,</i> <i>Porcine bocavirus 3,</i> <i>Porcine bocavirus 4,</i> <i>Porcine bocavirus 5,</i> <i>Po Circo like virus 21,</i> <i>Mongoose feces associated gemycircularvirus c,</i> <i>Mongoose feces associated gemycircularvirus b,</i> <i>Human genital associated circular DNA virus 1</i>	RVA RT-PCR No ct/no ct
64	PIWET 8	Pig	tissue culture	G4P6 RVA	Porcine Rotavirus A, Human rotavirus A	RVA RT-PCR 26/26
65	PIWET 9	Stork	serum	Unknown	<i>Snow goose hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>Sheldgoose hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>Ross goose hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>Parrot hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>Heron hepatitis B virus,</i> <i>Duck hepatitis B virus</i>	Human HBV RT-PCR no ct/no ct
66	VRI 1	Human	feces	Unknown	negative	
67	VRI 2	Human	Stool	Unknown	negative	
68	VRI 3	Human	CSF	Unknown	negative	
69	SSI 1	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	negative	
70	SSI 2	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	negative	
71	SSI 3	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	negative	
72	SSI 4	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	negative	
73	SSI 5	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	Blacklegged tick phlebovirus 1, Blacklegged tick phlebovirus 2	No PCR assay at SSI

74	SSI 6	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	negative	
75	SSI 7	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	<i>Blacklegged tick phlebovirus 1, Blacklegged tick phlebovirus 2, Uukuniemi virus</i>	Uukuniemi RT-PCR na/22
76	SSI 8	Tick (Ixodus ricinus)	Homogenized pool of ticks	unknown	negative	
77	SSI 9	Human	Lung secretion (T12107)	unknown	<i>Simian Agent 10, JC polyomavirus, Human parainfluenza virus 3</i>	Different samples from the same patient were pooled together on the same array.
78	SSI 10	Human	urine (T12074)	unknown	<i>Simian Agent 10, JC polyomavirus, Human parainfluenza virus 3</i>	SSI 9 PIV-3 RT-PCR 12/7
79	SSI 11	Human	EDTA-blod (M4176)	unknown	<i>Simian Agent 10, JC polyomavirus, Human parainfluenza virus 3</i>	SSI 10 JC PCR 30/11
80	SSI 12	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	CCHF ibar	CCHFV	CCHF RT-PCR 27/19
81	SSI 13	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	CCHF agf09	CCHFV, PIV-5	CCHF RT-PCR 28/22
82	SSI 14	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	EBOV Zaire	EBOV Zaire	EBOV RT-PCR 29/35
83	SSI 15	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	EBOV sudan	EBOV Sudan	EBOV RT-PCR 29/33
84	SSI 16	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	MARV popp	MARV	MARV RT-PCR 22/6
85	SSI 17	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	MARV mukose	MARV, PIV-5	MARV RT-PCR 26/20
86	SSI 18	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	LASV jos	LASV	LASV RT-PCR 30/26
87	SSI 19	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	LASV av2	Negative	LASV RT-PCR 31/35
					LASV	
88	SSI 20	EQA-panal	Serum spiked with MERS (#15)	MERS	MERS	MERS RT-PCR 18/6
89	SSI 21	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	Sin nombre	negative	Sin Nombre RT-PCR no ct/no ct

90	SSI 22	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	Seoul	negative	Seoul RT-PCR no ct/no ct
91	SSI 23	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	Puumala	negative	Puumala virus RT-PCR no ct/no ct
92	SSI 24	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	Dobrava	DOBV	DOBV RT-PCR 29/20
93	SSI 25	SSI Ctrl	Supernatant from cell culture	Hantaan	Hantaan virus	Hantaan RT-PCR 27/20
94	SSI 26	Tick (<i>Ixodur ricinus</i>)	Homogenized pool of ticks	TBE	Negative (PanVirus array v2)	TBE RT-PCR 29/34
					TBE	
95	SSI 27	Human	Biopsy from brain, (W25472)	ukendt	negative	
96	SSI 28	Human	EDTA-blod (63060)	HEV	Hepatitis E virus	HEV RT-PCR 28/20
97	SSI 29	Human	EDTA-blod (F34001)	HEV	Hepatitis E virus, Swine Hepatitis E virus	HEV RT-PCR 27/15
98	SSI 30	QCMD-panel	Plasma spiked with HEV (14-01)	HEV gg3f	Swine hepatitis E virus	HEV RT-PCR 34/16
99	SSI 31	QCMD-panel	Plasma spiked with HEV (14-05)	HEV gg3c	Swine hepatitis E virus, <i>Torque teno virus 1</i>	HEV RT-PCR 34/12
100	SSI 32	SSI Ctrl	Plasma spiked with Sindbis cell culture	Sindbis	Sindbis virus, Sindbis like virus, Ockelbo virus Babanki virus	Sindbis RT-PCR 35/no ct
101	SSI 33	Human	EDTA blood (M1057)	unknown	negative	
102	SSI 34	Human	serum/plasma (M1059)	unknown	negative	
103	SSI 35	Human	KF (S61939)	unknown	negative	
104	SSI 36	Human	serum	unknown	negative	
105	SSI 37	Human	EDTA blood (M1057)	unknown	negative	
106	SSI 38	Human	serum/plasma (M1059)	unknown	negative	

107	SSI 39	Human	biopsy (F54471)	unknown	negative	
108	SSI 40	Human	unknown (H14445)	Cowpox	Cowpox	Cowpox PCR 24/30
109	SSI 41	fox	NA from greenland foxes	Rabies virus	Rabies virus	Rabies virus RT-PCR 17/12
110	SSI 42	Human	serum (T21593)	unknown	TTV-16	Different samples from the same patient were pooled together on the same array.
111	SSI 43	Human	spinal (M12764)	unknown		SSI 42 : TTV PCR No ct/15 SSI43 : TTV PCR No ct/no ct

Supplementary Table 2: 1st round at PIWET

No	Name	Species	Material	Virus present	Array result	Remarks
112	Exp.4.Cy 51.1	cattle	faecal suspension	unknown	<i>Po Circo like virus 21,</i> <i>Bovine kobuvirus,</i> <i>Sewage associated gemycircularvirus 4</i>	New virus not confirmed by PCR
113	Exp.4.Cy 51.2	pig	faecal suspension	rotavirus group A, GXP[14] genotype	<i>Porcine teschovirus,</i> <i>Porcine rotavirus C,</i> Porcine rotavirus A, <i>Porcine kobuvirus,</i> <i>Porcine enterovirus,</i> <i>Porcine astrovirus 4,</i> <i>Po Circo like virus 51,</i> <i>Astrovirus wild boar</i>	Additional virus not confirmed by PCR
114	Exp.4.Cy 31.3	goat	peripheral blood leukocytes	Maedi Visna Virus	<i>Enzootic nasal tumour virus of goats,</i> <i>Jaagsiekte sheep retrovirus,</i> <i>Ovine enzootic nasal tumour virus</i>	Presence of Maedi Visna virus not confirmed by PCR

115	Exp.4.Cy 51.3	pig	faecal suspension	rotavirus group A, GXP[14] genotype	<i>Posavirus 1,</i> <i>Porcine teschovirus,</i> <i>Porcine kobuvirus,</i> <i>Porcine enterovirus,</i> <i>Porcine bocavirus,</i> <i>Porcine astrovirus 4,</i> <i>Astrovirus wild boar,</i> <i>Swine pasivirus 1,</i> <i>Porcine astrovirus 2,</i> <i>Porcine circovirus,</i> <i>Parechovirus like virus</i>	Presence of Rotavirus A virus not confirmed by PCR. Additional virus not confirmed by PCR
116	Exp.4.Cy 51.4	wild boar	serum	unknown	negative	
117	Exp.4.Cy 51.1	pig	serum + brain homogenate	unknown	negative	
118	Exp.4.Cy 3 1.2	rabbit	faecal suspension	rotavirus group A, G3P[13] genotype	Rabbit rotavirus A, <i>Sewage associated gemyrcircularvirus 4,</i> <i>Rabbit calicivirus</i>	Additional virus not confirmed by PCR
119	Exp.4.Cy 5 1.2	cat	tissue culture	feline calicivirus	Feline calicivirus	
120	Exp.4.Cy 5 1.3	cattle	faecal suspension	unknown	negative	
121	1	Turtle	internal organ homogenate (respiratory tract)	unknown	negative	
122	1	Turtle	internal organ homogenate (respiratory tract)	unknown	negative	
123	1	deer	DNA extracted from blood	bovine foamy virus (BFV)	negative	Presence of BFV not confirmed by PCR
124	1	Stork	RNA isolated from internal organs	Adenovirus type 11	<i>Fowl adenovirus 9,</i> <i>Fowl adenovirus 3,</i> <i>Fowl adenovirus 2,</i>	Additional virus not confirmed by PCR

					Fowl adenovirus 11, <i>Avian Leukemia virus,</i> <i>Avian leukosis virus</i>	
125	2	rabbit	liver homogenate	HEV ra (rabbit) genotype	negative	very low signals, experiments has to be repeated
126	2	cattle	DNA extracted from blood	BFV, BIV, BoHV-4, BoHV-6	negative	very low signals, experiments has to be repeated
127	2	wild boar	liver homogenate	HEV genotype 3	negative	very low signals, experiments has to be repeated
128	2	rabbit	liver homogenate	HEV ra (rabbit) genotype	negative	very low signals, experiments has to be repeated
129	3	wild boar	liver homogenate	HEV genotype 3	negative	re-analysed sample
130	3	cattle	DNA extracted from PBLs	BFV, BIV, BoHV-4, BoHV-6	negative	re-analysed sample
131	3	rabbit	liver homogenate	HEV ra (rabbit) genotype	negative	very low signals, experiments has to be repeated
132	3	rabbit	liver homogenate	HEV ra (rabbit) genotype	negative	re-analysed sample

Supplementary Table 3: 1st round at INIA

No	Name	Species	Material	Virus present	Array result	Remarks
133	INIA 3	Red-legged partridge	blood (dilution 1:10 in BA1 medium)	WNV Lineage 1	WNV lin 1, <i>Kunjin virus</i>	
134	INIA 59	Mouse	brain, macerated in PBS (1:10)	WNV Lineage 1	WNV lin 1, <i>Kunjin virus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Spleen focus forming virus</i>	Additional virus not confirmed by PCR
135	Usuv grey partridge heart	Grey partridge	brain, macerated in PBS (1:10)	Usutu virus	Usutu virus, <i>Reticuloendotheliosis virus</i>	Additional virus not confirmed by PCR

Supplementary Table 4: 2nd round at SSI

No	Name	Species	Material	Virus content	Array result	PCR confirmation ct-values before/after WTA	Confirmation by owner
136	VRI 1.2	Human	CSF	Unknown	Negative		
137	VRI 2.2	Human	CSF	Unknown	Negative		
138	VRI 3.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Human Herpesvirus type 1	HSV1 PCR 17/6	Correct, HSV1
139	VRI 4.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Zika virus	Zika RT-PCR 12/9	Correct, Zika virus (Africa)
140	VRI 5.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	TBE virus, <i>Spanish goat encephalitis virus,</i> <i>Negishi virus,</i> <i>Louping ill virus</i>	TBE RT-PCR 15/17	Correct, TBE (Neudoerfl)
141	VRI 6.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Louping ill virus, <i>Negishi virus,</i> <i>Spanish goat encephalitis virus,</i> <i>TBE</i>	No RT-PCR assay at SSI	Correct, recorded wrongly as Powassan virus
142	VRI 7.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Rift Valley fever virus	RVFV RT-PCR 24/5	Correct, RVFV
143	VRI 8.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	WNV lin 1	WNV RT-PCR 16/3	Correct, WNV
144	VRI 9.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	WNV lin 2	WNV RT-PCR No ct/29	Correct, WNV
145	VRI 10.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Porcine cytomegalovirus	No PCR array at SSI	Correct, Porcine cytomegalovirus

146	VRI 11.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	TBE, <i>Spanish goat encephalitis virus,</i> <i>Omsk hemorrhagic fever virus,</i> <i>Negishi virus,</i> <i>Louping ill virus</i>	TBE RT-PCR 18/17	Correct, TBE (hybr)
147	VRI 12.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Zika virus	Zika RT-PCR 11/7	Correct, Zika virus (Brazil)
148	VRI 13.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Infectious pancreatic necrosis virus, <i>Paralichthys olivaceus birnavirus,</i> <i>Marine birnavirus</i>	No PCR array at SSI	Correct, Infectious pancreatic necrosis virus
149	VRI 14.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Pestivirus type 1	No PCR array at SSI	Correct, BVDV
150	VRI 15.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Kyasanur forest disease virus, Alkhurma hemorrhagic fever virus	PanFlavi RT-PCR 16/8	Correct, KFDV
151	VRI 16.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	West Nile virus lin 2, <i>Spleen focus forming virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Friend murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Rauscher murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Abelson murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Moloney murine leukemia virus</i>	WNV RT-PCR 20/7	Correct, WNV 3 (99-222)
152	VRI 17.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Rabies virus, <i>Spleen focus forming virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Moloney murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Exogenous mouse mammary tumor virus</i>	Rabies RT-PCR 17/23	Correct, Rabies
153	VRI 18.2	Cultured virus	virus sample	Blinded	WNV		Correct, WNV

			cultured in cell culture				Lin 2
154	VRI 19.2	Cultured virus	virus sample cultured in cell culture	Blinded	Langat virus, <i>Spleen focus forming virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Mouse mammary tumor virus,</i> <i>Exogenous mouse mammary tumor virus,</i> <i>Abelson murine leukemia virus</i>	No PCR array at SSI	Correct, Langat virus
155	VRI 20.2	Human	CSF	unknown	Negative		
156	OKI/1.2	human	Serum	Blinded	GB virus C/Hepatitis G virus, Swine hepatitis E virus, Torque teno virus HD23	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
157	OKI/2.2	human	Serum	Blinded	Hepatitis A virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
158	OKI/3.2	human	Throat swabs	Blinded	Influenza A virus H3N2 2004	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
159	OKI/4.2	human	BAL	Blinded	Influenza A virus H1N1 2009	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
160	OKI/5.2	human	urine	Blinded	WNV lin2	WNV RT-PCR 32/18	
161	OKI/6.2	human	Serum	Blinded	Dengue virus type 1, <i>Torque teno virus type 16</i>	DENV RT-PCR 28/14	
162	OKI/7.2	human	Whole blood	Blinded	Chikungunya virus	CHIKV RT-PCR 32/18	
163	OKI/8.2	human	brain homogenate	Blinded	Rabies virus, <i>Spleen focus forming virus</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Mouse parvovirus</i>	Rabies RT-PCR 17/7	
164	OKI/9.2	human	Urine	Blinded	Measels virus, <i>Human papillomavirus type 107</i>	Measels RT-PCR 27/16	
165	OKI/10.2	human	stool	Blinded	Enterovirus A71,	EV RT-PCR	

					Coxsackievirus A5	31/12	
166	OKI/11.2A OKI/11.2B	human	Sample A: intestine homogenate, Sample B: Lung homogenate (2 samples from the same patient:	Unknown	Negative	Different samples from the same patient were pooled together on the same array.	
167	OKI/12.2	human	Throat swabs	Coxsackievirus A virus ,	Human coxsackievirus A6, Enterovirus A71, Coxsackievirus EVA, Coxsackievirus A6, Coxsackievirus A12	EV RT-PCR 23/5	Correct, Coxsackievirus A virus
168	OKI/13.2	human	Whole blood	WNV	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
169	OKI/14.2	human	Urine	WNV lin 2	WNV lin2, <i>Merkel cell polyomavirus,</i> <i>Human papillomavirus type 90,</i> <i>Human papillomavirus type 30,</i> <i>Human papillomavirus type 110</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	Correct, WNV lin 2
170	OKI/15.2	human	Urine	LCMV (?)	<i>JC virus</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
171	OKI/16.2	human	Whole blood	WNV lin 2	WNV lin 2	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	Correct, WNV lin 2
172	OKI/17.2A OKI/17.2B	human	Sample A: Whole blood (EDTA); Sample B: Urine (2 samples from the same patient:	Unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	Different samples from the same patient were pooled together on the same array. <i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
173	OKI/18.2	human	urine	Unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
174	OKI/19.2	human	Tracheal swabs	Influenza B Yamagata virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	Correct, Influenza B virus
175	OKI/20.2	human	Throat swabs	Influenza B Victoria virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	Correct, Influenza B virus

176	ANSES F1	18/280.2 Salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	(Cyprinid herpesvirus 2) Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
177	ANSES F2	18/280.3 salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
178	ANSES F3	18/280.4 Salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
179	ANSES F4	18/280.5 Salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
180	ANSES F5	18/361 Salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
181	ANSES F6	18/362 Salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
182	ANSES F7	18/363 Salmon	heart	Piscine reovirus	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, Piscine reovirus
183	ANSES F8	18/370 Sturgeon	gills	AcIV-E	(Cyprinid herpesvirus 2) Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		Correct, AcIV-E
184	ANSES F9	18/371 Sturgeon	gills	AcIV-E	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		Correct, AcIV-E
185	ANSES F10	18/372 Sturgeon	gills	AcIV-E	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		Correct, AcIV-E
186	ANSES F11	X1	Blinded	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		
187	ANSES F12	X2	Blinded	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		
188	ANSES F13	X3	Blinded	Blinded	Reovirus sp Salmo, Piscine reovirus isolate CGA280, (Cyprinid herpesvirus 2) Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		
189	ANSES F14	X4	Blinded	Unknown	Negative Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		

190	ANSES F15	X5	Blinded	Blinded	(Cyprinid herpesvirus 2) Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		
191	ANSES F16	X6	Blinded	Blinded	(Cyprinid herpesvirus 2) Will be re-analyzed using the PanVirus array v3.1.		
192	ANSES F17	X7	Blinded	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		
193	ANSES F18	X8	Blinded	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		
194	ANSES F19	X9	Blinded	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		
195	ANSES F20	X10	Blinded	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>		
196	APHA 1	Pig	Brain	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
197	APHA 2	Elephant	Heart	Blinded	Elephant herpesvirus 1	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
198	APHA 3	Elephant	Muscle	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
199	APHA 4	Pig	Heart	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
200	APHA 5	Turkey	Faeces	Blinded	Turkey hepatitis virus, Turkey gallivirus, Turkey rotavirus A, Turkey calicivirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
201	APHA 6	Pig	Lung	Blinded	Porcine parvovirus 6, Porcine circovirus 2, porcine circovirus 12a, porcine circovirus 1	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
202	APHA 7	Cow	Cell Supernatant	Blinded	Bovine respiratory syncytial virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
203	APHA 8	Cow	Cell Supernatant	Blinded	Bovine adenovirus A, Adeno associated virus 5	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
204	APHA 9	Cow	Cell Supernatant	Blinded	Bovine parainfluenza virus 3, Bovine viral diarrhoea virus 1, Pestivirus type 1,	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

					Simian Agent 10,		
205	APHA 10	Cow?	Cell Supernatant	Blinded	Porcine reovirus, Mammalian orthoreovirus type 2, Mammalian orthoreovirus type 3, Ndelle virus, Bovine parvovirus 1	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
206	APHA 11	Pig	Faeces	Blinded	Porcine astrovirus 4	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
207	APHA 12	Pig	Faeces	Blinded	Porcine astrovirus 4, Porcine bocavirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
208	APHA 13	Pig	Faeces	Blinded	Porcine stool associated circular virus, Porcine enterovirus, Porcine Bastrovirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
209	APHA 14	Pig	Faeces	Blinded	Porcine bocavirus, Po Circo like virus 21, Porcine stool associated circular virus, PoSCV Kor J481, (Porcine astrovirus), (Adeno associated virus)	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
210	APHA 15	Pig	Faeces	Blinded	Porcine stool associated circular virus 7, Porcine enterovirus, Porcine bocavirus, Astrovirus wild boar, Porcine astrovirus 4, Gorilla smacovirus, Fur seal faeces associated circular DNA virus, (Picobirnavirus)	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
211	APHA 16	Pig	Heart	Blinded	Porcine circovirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
212	APHA 17	Duck	Liver	Blinded	Goose parvovirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

213	INIA 1.2	pig	lung	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
214	INIA 2.2	pig	serum	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
215	INIA 3.2	pig	faeces	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
216	INIA 4.2	sheep	mesenteric ganglion	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
217	INIA 5.2	sheep	blood	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
218	INIA 6.2	grey partridge	heart	Blinded	Usutu virus, <i>Avian Sarcomavirus,</i> <i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus,</i> <i>Avian leukemia virus</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
219	INIA 7.2	grey partridge	kidney	Blinded	Usutu virus, <i>Avian Sarcomavirus,</i> <i>Avian myelocytomatosis virus,</i> <i>Avian leukemia virus</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
220	INIA 8.2	mouse	brain	Blinded	<i>Spleen focus forming virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Mouse mammary tumor virus,</i> <i>Exogenous mouse mammary tumor virus</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
221	INIA 9.2	mouse	brain	Blinded	<i>Spleen focus forming virus,</i> <i>Murine type C retrovirus,</i> <i>Murine osteosarcoma virus,</i> <i>Murine leukemia virus,</i> <i>Mouse mammary tumor virus,</i> <i>Exogenous mouse mammary tumor virus</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
222	INIA 10.2	red-legged partridge	feather pulp	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
223	INIA 11.2	mouse	brain	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
224	INIA 12.2	red-legged partridge	feather pulp	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

225	INIA 13.2	horse	brain	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
226	INIA 14.2	golden eagle	kidney	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
227	INIA 15.2	cinereous vulture	feather pulp	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
228	INIA 16.2	Barn owl	brain	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
229	INIA 17.2	Barn owl	kidney	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
230	INIA 18.2	Barn owl	heart	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
231	INIA 19.2	Barn owl	spleen	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
232	INIA 20.2	Barn owl	lung	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
233	UoS 1	European hedgehog	Faeces	Betacoronavirus	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
234	UoS 2	European hedgehog	Faeces	Betacoronavirus	MERS-like coronavirus, <i>Rotavirus A (cross hybridisation to many species)</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
235	UoS 3	European hedgehog	Faeces	Betacoronavirus	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
236	UoS 4	European hedgehog	Faeces	Unknown	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
237	UoS 5	European hedgehog	Distal Large intestine	Betacoronavirus	Hedgehog hepatovirus, <i>Alphaherpesvirus 1 (cross hybridisation to many species)</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
238	UoS 6	European hedgehog	Distal Large intestine	Betacoronavirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
239	UoS 7	Calf 6	liver	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
240	UoS 8	Calf 6	trachea	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
241	UoS 9	Cow 3	liver	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
242	UoS 10	Cow 3	Lymph node	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
243	UoS 11	Cow 4	liver	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
244	UoS 12	Cow 4	Lymph node	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

245	UoS 13	Cow 2	Lymph node	unknown	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
246	UoS 14	Cow 2	liver	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
247	UoS 15	Cow 2	respiratory epithelium	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
248	UoS 16	Cow 2	gastrointestinal tract	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
249	UoS 17	Cow 3	Gastrointestinal tract	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
250	UoS 18	Cow 3	respiratory epithelium	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
251	UoS 19	Cow 4	Gastrointestinal tract	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
252	UoS 20	Cow 4	respiratory epithelium	unknown	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
253	IZSLER 1.2	Chicken	intestinal content	Blinded	Turkey hepatitis virus, Chicken rotavirus D, Chicken picornavirus 5, Chicken picornavirus 4, Chicken megrivirus, Chicken astrovirus, Avian myelocytomatosis virus, Avian leukosis virus, Avian leukemia virus, Caribou feces associated gemycircularvirus, Rous sarcoma virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
254	IZSLER 2.2	Pig	intestinal content	Blinded	Sapovirus pig sav1, Sapovirus pig Gansu, Porcine teschovirus, Porcine sapovirus, Porcine rotavirus C, Porcine rotavirus A, Porcine kobuvirus, Porcine enterovirus, Porcine enterovirus 9,	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

					Porcine enteric sapovirus, Porcine astrovirus 2,		
255	IZSLER 3A.2	Goat	skin ulcerated lesion	Blinded	Pseudocowpox virus, Parapoxvirus red deer, Orf virus, Bovine papular stomatitis virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
256	IZSLER 3B.2	goat	skin ulcerated lesion	Blinded	Pseudocowpox virus, Parapoxvirus red deer, Orf virus, Bovine papular stomatitis virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
257	IZSLER 4A.2	bovine	skin proliferative lesion	Blinded	Bovine papillomavirus 5, Bovine papillomavirus 7	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
258	IZSLER 4B.2	bovine	skin proliferative lesion	Blinded	Bovine papillomavirus 5, Bovine papillomavirus 7	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
259	IZSLER 5A.2	rabbit	Liver	Blinded	Rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus, Rabbit calicivirus MRCV	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
260	IZSLER 5B.2	rabbit	Liver	Blinded	Rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus, Rabbit calicivirus MRCV	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
261	IZSLER 5C.2	rabbit	Liver	Blinded	Rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus, Rabbit calicivirus MRCV	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
262	IZSLER 6A.2	bee	whole carcass	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
263	IZSLER 6B.2	bee	whole carcass	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
264	IZSLER 6C.2	bee	whole carcass	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
265	IZSLER 7.2	chicken	intestinal content	Blinded	Turkey coronavirus, Sicivirus 1, Rous sarcoma virus, Pigeon paramyxovirus 1, Newcastle disease virus, Infectious bursal disease virus, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 2, Duck coronavirus ZZ2004,	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

					Chicken orivirus 1, Chicken megrivirus, Avian myelocytomatosis virus, Avian leukosis virus, Avian leukemia virus, Avian infectious bronchitis virus, Avian adeno associated virus		
266	IZSLER 8.2	chicken	intestinal content	Blinded	Pigeon avian nephritis virus, Rous sarcoma virus, Chicken astrovirus, Avian nephritis virus 2, Avian myelocytomatosis virus, Avian leukosis virus, Avian leukemia virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
267	IZSLER 9.2	pig	faecal swabs	Blinded	Posavirus 1, Porcine stool associated circular virus 1, Porcine kobuvirus, Porcine epidemic diarrhea virus, Porcine enterovirus, Porcine bocavirus, Porcine astrovirus 4, Po Circo like virus 21, Astrovirus wild boar	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
268	IZSLER 10.2	turkey	intestinal content	Blinded	Turkey rotavirus A, Turkey astrovirus 3, Turkey astrovirus 2, Turkey astrovirus 1, Chicken stool-associated gemycircularvirus, Caribou feces associated gemycircularvirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
269	IZSLER 11A.2	bee	whole carcass	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
270	IZSLER 11B.2	bee	whole carcass	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

271	IZSLER 11C.2	bee	whole carcass	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
272	IZSLER 12A.2	roe deer	skin lesion (crusts)	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
273	IZSLER 12B.2	roe deer	skin lesion (crusts)	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
274	IZSLER 13.2	chicken	intestinal content	Blinded	Sicivirus 1, Infectious bursal disease virus, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 2, Fowl adenovirus 11, Fowl adenovirus 3, Chicken stool-associated gemycircularvirus, Chicken rotavirus G, Chicken orivirus 1, Chicken astrovirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
275	IZSLER 14.2	chicken	intestinal content	Blinded	Gallivirus Pf CHK1 GV, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 2, Fowl adenovirus 3, Fowl adenovirus 11, Chicken gallivirus 1, Chicken anemia virus, Avian leukemia virus, Avian adeno associated virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
276	IZSLER 15A.2	bat	cellular culture (5°pass. VERO)	Blinded	Bat adenovirus 2	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
277	IZSLER 15B.2	bat	cellular culture (5°pass. VERO)	Blinded	Bat adenovirus 2	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
278	IZSLER 16.2	pig	faeces	Blinded	Porcine rotavirus B, Porcine kobuvirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

279	IZSLER 17.2	turkey	intestinal content	Blinded	Turkey rotavirus A, Turkey astrovirus 3, Turkey astrovirus 2, Turkey astrovirus 1, Duck associated cyclovirus 1, Caribou feces associated gemyrcircularvirus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
280	IZSLER 18A.2	chicken	pool of organs	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
281	IZSLER 18B.2	chicken	pool of organs	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
282	IZSLER 19.2	bovine	intestinal content	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
283	IZSLER 20A.2	insect (sandflies)	carcasses	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
284	IZSLER 20B.2	insect (sandflies)	carcasses	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
285	IZSLER 21.2	cricket	carcasses	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
286	IZSLER 22A.2	duck	pool of organs	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
287	IZSLER 22B.2	duck	pool of organs	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
288	IZSLER 23.2	chicken	intestinal content	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
289	IZSLER 24A.2	chicken	trachea	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
290	IZSLER 24B.2	chicken	trachea	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
291	IZSLER 25A.2	chicken	l. allantoid.	Blinded	Y73 sarcoma virus, Rous sarcoma virus, Gallid herpesvirus 1, Avian Sarcoma Virus, Avian myelocytomatosis virus, Avian leukosis virus, Avian leukemia virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
292	IZSLER 25B.2	chicken	l. allantoid.	Blinded	Y73 sarcoma virus, Rous sarcoma virus,	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

					Gallid herpesvirus 1, Avian Sarcoma Virus, Avian myelocytomatosis virus, Avian leukosis virus, Avian leukemia virus, Chicken anemia virus		
293	IZSLER 26A.2	bovine	skin	Blinded	(Herpesvirus)	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
294	IZSLER 26B.2	bovine	skin	Blinded	(Herpesvirus)	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
295	IZSLER 27A.2	bat	cellular culture (2°pass. VERO)	Blinded	Eptesipox virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
296	IZSLER 27B.2	bat	cellular culture (2°pass. VERO)	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
297	IZSLER 28A.2	bat	cellular culture (3°pass. VERO)	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
298	IZSLER 28B.2	bat	cellular culture (3°pass. VERO)	Blinded	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
299	PIWET 1.2	cattle	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
300	PIWET 2.2	cattle	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
301	PIWET 3.2	cattle	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
302	PIWET 4.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
303	PIWET 5.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
304	PIWET 6.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
305	PIWET 7.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
306	PIWET 8.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

307	PIWET 9.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
308	PIWET 10.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
309	PIWET 11.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
310	PIWET 12.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
311	PIWET 13.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
312	PIWET 14.2	pig	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
313	PIWET 15.2	rabbit	faecal suspension	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
314	PIWET 16.2	wild boar	serum	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
315	PIWET 17.2	wild boar	serum	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
316	PIWET 16.2	wild boar	serum	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
317	PIWET 19.2	wild boar	liver homogenate	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
318	PIWET 20.2	wild boar	liver homogenate	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
319	PIWET 21.2	chicken	spleen homogenate	Blinded	Fowl adenovirus D, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 2, Fowl adenovirus 11	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
320	PIWET 22.2	chicken	liver homogenate	Blinded	Fowl adenovirus D, Fowl adenovirus 9, Fowl adenovirus 3, Fowl adenovirus 2, Fowl adenovirus 11, Avian leukemia virus	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
321	PIWET 23.2	chicken	liver homogenate	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

322	PIWET 24.2	chicken	liver homogenate	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
323	PIWET 25.2	chicken	gizzard homogenate	Blinded	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
324	SSI 44	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 1 (strain 17D, plasma: 5,4x10 ³ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 37/38	
325	SSI 45	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 2 (strain American, plasma: 3,54x10 ⁴ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 33/22	
326	SSI 46	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 3 (strain American, plasma: 3,4x10 ³ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 36/27	
327	SSI 47	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 4 (Zika, WNV, DENV positiv)	Zika virus, WNV, Dengue virus	Zika virus, West Nile virus 1, <i>Parainfluenza virus 5,</i> <i>Kunjin virus,</i> DENV 4, DENV 3, DENV2, DENV 1, <i>Usutu virus</i>	Zika RT-PCR 27/13 WNV RT-PCR 26/10 DENV RT-PCR 27/19 Usutu RT-PCR 34/31	
328	SSI 48	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 5 (strain American, urine: 3,54x10 ⁵ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Negativ	RT-PCR No ct/no ct	
329	SSI 49	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 6 (strain American, plasma: 4,7x10 ⁶ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	Rt-PCR 27/not tested	
330	SSI 50	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 7 (neg ctrl plasma)	Negative	Negative		

331	SSI 51	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 8 (strain American, plasma: 2,8x10 ⁶ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 24/7	
332	SSI 52	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 9 (strain American, plasma: 2,8x10 ⁵ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 28/18	
333	SSI 53	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 10 (neg ctrl urine)	Negativ	Negative		
334	SSI 54	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 11 (strain American, urine: 2,3x10 ³ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Negative	RT-PCR No ct/no ct	
335	SSI 55	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 12 (strain Africa, plasma: 4,75x10 ⁵ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 27/17	
336	SSI 56	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 13 (strain Africa, plasma: 3,7x10 ³ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 33/38	
337	SSI 57	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 14 (strain 17D, plasma: 6,5x10 ⁴ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 31/21	
338	SSI 58	2018 EVD-LabNet YF panel	YF 15 (strain Africa, plasma: 4,9x10 ⁴ copies/vial)	Yellow fever virus	Yellow fever virus	RT-PCR 30/35	
339	SSI 59	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 1 : Toscana lineage A (1,75x10 ⁵ copies/0,4ml)	Toscana lineage A	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
340	SSI 60	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 2 : Toscana lineage B (1,24x10 ⁵ copies/0,4ml)	Toscana lineage B	Negativ	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
341	SSI 61	2017 EVD-LabNet	Neuro 3 : TBE	TBE	TBE	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

		neutropisk panel	(5,06x10 ⁴ copies/0,4ml)				
342	SSI 62	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 4 : WNV lineage 1 (7,2x10 ⁴ copies/0,4ml)	WNV lineage 1	WNV lin 1, <i>Kunjin virus</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
343	SSI 63	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 5 : WNV lineage 2 (4.96x10 ⁵ copies/0,4ml)	WNV lineage 2	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
344	SSI 64	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 6 : Usutu (6.34x10 ³ copies/0,4ml)	Usutu	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
345	SSI 65	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 7 : neg ctrl plasma	Negativ	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
346	SSI 65	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 8 : neg ctrl plasma	Negativ	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
347	SSI 67	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 9 : neg ctrl plasma	Negativ	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
348	SSI 68	2017 EVD-LabNet neutropisk panel	Neuro 10 : neg ctrl plasma	Negativ	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
349	SSI 69	Panel Corona 18S05		HKU1 corona virus	Negative	RT-PCR No ct/no ct	
350	SSI 70	R2011	Spinal	Unknown	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	
351	SSI 71	R2011	EDTA-blod	Unknown	Negative	<i>Not analyzed yet !</i>	

5. TOX-Detect

5.1. Summary of the work carried out

The kick-off meeting has been organized from 28th of February to the 1st of March 2018. After general information dedicated to the architecture of the EJP, elements of reporting and budget, a focus on the work package dedicated to the selection of bacterial strains has been discussed.

The project brings together five leading institutions from EU and Norway to work together on three pathogens (ie. CPS, *Bacillus cereus* and *Clostridium perfringens*) which are responsible for a large number of food-poisoning outbreaks (FPOs) in the European Union. FPOs caused by toxigenic bacteria share a common symptomatology that makes outbreak investigation challenging. As a consequence, the proportion of “weak evidence” FPOs is particularly high in case of bacterial toxins being the causative agent. The ultimate goal of this project is to fill the dramatic gaps of lacking methodologies to detect bacterial toxins, moreover characterize foodborne toxigenic bacteria, consequently contributing to an increased consumer health protection. Proteomics approaches based on liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization coupled to time-of-flight detectors (MALDI-ToF), and immune-enzymatic methods will be developed and implemented in this Tox-Detect project in view of their possible use for toxins/virulence factors detection and characterization. Ring trials between partners and collaborators will be organized for evaluation purposes, to assess, and to optimize the performance of the developed methods.

The aim of the KO meeting was to select 30 strains for each species studied in the Tox-Detect project (CPS, Bc and Cp). A previously designed table has been prepared by the WPL in agreement with partners. This table contained relevant data including, origin, characterisation, vigilance factors. Partners had to complete this table by suggesting strains from the collections available in their institutions. A total of 80 CPS, 90 Bc and 54 Cp strains have been proposed.

From this proposal, about 30 reference strains that will be used for further studies in Tox-Detect project had to be selected according to different criteria with agreement of partners (origin, virulence factors...).

For CPS, the aim was to develop Ab against SEG and SEH toxins. However, recently, partners not involved in EJP projects implemented the ELISA method dedicated to the detection of toxins type SEG and SEH. In order to avoid overlapping the EU projects, EJP Tox-Detect project and WP4 coordinators decided to develop Ab against SEM, SEN, SEO and to produce their types of toxins using cell-free system. Studies carried out using NGS techniques showed that these genes (sem, sen and seo) are highly found in food borne outbreaks occurred in Europe. 13 strains encoding for SEM, SEN and SEO and a negative control (CIP 53.154) have been selected in the frame of WP1.

For Bc and Cp dedicated separated meetings were organized to select the most relevant strains. Despite losses of critical staffs in two partners (P1 and P4), all the planed work but MalDI-TOF reference spectra library was performed in due time during this first year of the TOX-DETECT project.

5.2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

5.2.1. WP0. Coordination, management and communication

JRP4-WP0-T1: General coordination and management of the project (administrative and financial)

The overall purpose of the management structure is to ensure the timely implementation of the tasks and the smooth running of the project as a whole. Its primary goal is to identify arising opportunities and detect the occurrence of obstacles as early as possible, hence maximise the outcome of the project while preventing delays in its implementation. This will ensure that all tasks and research objectives are performed in due time.

The WP0 organized TC meetings when appropriate, the Kick off meeting and 3 face to face meetings especially on WP1.

JRP4-WP0-T2 to JRP4-WP0-T5: Organisation of four face-to-face meetings with all partners.

Only T0.2 on “The kick-off meeting. Discussion of criteria to select bacterial strains. Discussion of organization of interlaboratory trials “ was planned on 2018.

The Tox-Detect kick-off meeting held in Maisons-Alfort (France) from 28th of February to the 1st of March 2018 (M3). 16 participants representing all Tox-Detect partners were present during the kick-off meeting. All participants presented their institutions, activities and involvement in the Tox-Detect project. The kick-off-meeting was the first meeting of all project partners. The meeting was split into two half days.

The aims of the Tox-Detect Project kick-off-meeting were:

- to introduce all project members;
- to get information on administrative and financial issues by representatives of EJP coordination team;
- to give an overview of the aims of the project and provide detailed information on all work packages;
- to discuss open questions on the selection of the reference strains that should be used in this project
- to vote the logo of the project

JRP4-WP0-T6: mandatory reports on network activities: interim activity report, final report

The 9 month report has been dispatched by the end of august.

5.2.2. WP1. Constitution of a reference strain collection for *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*

JRP4-WP1-T1: Constitution of *S. aureus* strains collection

80 *S. aureus* strains have been proposed by Tox-Detect partners, representing human and food categories. The major part was issued from food poisoning outbreaks. For CPS, the aim was to develop Ab against SEG and SEH toxins. 13 strains encoding for SEG and SEH and a negative control (CIP 53.154) have been selected. As development of recombinant toxins SEG and SEH has been already initiated, it has been decided to also focus on toxins SEM, SEN, SEO to produce these types of toxins using cell-free system.

JRP4-WP1-T2: Constitution of *B. cereus* strains collection

90 *Bacillus* (Bc) strains have been proposed by Tox-Detect partners, representing human and food categories. This meeting does not able to perform a selection of relevant strains; it was decided to organize a dedicated meeting for this topic on 12th March 2018 at Partner 19 location. This dedicated meeting enabled to select both virulence factors to be tested and associated Bc strains. Therefore, 21 strains were selected.

JRP4-WP1-T3: Constitution of *C. perfringens* strains collection

54 *C. perfringens* (Cp) strains have been proposed by Tox-Detect partners, representing human and food categories. For Cp, as it was not possible to cover this topic during the Kick-of meeting. Another dedicated meeting has been planned on 22nd of March 2018. This dedicated meeting enabled to select both virulence factors to be tested and associated Cp strains. Therefore, 40 strains were selected representing human, food and environmental categories. All strains were selected on the base of the production or not of CPE.

JRP4-WP1-T4: Transfer of libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra

This task was launched on M3, TC meeting was organized on 16th May 2017. In order to create a database of protein profiles with the strains chosen in WP1-T1, T2, and T3, biomasses will be prepared by the partners who hold the strains. These biomasses will then be sent to Anses partner (Benoît Gassilloud) to perform spectra. Each partner will have to sign a material transfer agreement (MTA) before sending biomasses. The protocol to prepare biomasses was discussed and dispatched to the involved partners. After analysis of the selected reference strains, MALDI-TOF libraries will be established and dispatched to TOX-Detect partners.

Each partner has to fill its own MTA to dispatch strain extract for MALDI-TOF analysis.

5.2.3. WP2 Characterization of toxins/virulence factors

JRP4-WP2-T1: Characterization of candidate toxin and/or virulence genes using toxicity tests

This task was launched on M4. The growth conditions of the strains as well as the cytotoxicity assays were discussed between partners. 21 *B. cereus* strains and 40 *C. perfringens* strains were selected on the May 28, 2018. Supernatants of the selected reference strains were collected and cytotoxicity assays were performed on a selection of strain supernatant. The protocols were exchanged between partners. A meeting was organized on August 29 between partners involved in the WP2 and the coordinators.

JRP4-WP2-T2: Assessment of virulence and toxin gene expression using RT-PCR and transcriptomic assays

Not relevant

JRP4-WP2-T2-ST1: Optimization of growth conditions to be used for gene expression analysis

This task was launched on M5. The protocols of bacterial growth and RNA extraction were optimized. Various growth conditions are currently tested for *B. cereus*.

JRP5-WP2-T2-ST2: Development of RT-PCR assays and transcriptomic analysis

The protocols for RT-PCR are under optimization.

5.2.4. WP3: Development of Mass Spectrometry-based proteomics procedures for detection of bacterial toxins and virulence factors

JRP4-WP3-T1: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins (eg SEG, SEH, SEI) from *S. aureus*

Two TC (February, 22 and November 28) have been organized between partners.

JRP4-WP3-T2: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *B. cereus*

JRP4-WP3-T3: Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *C. perfringens*

5.2.5. WP4: Development of new immuno-enzymatic assays for detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence determinants

JRP4-WP4-T1: Development of quantitative immunoassays for five known *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence factors

One face-to-face meeting took place in Berlin (September 5) involving Anses and BfR.

The first year WP4 meeting was held on November 8th with the two partners involved and the coordinators represented by Stephen Marino and Hendrik Frentzel (BfR), Michel Gohar (INRA Micalis), Jacques-Antoine Hennekinne and Yacine Nia (Anses Maison-Alfort).

WP4 aims at the development of ELISA assays against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus* toxins.

JRP4-WP4-T1-ST1: Selection of 5 target genes and construction of genetic tools for proteins overexpression

The toxins which should be targeted by these assays were selected during the 2018 March kickoff meeting for both species: Staphylococcal Enterotoxins (SEs) SEM, SEN and SEO for *S. aureus*; Nhe, CytK1 and Smase for *B. cereus*.

Regulatory issues have delayed the cloning of *S. aureus* toxins sequences. *S. aureus* toxins are indeed considered as highly toxic – particularly the type B enterotoxin - and regulatory authorities in Germany (the Landesamt für Gesundheit und Soziales, <LaGeSo> and the Zentrale Kommission für die Biologische Sicherheit, <ZKBS>) wanted to evaluate the conditions under which the BfR can be permitted to produce the proteins in the available laboratory facilities. An answer was released the 12th of December, allowing BfR to proceed to *S. aureus* toxins production, but with increased security conditions requiring specific laboratory equipment, which will be implemented from now to the beginning of 2019.

In the meantime, an *S. aureus* strain harboring full length genes for SEM, N and O has been selected from the BfR strain collection and all three genes have been successfully amplified from genomic DNA by PCR (see Figure 1), so that cloning of the SEs can start immediately. Also, internal BfR process for contracting a company to produce antibodies using the BfR purified SEs has been initiated. Therefore, no delays in meeting the future scheduled milestones are expected.

A

B

Figure 1. A) Workflow for WP4 BfR Task 1 (Subtasks 1.1 – 1.3); already accomplished steps are indicated in green text. B) 1,5% agarose gel of SE PCR products; all three target SE genes (SEM, N and O) were amplified from the target *S. aureus* strain and have the expected size.

Similarly, the work on *B. cereus* was delayed due to the unavailability of the strains reference collection.

As a consequence, an alternative collection had to be assembled. This collection includes the following strains:

- F4370/75 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, barbecued chicken
- F2769/77 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, lobster plate
- F352/90 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, chow mein
- F284/78 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, pork pie
- NVH1651/00 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, caramel pudding
- F4433/73 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, meat loaf
- NVH0597/99 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, spice mix
- NVH0075/95 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, stew with vegetables
- NVH1230/88 diarrheal food poisoning outbreak, oriental stew

The cloning work of the selected targets (cytK2, Sphingomyelinase and Nhe genes) will start at the beginning of 2019.

The WP4 task 1 is therefore delayed by 6 months but is still manageable within the project timeframe.

JRP4-WP4-T1-ST2: Proteins production

Not relevant

JRP5-WP4-T1-ST3: Development of specific Ab (poly/monoclonal)

Not relevant. Only PAb will be developed in this sub task 3.

5.2.6. WP6. Dissemination, protection and exploitation of results

JRP4-WP6-T1: dissemination of information within the partners

WP0 prepared various documents including contact list, logo, ppt template to promote Tox-Detect activities. All these documents were joined as annexes to the minutes of the KO meeting (M12)

JRP4-WP6-T2: dissemination of information to the outside

An overview of the Tox-Detect project has been presented during the annual workshop of the NRL for CPS which took place in Maisons-Alfort from May 30 to June 2, 2018.

Another presentation of this project has been performed during a tri lateral meeting involving Germany (RKI, Berlin), Switzerland (Agroscope, Spiez Lab, Bern) and France (CEA and Anses). This meeting took place at Agroscope (Bern, Switzerland) on May 24, 2018.

Finally, a slide presenting the overview of the Tox-Detect project has been presented during Food Micro conference (Berlin, Germany) on September 3, 2018.

5.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

5.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
Tox-Detect	D-JRP4-0.1	Report of the kick-off meeting	3	/	12	The K-O off meeting was organized on M3. Minutes of KO was dispatched on M12
Tox-Detect	D-JRP4-1.1	List of well characterized reference strains of <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	3	5	/	done
Tox-Detect	D-JRP4-1.2	Libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra	3	/	18	It was proposed to postpone this deliverable until the analyse of reference strains selected in D1.1. Analyses will be performed during 2019 after reception of strains and MTA.

5.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
Tox-Detect	M-JRP4-01	General decision on criteria to select strains	3	Yes		Discussed during TC conference 17 th January 2018
Tox-Detect	M-JRP4-02	General discussion on interlaboratory trial scheme	3	Yes		Discussed during KO meeting on 1 st March 2018
Tox-Detect	M-JRP4-03	Construction of the reference strains of <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	3	Yes		Diffused by email to partners on 28/05/2018
Tox-Detect	M-JRP4-04	Exchange of libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra	3	No	18	Additional analysis by Maldi-TOF is necessary before exchange of libraries. TC organized with coordinators and WP Leader on 16 th May 2018 Protocol extractions have been discussed, defined and shared among partners on November 2018. Partners have to perform extraction before sending extracts to MALDI-ToF platform (early 2019).
Tox-Detect	M-JRP4-05	Reference materials available	5	No	18	Reference strains are available for WPs depending on the availability of MTA and results of M-JRP4-04.

5.4. Publications and patents

None

5.5. Impact & relevance

Through WP1, interdisciplinary collaboration is demonstrated because a large panel of bacterial strains from human, animal and food origin were selected in the respective collections of the partners. Protocols to prepare supernatants and biomasses in order to test cytotoxicity and to perform MALDI-ToF mass spectrometry were shared between the partners. This first and crucial step was a pre requisite to achieve the overall goal ie develop tools and characterization schemes of bacterial producing toxins.

A common meeting with partners of another H2020 project (EuroBioTox) was organised on May 24 to avoid overlapping of activities and to share roadmaps.

5.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm the source of tissues.	Cell lines from American Tissue Culture Collection (ATCC) : colon Caco2 cells
The applicants must document the safety mitigation measures in place to protect the staff.	BSL2 working conditions, Protection as for the use of CMR substances

5.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	yes
Delay in work plan execution	yes
Conflicts within the consortium	yes
Lack of commitment of partners	yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Loss of key person :

In P1, the identified WPO coleader (Frédéric AUVRAY) left Anses in another position by the end of August 2017. To date, there is no replacement. Hopefully, Yacine NIA (already engaged on other projects) accepted to take this position to support the Tox-Detect leader. Considering the allocated MM for 2018 the Tox-Detect consortium faced difficulties to properly manage all the expected action.

Moreover, an internal reorganization took place in one partner (P4). It has been decided to move WP3 responsibility from P4 to P19. Due to this internal situation in P4, a lack of commitment of WP3 leader has been pointed out. WP3 L advised the management team to propose a new organization. A dedicated meeting was organized on M13 (January 17, 2019) to transfer responsibility from P4 to P19.

Delay in work plan execution :

Delay in D-JRP4-1.2 without impact on the other deliverables

Conflicts within the consortium :

During the KO meeting, P19 member asked for data (Bc sequences) coming from other projects. As these ones were not including in the consortium (state of art, knowlegde) it was decided not to dispatch this information to the whole consortium (see JRP4-WP4-T1-ST1).

5.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

A common meeting with partners of another H2020 project (EuroBioTox) was organised on 24 May 2018 to avoid overlapping of activities and to share roadmaps.

5.9. *List of dissemination and communication activities*

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	Oral presentation in the CPS EURL annual workshop		
<i>Date:</i>	May 30 to June 2, 2018		
<i>Place:</i>	Maisons-Alfort		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	Yes	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	30	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	European workshop dedicated to toxins		
Date:	May 24, 2018		
Place:	Agroscope (Bern, Switzerland)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	Y (linked with EuroBioTox project)
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	8	Media	
Industry	0	Investors	
Civil Society	0	Customers	
General Public	0	Other	
Policy Makers	2		

Name of the activity:	<i>Presentation at Food Micro conference</i>		
Date:	<i>on September 3, 2018.</i>		
Place:	<i>Berlin, Germany</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	<i>?</i>	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>?</i>	<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>	<i>?</i>	<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>?</i>		

5.10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

January 17, 2019 : Face to face meeting in P19 location for transfer of leadership of WP3 between P4 and P19.

March 20-21, 2019 : 2nd general face to face meeting of the TOX-DETECT project in Maisons-Alfort (P1 location)

6. NOVA

6.1. *Summary of the work carried out*

The project has been in a start-up phase with continued planning and collaboration within all work packages. A kick-off meeting was held in Rome, February 28th – March 1st, 2018. At this meeting, researchers working in all work packages, and from all but two partners, were present. Some of the researchers have had previous collaborations but many of us have not met in person before and it was a good opportunity to get to know each other and understand how we can make the best use of each other's competences. We also spent time within the WP groups to discuss details within each WP.

During the first half of the year, several partners have recruited staff that will work part time or full time in the project. The work is now ongoing within the first tasks and the first deliverables have been completed. In several WPs (1, 2, 3, and 4), the first tasks include mapping of different aspects of surveillance and available data sources. To avoid overlap and to enable synergies across projects, mapping strategies and content have been discussed with experts in the ORION and the COHESIVE projects. WP1 also includes work on surveillance terminology that can be linked to work in ORION, and a dialogue is kept between experts in the two projects.

In addition to work on glossaries and mapping, WP1 (Food chain surveillance mapping) has initiated more detailed investigations of surveillance opportunities and barriers, as perceived by some of the key stakeholders. In addition, a questionnaire study of data availability and barriers as regards use of food purchase data has been performed in WP2 (Analysis of food purchase data). The use of such data for outbreak investigations was also the focus of a review study that indicated that the method is potentially powerful but should be further developed. Consumer purchase data used in analyses for other purposes, such as identification of risk factors for sporadic disease, has not been previously described but is now being explored in this project. Studies of nosocomial foodborne outbreaks have also been performed within WP2.

WP3 (Syndromic surveillance) has also been involved in the identification of data sources, specifically for syndromic surveillance purposes. In the ongoing work, the partner institutes make use of each other's different systems and progress in different areas to develop new systems that connect veterinary and public health syndromic surveillance. WP4 (Spatial risk mapping) has performed review studies on spatial risk mapping and has also started to gather data for analysis and modelling. Spatial modelling for the studies of surveillance strategies in the low and high prevalence context is ongoing. In parallel, WP5 (Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency) has focused the first year on work with disease spread models of infection in production animals, that will be used to compare surveillance strategies and the effect on human exposure. As part of this, measures of surveillance performance and disease burden is being discussed.

6.2. *Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results*

6.2.1. WP0: Coordination and project management

JRP6-WP0-T1: Project management

Monthly meetings with WP leaders have been held. The coordinator has also attended information meetings within the One Health EJP (face-to-face and via video conferences). She also presented the project at the official kick-off of the EJP in January. This task has also included reporting, finding platforms for sharing of information

and documents and to summarise information about the project for the websites of the One Health EJP and our institutes. Management has also involved work with the ethics self-assessment and the data management plan.

JRP6-WP0-T2: Organise annual assemblies

An annual assembly (kick-off meeting) was organised and held in Rome, February 28th to March 1st. Organisation of the second annual assembly was started in November 2018.

JRP6-WP0-T3: Economic reporting and financial management

SVA participated in the financial OHEJP meeting at ANSES in Paris on June 25th. The financial reporting for NOVA is performed by each partner institute involved.

6.2.2. WP1: Food chain surveillance mapping

JRP6-WP1-T1: Definition of a joint food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology

The objective of this task is to provide a **common glossary of defined terms used in food borne surveillance**. Given the work on a Med-Vet glossary in the ORION project, integration in which members of NOVA WP1 have also participated, the deliverable of this WP will also be based on the work conducted within the framework of ORION. After the recent competition of this glossary work, all participants in WP1 have become familiar with its content and function, thanks to collaborative webinars and discussions (between NOVA-ORION and within NOVA). At the moment, a detailed email is being drafted with the aim to inform the leaders of the other WPs about the specific input needed from them, considering terms to be added to the glossary. After collaboration with WP2-5, any additional terms will be included and defined.

JRP6-WP1-T2: Mapping of surveillance: data, regulatory framework, key stakeholders, opportunities and barriers

One of the objectives of this task is to identify and describe **all currently used and unused sources** that potentially could be used for improving **surveillance**: the focus is on the **potential for synergy** between Med and Vet with the aim of **surveillance**. Group discussions about this topic have been regularly held (at least once a month) and documented. After **identification of stakeholders** across Member States (i.e. Belgium, Norway, Sweden) through an overall **mapping exercise** on *Salmonella* spp, potential novel data sources or surveillance gaps are being investigated with discussion among participants. After the completion of the overall mapping exercise, each MS chose a different stakeholder to focus on (i.e. policy maker, herd veterinarian, general practitioner) and identified and described the **surveillance activities** they are involved in. Currently, the inclusion/exclusion criteria of the various surveillance components are being defined and an in-depth discussion over gaps and opportunities related to these components is being carried out. The output of this discussion will be used for the drafting of the questionnaire addressing the selected stakeholders. This questionnaire will involve all partners in NOVA, and potentially also other partners in the EJP consortium.

6.2.3. WP2: Analysis of food purchase data

Research done into the epidemiology of foodborne diseases in order to prevent them better, is generally dependent on data on food exposure. These are most often collected via interviews with patients regarding food consumption – a method that have limitations due to incomplete recall and difficulties in contacting patients in a timely manner. Therefore, the possibility of extracting food purchase data is attractive. This WP explores this method and aims to cast light on its feasibility.

JRP6-WP2-T1: Data availability and barriers

The availability of purchase data for outbreak investigations has been explored through two questionnaires send to key actors in EU member states. The aim was to get an overview of the degree the methods had been used, if data were seen to be available in theory and reality and to identify obvious barriers towards use of the data. A total of 11 countries replied. Seven countries had already used such data, and most had relied on supermarket data and with the purpose to perform hypothesis-generation or aid food trace-back investigation. Several benefits of the method were seen, and it was assumed it could be used more in the future. Barriers were noted, the most important being consumer privacy legislation. The study is described in detail in D-JRP6-2.1. Future work will focus on more precisely describing the obstacles in order to suggest ways to work around them.

JRP6-WP2-T2: Food purchase data for outbreak investigations

This task aims to describe the use of consumer purchase data as an outbreak investigation methodology. This has been addressed by a structured review of published papers reporting on its use (described in D-JRP6-2.3). For the period 2006–17, scientific articles were found describing 20 outbreak investigations. The consumer purchase datasets were most frequently used to generate hypotheses about the outbreak vehicle where case-interviews had not been fruitful. Secondly, they were used to aid trace-back investigation, where a vehicle was already suspected. Several of the outbreaks were unlikely to have been solved without the use of consumer purchase data. The method can be concluded to be potentially powerful but should be further developed. Future work in the task will focus on finding and structuring concrete descriptions of prior use of the method in parallel to work done in T1.

JRP6-WP2-T3: Big data analysis of risk factors for sporadic disease

This task aims to explore if consumer purchase data can be used for studies beyond the outbreak setting; something which to our knowledge has not previously been done. In the first year, an electronic web module was built in which Danish users can be invited to sign up and give consent for their electronic purchase data to be used. This has largely been obtained (described in detail in D-JRP6-2.5). Using the module, it will be possible to invite cases with acute illness and non-ill citizens to take part in an analytical study addressing risk factors for sporadic disease.

In parallel, we analyse a large dataset, which has been obtained in cooperation with the major Danish supermarket chain. With this, we will explore the possibility of addressing risks and frequencies associated with different food groups.

JRP6-WP2-T4: Food distribution data for hospital outbreaks

This task aims to use electronic food purchase data at the institutional level for investigation of nosocomial foodborne outbreaks. So far, two paths have been explored (both described in D-JRP6-2.8). One path concerns German surveillance data on healthcare-associated foodborne outbreaks using the electronic surveillance system SurvNet. This was done in order to describe the number of outbreaks, their settings and agents. The second subtask has been to conduct a systematic literature review on published health-care associated foodborne outbreaks in OECD countries, 2001-2018. A total of 49 such papers were found and included. This work is presented in preliminary form in the deliverable and is expected to form the basis of a full publication in 2019.

JRP6-WP2-T5: Trace back and food risk mapping

This task aims to develop improved tools for food risk mapping and integrate them into the state-of-the-art tracing tool software FoodChain-Lab. In agreement with the work plan, this work has been planned during the first year and will commence in the second and third year of the project.

6.2.4. WP3. Syndromic surveillance

Syndromic surveillance (SyS) consists in the nearly real-time collection, analysis, interpretation and diffusion of non-specific indicators in order to detect any changes in human or animal health. From a “One Health” perspective, no SyS system is currently operational in EU, including data from animal sector, environmental sector, food industry and human sector. NOVA’s WP3 was therefore designed to assess whether SyS in animal and food sectors could be a valuable add-on to the current or future surveillance of FBD (Foodborne diseases).

JRP6-WP3-T1: Identify the opportunities for SyS of FBD

JRP6-WP3-T1-ST1: Food chain mapping

JRP6-WP3-T1-ST2: Data source screening: availability, quality and suitability for SyS

Year 1 was devoted to the task 3.1. The objective of this task was to identify potential data sources in Member states contributing to WP3 in order to develop specific surveillance components for FBD based on “secondary data” in tasks 3.2 and 3.3. “Secondary data” are already available information, sometimes collected for other purposes than health surveillance that may be of interest for health surveillance.

The methodology for the inventory of data sources was defined in the kick-off meeting in March 2018. We drew a comprehensive map of the food chain, from primary production to human consumption (JRP6-WP3-T1-ST1). Upon finalizing this mapping, we identified strong synergies with other WPs, within different projects in the EJP group of projects. In particular, the work being developed in WP1 in NOVA, and in ORION. Therefore, we deemed very relevant to subject our first food chain mapping to their review and input. The map was not further developed pending the finalization of WP1's work.

In parallel from the food-chain mapping, we worked on a detailed inventory of data sources existing along this food producing continuum. A table was designed to collect data potentially useful and available for data-driven surveillance of FBD. The table was filled in based on expertise of NOVA WP3 members. The

identified data sources were placed on the food chain map to visualize the coverage of the food chain with the available sources. Potential gaps in surveillance coverage were identified. As the identified data sources are planned to be used in task 3.2. for the development of univariate surveillance modules, quality of the data for that purpose were critically assessed (JRP6-WP3-T1-ST2). T1 results were detailed in the first and second WP3 reports.

JRP6-WP3-T2: Univariate syndromic surveillance development for FBD (and AMR)

JRP6-WP3-T3: Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance for FBD

Tasks 2 and 3 were launched at the end of Year 1. Task 1 showed that the three countries participating in T2 and T3 do not have the same level of progress in the implementation and use of SyS monitoring tools. We therefore put in place different strategies depending on the degree of progress. However, we chose the same case study in all three countries: the monitoring of Salmonella and Campylobacter from animal and food production to human population. For France, we will develop univariate surveillance modules for Salmonella in feed, cattle, poultry and pig, as no operational systems are currently available (T2), although several sources of data were identified in T1. In Norway, a syndromic surveillance system called Sykdomspulsen (NorSySS) was established in 2012. This is used to monitor the infectious status and possible outbreaks of gastro-intestinal and respiratory diseases in humans. In T3, we want to assess if NorSySS in combination with data from veterinary and food monitoring systems could lead to an improvement of the surveillance and thereby earlier notice and decision making for gastrointestinal outbreaks. In Sweden, we would like to develop a tool similar to NorSySS on Campylobacter infections, including at least data on poultry sector and human cases (T2 and T3). We will focus on the actual syndromic surveillance methods, but also on visualization tools (dashboard) to support surveillance officials.

6.2.5. WP4: Spatial risk mapping

JRP6-WP4-T1: Identification of spatial relationships and patterns in Salmonella prevalence

JRP6-WP4-T1-ST1: Surveillance in high prevalence regions to detect introduction and changes in prevalence

The high prevalence region chosen for this subtask is Spain. Salmonella surveillance in Spain has been reviewed focusing on isolates of swine origin and the links between the main stakeholders of such surveillance in Spain which ultimately are the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Health. Recorded surveillance information on pigs has been associated to its geographical location and farm characteristics. Overall, prevalence of Salmonella at the farm level (2002-2015) was 35.0%. However, this number varied considerably over time. A deeper spatio-temporal analysis will be performed next year. Data on the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of the isolates are currently being collected and will be incorporated in the analyses. The distribution of serovars was heterogeneous, with some being particularly abundant in certain areas. Further analyses to assess the statistical significance of this trend and identify slaughterhouse/farm characteristics associated with these results are ongoing.

Recorded surveillance information on human cases could only be linked to administrative level NUT3. A descriptive analysis of the clinical data was performed to evaluate changes in the burden of the disease.

JRP6-WP4-T1-ST2: Surveillance in low prevalence regions to reduce prevalence

The prevalence region chosen in ST2 is Sweden, where control includes all serotypes and all animal species. Since the mid-1990s, the number of cattle found in the control program has been low but maintained a steady level. To assess potential surveillance strategies, both the within- and between-herd transmission dynamics of infection need to be considered. Within-herd transmission has been extensively studied but approaches to model the between-herd spread of this infection is still missing in the literature. In this study, we develop a two-stage transmission model for S. Dublin infections in dairy farms that is suitable for evaluating the effectiveness of different surveillance strategies in a hypoendemic context. We also explore hidden variables that can affect the transmission of Salmonella by investigating the spatial differences in environmental and social characteristics. The developed model provides a better understanding of the spread within herds, but it is still insufficient to simulate the surveillance strategies. Next year we will improve the model by exploring different options.

JRP6-WP4-T2: Risk of introduction of Salmonella in pig farms through animal feed.

Salmonella surveillance in Spain in pig farming (overseen by the Ministry of Health, AECOSAN) has been reviewed.

JRP6-WP4-T3: Role of the environment in the occurrence and maintenance of Salmonella infection in extensive farming

So far, data have been gathered from official sources as regards faecal sampling in slaughterhouses 2008. Results indicate that 43% of the extensive pig farms sampled were positive to Salmonella. Available data also showed that prevalence at the farm level was low. However, these data are very scarce and represents less than 1% of total extensive production in the country. I.e. the sampling should not be considered as representative for extensive farming in Spain.

6.2.6. WP5: Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency

JRP6-WP5-T1: Adapt infectious disease models for assessing the effect of surveillance programs in primary animal production on consumer exposure to foodborne pathogens

The surveillance strategies that will be implemented in the models are either strategies for early detection of emerging infections or hazards in a population, or strategies for detecting changes in the occurrence of existing infections or hazards.

The models developed and adjusted in within this task in 2018 are listed below. The spread of the infections/hazards is modelled between farms and/or within farms. At this stage, some of the models also includes elements of surveillance.

- Model for simulation of imperfect testing of individuals or groups in compartmental disease-spread models for the purpose of assessing surveillance system performance has been initiated for paratuberculosis in cattle. The main outcome is the time to detection after introduction at national level.
- Introduction to and spread of *Salmonella* within egg laying flocks using different approaches for modelling the spread. The model assesses the effect of different sampling schedules and laboratory methods. The main output is the amount of contaminated eggs released to market from an infected flock before detection.

- Within and between farm spread of *Salmonella* in pig production. The main output is national infection prevalence over time.

JRP6-WP5-T2: Assessing the effect of using metagenomics in surveillance of foodborne zoonoses

We have developed a primary model simulating spread of AMR in large animal populations, and how use of metagenomics in the surveillance can be optimised using different sampling schedules. The main outcome is the spread by time of a new strain of AMR bacteria in a large animal population, and time until detection using different sampling schedules.

JRP6-WP5-T3: Modelling the effect of surveillance programs in the food production on human health

Work is conducting adjusting an existing QMRA of Salmonella in slaughter and breeder pigs. The main output is the number of consumers getting salmonellosis due to pork meat. How to incorporate burden of disease as an outcome in this model is being considered.

6.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

6.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
NOVA	D-JRP6-0.1	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	3	2018-06-21		Documentation completed in Month 3 but deliverance was postponed because we wanted to use the right template. The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-2.1	Description by member state of data sources, agreements and organisations (e.g. retailer chains).	10	2018-11-31	12	The delivery date in the original AWP was 10 but during the year it was changed to 12. The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-2.3	Structured review of the field.	5	2018-05-31		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-2.5	Data infrastructure built, electronic informed consent tool in function.	12	2018-12-17		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-2.8	Epidemiological analysis of existing surveillance data regarding ha-FBO and foods involved.	10	2018-12-19	12	The delivery date in the original AWP was 10 but during the year it was changed to 12. The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-3.1	Full mapping of the chain process for three main productions in E.U	8	2018-08-31		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-3.2	Data inventory with assessment of availability, quality and fitness for SS	10	2018-10-30		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-4.1	Maps for Salmonella prevalence geographical	12	2018-12-15		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.

		patterns in intensive livestock and slaughterhouses completed in high prevalence regions				
NOVA	D-JRP6-4.3	Assessment of the spatio-temporal infection dynamics model in Salmonella in low prevalence regions.	12	2018-12-15		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.
NOVA	D-JRP6-4.7	Salmonella data in extensive farming in Mediterranean scenario mapped and analysed.	12	2018-12-15		The deliverable has been uploaded on the NOVA group on the OHEJP website.

6.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
NOVA	M-JRP6-1	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	2	Yes		
NOVA	M-JRP6-2	Meeting for information exchange (data, literature, data bases) exchange on exposure assessment, DALY's, consumption data and food handling at home	6	Yes	10	Meeting postponed to await recruitment of staff, and thereby enabling these new co-workers to participate.
NOVA	M-JRP6-3	Food Chain mapping completed, data sources identification advanced, and ready to start developing the SS components	7	Yes		
NOVA	M-JRP6-4	Pilot, data availability.	9	Yes		
NOVA	M-JRP6-5	Case-study choice	9	Yes		
NOVA	M-JRP6-6	Surveillance strategies to implement into the models agreed	12	No	18	More discussion is considered needed and there is no rush to reach this milestone before the end of next year.
NOVA	M-JRP6-7	Basic model describing spread of emerging zoonoses in immunological naïve animal populations established	12	Yes		

6.4. Publications and patents

Garrido-Esteba M, Latasa P, Ordóñez-León GY, Martínez-Avilés M, de la Torre A, García-Comas L, 2018. Clinical aspects of non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi Salmonella related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, comorbidities, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs. Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis (2018).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1>. Open access article.

Møller FT, Mølbak K, Ethelberg S, 2018. Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review. Eurosurveillance, 23(24).

<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.24.1700503>

www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.24.1700503

6.5. Impact & relevance

The project contains cultivation of new methods as well as more efficient utilisation of existing data and methods. It offers ideas for direct surveillance tools, but also for tools directed towards evaluation of surveillance systems. The tools and methods are primarily developed with a focus on the currently most important/frequent zoonotic diseases but may also be adapted to control other hazards or emerging agents.

The surveillance of food purchase patterns is currently non-existent in Europe. Results from WP2 show that this genuinely new surveillance approach is potentially valuable and cost-effective. The methods/tools for surveillance of food exposures and trace-back developed, include tools that presently do not exist anywhere in the world (WP2). This project's development and combination of syndromic surveillance systems and use of new data sources, is a first bridge across the Med-Vet gap in the syndromic surveillance context (WP3). Understanding the geographical transmission of diseases is a cornerstone in epidemiology, yet surprisingly rarely used in practise – the focus on spatial mapping and analysis will provide better possibilities for actual utilisation in the zoonotic disease community (WP4). Mathematical modelling is another cornerstone of modern disease transmission understanding that we are now using to find ways to actually measure surveillance performance, and thereby be able to compare the cost-efficiency of different surveillance strategies, considering potential disease spread across the food chain (WP5). Finally, our mapping of available data sources and identification of surveillance key actors across the food chain, including the underlying reasons for sub-optimal surveillance, should help clarify surveillance structures and challenges across the EU (WP1).

6.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of isolates from human origin have been sought.	Isolates from human origin will not be used in NOVA. Analysis in WP4 only includes anonymous public data of serotype results from clinical human cases. Ethic approvals for the use these data will not be needed.

The applicants must confirm the compliance with GDPR.	Work to confirm compliance with GDPR is on-going in all partner institutes. As experts working in NOVA, we continuously check that we follow the national regulations and institute routines that are adjusted or updated due to GDPR. As part of the One Health EJP, the project is participating in our common web-learning programme, to ensure that the details of our data management plan comply with GDPR.
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6.7. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

The risk to lose key-persons exists but is weak. The problem has rather been that recruitment of staff that will work in the project has been delayed. This connects to the second point, i.e. the delay in work plan execution, which we consider a more immediate risk. Our assessment is that now that staff has been recruited, we will be able to catch up in tasks that have had a slower start than expected. The lack of commitment of partners is also weak, but we want to acknowledge that risk, as we are a relatively wide project with several institutes being involved, but on a varied budget. So far, we have not seen any lack of interest or failure to deliver.

6.8. *Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project*

National projects:

- **EG17-141. Assignment from Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment to INIA in R&D animal health activities and technical support to the national reference laboratories (2017-2019).**

It favours and support the exchange of information with the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment on 1) data on salmonella surveillance in animal health, and b) technical and scientific meetings.

- **Workshop on animal health and wildlife.** 14th June, 2018. https://www.mapa.gob.es/gl/ganaderia/temas/sanidad-animal-higiene-ganadera/programafinalsjunio2018_tcm37-453127.pdf
- **Vet+i Foundation, Spanish Technology Platform for Animal Health.** http://www.vetmasi.es/plataforma-tecnologica-espanola-de-sanidad-animal/menu-superior/inicio_37_1_ap.html.
Vet+i is an interdisciplinary forum that integrates all relevant stakeholders from academia, research, farmers, veterinarians, industry, regulators, etc. interested in animal health. This is an efficient instrument to facilitate the networking and discussion in order to achieve its main goal: to enable the efficient transfer of research developed in Spain and accelerate the development and delivery of the most effective tools for controlling the animal diseases of priority for Spain, thereby improving human and animal health, food safety and quality, animal welfare and market access.
- **Workshop on new technologies for early warning of shared diseases and zoonosis between wildlife and domestic animals.** 11th September, 2018. http://www.vetmasi.es/plataforma-tecnologica-espanola-de-sanidad-animal/presentaciones/jornadas-nuevas-tecnologias-de-alerta-temprana-de-enfermedades-compartidas-y-zoonosis-entre-fauna-silvestre-y-domestica_4072_12_4245_0_1_in.html
- **Workshop on new technologies for early warning of shared diseases and zoonosis between wildlife and domestic animals.** 23th July, 2018. http://www.vetmasi.es/plataforma-tecnologica-espanola-de-sanidad-animal/presentaciones/jornada-vigilancia-epidemiologica-y-sistemas-innovadoras-de-deteccion-temprana-de-enfermedades-en-el-sector-porcino-y-bovino_4053_12_4222_0_1_in.html
- **Annual Conference. R&D&I future.** 3th May, 2018. http://www.vetmasi.es/plataforma-tecnologica-espanola-de-sanidad-animal/presentaciones/x-conferencia-anual-veti_4009_12_4176_0_2_in.html
- **Spatial modelling of VTEC/EHEC:** WP4 has had minor/some support from a Swedish research project financed by the Swedish Research Council Formas. This project uses the same modelling framework as in task 4.1.2 to model the spatial distribution and spread of VTEC/EHEC.
- **AMR in Danish pig production:** The activities in WP5 is interacting with research activities related to surveillance in the participating institutes/countries. In particular the work can be linked to a national project on predicting the occurrence of AMR in Danish pig production when altering the AMU. 2018-2022 (founded by the Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark).
- **Surveillance of salmonella in poultry meat:** The title of another project that the WP5 is connected to is: Evaluate and Establish Surveillance programs of Salmonella in imported and domestic Poultry Meat in Jordan. 2016-2020 (founded by the Islamic Development Bank)

EU projects:

- **COST ASF-STOP CA15116. Understanding and combating African Swine Fever in Europe.** <https://www.asf-stop.com>; Some of the NOVA WP4 members are participating in this e-cost action. Within this project a systematic review and assessment of biosecurity measures to prevent the spread of infection diseases in (intensive and extensive) pig farms has been conducted. Information generated has been employed to describe the pig production sector in Spain.
- **ASF-STOP WG2-4 workshop “Control of ASF in Eastern Europe. Knowledge gaps and the need of data driven evidence”.** 20th March, 2018. Tallin, Estonia.
- **ASF STOP annual meeting.** 3th July, 2018. Lisbon, Portugal.
- **One Health EJP:** Within the EJP, we have had collaboration with the integrative project **ORION**, in particular as regards Med/Vet surveillance terminology. To avoid the risk that the same or similar work is being done in parallel, we have also had discussions to clarify how our work connects and how we make use of potential overlap.

6.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	De la Torre, A. Role of the wildlife-livestock interface in zoonosis spreading. Risk Assessment Research Assembly (RARA) https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/event/180207/180207-Posters-Presentations.pdf		
Date:	7 th February 2018		
Place:	Utrecht, Netherlands		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other (presentations book)	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	25
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	25		

Name of the activity:	<p><i>Martínez, M; Álvarez, J; Garrido, M; de la Torre, A. Monitoring systems of salmonella in Spain to assess a “one health” approach towards a potential risk to humans from ingestion of contaminated pork meat.</i></p> <p><i>International Meeting on Emerging Diseases and Surveillance.</i></p> <p>http://imed.isid.org/downloads/PosterAbstracts2018.pdf</p>		
Date:	November 9-12, 2018		
Place:	Vienna, Austria		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other (abstract book)	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No	Other (QDR code)	Yes
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

6.10. *List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year*

The coordinator and WP leaders will have monthly one-hour (or longer, if needed) video conferences throughout 2019. The planned dates for these are:

- *January 15*
- *February 12*
- *March 12*
- *April 9*
- *May 14*
- *June 11*
- *August 27*
- *September 17*
- *October 15*
- *November 12*
- *December 10*

An annual assembly with an opportunity for face-to-face meetings across and within WPs will also be held. The plan is to have this meeting in Brussels in *March 7-8, 2019*.

7. LISTADAPT

7.1. *Summary of the work carried out*

The LISTADAPT JRP project has officially started in January 2018. The kick-off meeting and a workshop were held in Maisons-Alfort in March. The workshop has permitted to discuss and refine the initial strategy for the strains selection as well as for the statistical tools and bio-informatics approaches that will be used in the project.

Partners of LISTADAPT have concentrated their efforts in the first months on strain selection and characterization of their existing collections. LISTADAPT partners also took contact with other research laboratories to increase the diversity of the sampling at EU levels. LISTADAPT members have conducted new sampling campaigns in environment and farms. These campaigns have helped to increase the isolates available for sequencing and characterisation. The overall prevalence for samples gathered from the new campaigns is 1.5%. Some samples taken from environment were also shared with EJP MedVetKLEBS project.

An original algorithm for selecting strains according to metadata available has been developed and has been applied. The first batch of DNA extraction and sequencing has been carried out and the genome assemblies and annotation have been produced. After one year, 750 strains have been gathered in ANSES from 15 partners (both EJP LISTADAPT and other EU laboratory partners). 520 strains have been extracted and sequenced. For 70 strains genome assemblies and annotation have been produced. The first sequencing results confirm that environmental/farm/animal strains largely differ from food strains.

The LISTADAPT partners have also decided to sequence some strains (<50) from other *Listeria* species found in the environment. The comparison of the sequences from those species with *L. monocytogenes* from soil could help to look for potential exchange between them (mobile genetic elements) in the environment.

Partners in charge of phenotypic characterization (adhesion, biocides, etc) have received 100 strains (out of the 200 strains) from the food compartment. The 100 remaining strains from the farm/animal/environment compartments have been identified and will be sent in January 2019 to partners in charge of phenotypic characterization.

The protocols to be applied to that two collections has been established and have been tested on a subset of strains.

7.2. *Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results*

7.2.1. WP0: Coordination

The kick-off meeting and workshop were organized in Maisons-Alfort in March 2018. The coordinator assisted most meetings organized by the EJPOH coordination.

The communication (e.g. exchange of documents) between partners was limited to a few meetings. This was considered sufficient for 2018 as tasks were well defined and because the sampling campaigns had to be carried out to obtain strains.. More interactions are planned in 2019 (more results to discuss, more challenges to solve). The website/intranet will be used in 2019. It will help to improve communication between partners.

7.2.2. WP1: Constitution of a strain collection representative of the different reservoirs of *Listeria monocytogenes*

JRP7-WP1-T1: Strain collection

JRP7-WP1-T2-ST1: External collaborations

Before the beginning of the project, external participants had already agreed to provide animal and natural environment isolates from their own strain collections: National Veterinary Institute of Ljubljana (SI); ISAE (Agronomic institute) (FR); IFIP The French pork institute (FR), Veterinary Faculty of Skopje (MK).

Several other research scientific teams were approached to collect strains from animals and the environment. The list of new contacts is reported in Table 1. These collaborations will increase the representativeness/diversity of the LISTADAPT strain collection (more countries at EU-level, more partners at country level).

The algorithm of strain selection (see Task 1.3) was used to select strains according to the metadata (region, period, subtype...) provided by partners.

Table 1. List of newly established external collaborations for increasing diversity of LISTADAPT strain collection

Partners	Country	Contact	Strain collection panel	Number of selected strains*
University of Helsinki	Finland	Dr Miia Lindstrom	animal sector (cattle and farm strains)	180 strains
BIOR The Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment	Latvia	Dr Zanete Steingolde	animal sector (cattle and farm strains)	36 strains
Faculty of Food Science and Fisheries - West Pomeranian University of Technology	Poland	Dr Barbara Szymczak	Environment (soil, fruits, vegetables)	80 strains
PIWET	Poland	Dr Wasyl Dariusz	Environment/farm/animal	To contact again in 2019
ONCFS	France	Dr. Anouk Decors	Wild animal	Discussion in progress
University of Munich	Germany	Dr Verena Hohenester	Wild animal	32 strains
Neiker Tecnalia	Spain	Dr Ana Hurtado	Farm animal (cattle, sheep)	38 strains
Teagasc	Ireland	Dr Kieran Jordan	animal sector (milk strains)	To contact again in 2019
PHE	UK	Dr Corinne Amar	Wild animal	5 strains
INIAV Animal Pathology Laboratory	Portugal	Dr Leonor Orge	Farm animal (cattle, sheep, poultry)	Selection in progress
Slovenian LNR for Lm	Slovenia	Dr Bojan Pabic	Farm animal (cattle, sheep)	25 strains
NVWA - NL LNR for Lm	The Netherland	Dr Nathalie Loeke	Farm animal	21 strains
Veterinary and Food Laboratory	Estonia	Toomas Kramarenko	Farm animal	Selection in progress

* Selection procedure based on method described in task 1.3

JRP7-WP1-T2-ST2: Sampling campaigns

JRP7-WP1-T2: Campaigns to collect additional animal and environmental strains

The strain collection established on existing isolates at the beginning of the project consisted mostly of isolates from food, production environments and humans. The most underrepresented niches were wild life and nature. Several sampling campaigns have been organized during the first nine months of the project to fill this gap. Table 2 show the planned and ongoing campaigns. A specific protocol has been proposed for every partner of the project. A video has been made (the video will be shared through the website when available). The sampling has to be made either at farm (manure, soil), in the pasture (mud, soil) or in the forest (soil). For each sample, GPS coordinate (GPS coordinate are reported (in decimal format provided by google maps), as well as a picture of the sampling place with a brief description of the sampling environment.

The analyses of the samples have so far led to only few new isolates of *Listeria* (e.g. only 17 isolates were found from 1200 wild animals), but more samples are available and will be analysed. In order to limit resources, the

feces samples are analysed as pooled samples from 5 animals. Further, a specific PCR protocol has been established to save resources. The PCR analysis is carried out on the selective media for isolation, without prior cultivation on agar plates.

Table 2. List of sampling campaigns already realized or planned

Partners	Country	Region	Period	Type of samples	Number of samples
ANSES	France	Burgundy/Morvan	May	Meadow/forest	25
ANSES	France	Brittany	June	Meadow/forest	10
INRA	France	Burgundy	July-September	Farm/Meadow	>50
ANSES	France	Burgundy	July	Meadow/forest	5
ANSES	France	Burgundy/Sologne/Corrèze	October-December	Meadow/forest/wild animal	50
VRI	Czech Republic	Various regions	September-October	Meadow/forest/farm	50
ANSES	Slovenia	Various regions	October	Meadow/farm	50
SVA	Sweden	Various regions	June-October	Meadow/forest/farm	50
NVI	Norway	Various regions	July-October	Soil and grass from forest, mountain areas and nature	200¹
NVI	Norway	Various regions	Analyses of samples from 2015-2018	Feces from deer and other wild animals, no symptoms of listeriosis	1200¹

¹: **The analyses and sampling will be continued during 2019.**

JRP7-WP1-T3: Strategy for sequencing

Sampling is crucial for the pertinence/performance of the genomic analysis carried out. Several strategies of sampling are available and the analyst must adapt to the global objective he has. At least two different strategies can be envisaged. If the objective is to characterize the strains that contribute the most to consumer exposure, the sampling effort must be put on strains isolated in the food product from the main food companies (or issued from the main food producing regions). Stratified sampling is commonly applied in such situations. On the other hand, if the objective is to explore the diversity of strains circulating in a country, the analyst can use the metadata associated to strain to reach that objective. When there is more than two categories of metadata describing the strains, the selection requires an algorithm of selection.

In the context of LISTADAPT, we developed an innovative algorithm based on a three step process for selecting strains based on metadata information (e.g. region, type of animal, ...). This method relies on the Gower's coefficient (GC) (1971), which is a metric expressing a dissimilarity : the "distance" between two units is the sum of all the variable-specific distances (associated to metadata categories). The GC metric is capable of combining numeric and categorical data and offers the opportunity to select weights for each individual variable, effectively altering the importance of each metadata categories (region more important than year). A three proposed steps are:

- calculating dissimilarity matrix based on Gower distance
- applying the clustering method on dissimilarity matrix with hierarchical clustering. (agglomerative (bottom-up approach of clustering)
- assessing clusters with the "Silhouette" method: the silhouette plot displays a measure of how close each point in one cluster is to points in the neighbouring clusters.

The approach is illustrated in Figure below. A script (strain_metaselect.r) is available. It takes a csv file that includes strains ID and metadata information. It provides as output a csv file of selected strains.

1. Collect the metadata describing strain

ID isolate	Season	ID Sampling	Location	Risk
L0524	S1	0_14_01405	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0527	S1	0_14_01388	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0532	S1	0_14_01379	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0533	S1	0_14_01379	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0538	S1	0_14_01322	Shenzhen_1	NEG
L0539	S1	0_14_01322	Shenzhen_1	POS
L0550	S2	0_14_03047	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0552	S2	0_14_03047	Shenzhen_1	POS
L0558	S2	0_14_03036	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0559	S2	0_14_03036	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0566	S2	0_14_04042	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0567	S2	0_14_04042	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0574	S3	0_14_04217	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0575	S3	0_14_04217	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0588	S3	0_14_03941	Shenzhen_1	NEG
L0589	S3	0_14_03941	Shenzhen_1	POS
L0592	S4	0_14_06446	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0593	S4	0_14_06446	Shenzhen_3	POS
L0596	S4	0_14_06290	Shenzhen_1	POS
L0597	S4	0_14_06290	Shenzhen_1	POS

2. Cluster strains based on metadata Gower distances

4. Pick one strain in each of the k groups

3. Assess the number of relevant groups (distinct strains) - k

Figure 1. Method for selecting strains based on their metadata for diversity characterization.

7.2.3. WP2: Whole genome sequencing of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

JRP7-WP2-T1: Purification of Lm DNA from 2000 Lm strains

JRP7-WP2-T1-ST1: First batch Purification of DNA from Lm strains available

The first batch of 140 strains has been used to purify DNA at month 10. Four additional batches of strains have been used at months 11-12, for a total number of 546 strains

JRP7-WP2-T1-ST3: Purification of DNA from routine surveillance systems at IZSAM, DTU, AGES

DNA from strains gathered during routine surveillance were also made available by ANSES, IZSAM, DTU and AGES.

Partners	Country	Number of samples
ANSES	FR	171
DTU	DK	
IZSAM	IT	Final number to be communicate in January 2019
AGES	AT	

JRP7-WP2-T2: Whole Genome Sequencing

JRP7-WP2-T2-ST1: First batch Whole genome sequencing for available Lm strains

The first batch of 140 strains was sequenced in November 2018. The phylogenetic tree obtained on the first batch is shown on Figure 2.

Figure 2. First phylogenetic tree based on mash-distance for the first batch of strains sequenced in LISTADPT.

JRP7-WP2-T2-ST3: Ad hoc Whole genome sequencing

Four other batches (386 strains) were sequenced in December 2018 and sequencing will go on in January 2019.

JRP7-WP2-T3: Genome Assembling and Annotation

LISTADAPT partners planned at the beginning of the project to use outputs from H2020 COMPARE projects. The cogwheel meeting in April 28th 2018 (three LISTADAPT partners ANSES, NVI and IZSAM assisted) between JRP/JIP leaders and COMPARE members permitted to reveal that no SOPs are yet available from COMPARE projects. Partners are looking for alternative solutions like tools proposed by Innuendo project (<http://www.innuendoweb.org/>) or the one presented below.

In December 2018, 70 strains have been assembled according to the following workflow. The different tasks of WP4 rely on WGS data. The internal workflow (ARTwork) of ANSES was used to prepare the input data. The various tools integrated in this analysis procedure as well as the associated parameters are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Tools used for producing Lm assemblies (steps 1 to 4) and for in silico mlst determination (step 5) and annotation (step 6)

Step	Tools	Version		Reference
1 Read normalization	bbtools	36.14	bbnorm : mindepth = -1 maxdepth = 1 prefilter = t tossbadreads = t bbmap : covbinsize = 1000 k=13 nodisk	https://jgi.doe.gov/data-and-tools/bbtools/bb-tools-user-guide/
2 Read quality checking	fastqc	0.11.5	-q	Andrews (2010)
3 Read curation	Trimmomatic	0.33	PE -phred33 TRAILING:20 MINLEN:50	Bolger et al. (2014)
4 Assemblies preparation	Spades	3.9.1	--carefull	Bankevitch et al. (2012)
5 7 MLST characterization	mlst	2.6	--quiet	https://github.com/tseemann/mlst https://pubmlst.org/
6 Genome annotation	Prokka	1.12	--fast	https://github.com/tseemann/prokka 10.1093/bioinformatics/btu153

The first step implemented in ARTwork is the normalization of the reads. The threshold set to initiate the complete analysis is 30x. If the depth is greater than 100x, the reads are normalized to 100x in order to limit the calculation time. The reads covered between 30x and 100x are not modified. The second step is the quality control of the reads. The third step cleans reads by removing contaminant sequences or poor quality sequences to produce a more relevant assembly. The adapter sequences used for sequencing, portions of reads having a phred score (a measure for base quality in DNA sequencing) less than 20 and reads smaller than 50 base pairs are then deleted. After cleaning reads, these are used for the de novo assembly of the genome. The assemblies are used for the prediction of a standard sequence (ST) by an in silico MLST tool. Once the ST is identified, it is used to predict the clonal complex (CC). The annotation is carried out with Prokka tool (Seeman, 2014).

7.2.4. WP3 Phenotypic characterisation of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

JRP7-WP3-T1: Strategy for selection of strains for phenotypical characterization

A balanced sampling strategy has been selected for partitioning the 200 strains between food (100) and environmental/animal strains (100). Within the two categories, subcategories were proposed (see. Figure 1).

Within each category, selection of strains was carried out based on the described CC diversity. Strains from the top four CCs of each subcategories were selected.

For this reason, selection of 100 strains from environmental/animal reservoir was done. We would like to have CC information in some sub-categories for having an homogenous selection procedure.

Figure 3. Partitioning of the strains for phenotypical characterization

JRP7-WP3-T2: The effects of biocides on *Listeria monocytogenes* strains adaptation

JRP7-WP3-T2-ST1: Antibiotics and biocides resistance profiles of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

The determination of the antimicrobial susceptibility profiles of *L. monocytogenes* strains are carried out only from planktonic bacteria by doing MIC assays against biocides and antibiotics. For MIC assays, we intend to test up to 8 biocides (see table below). The first preliminary assays have to be done from at least 10 strains.

Abbreviation	Biocide	Cas number
TR	Triameen Y12-30	2372-82-9
DDAC	Didecyl DimethylAmmonium Chloride	7172-51-5
BC	Benzalkonium Chloride (BTC 50 E)	68391-01-50 and 64-17-5
PHMB	PolyHexaMéthylène Biguanide	32289-58-0
HPer	Hydrogen Peroxide	7722-84-1
SH	Sodium Hypochlorite	
PAc	Peracetic Acid	
EtOH	Ethanol	

The first results on MICs obtained in December 2018 have helped to set the experiments to be conducted on the effects on biocides on biofilms. The Biofilm-Oriented Antiseptics Test (BOAT) and the Bactericidal Biofilm Test will be used with 3 biocides: 1 ammonium quaternary compound (BC or DDAC), 1 chlorine compound (sodium hypochlorite) and 1 peracid compound (hydrogene peroxide or peracetic acid).

JRP7-WP3-T3: Bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

Biofilm formation is investigated by discriminating early and late stages of biofilm development in microtiter plates. Early stage of biofilm formation will be investigated using the Biofilm Ring Test (Chavant et al., 2007), whereas late stage of biofilm formation will be investigated using the crystal violet staining method. These complementary techniques will allow estimating the adhesion and sessile development abilities of *the L. monocytogenes* strains.

JRP7-WP3-T4: Survival and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in different ecological niches

JRP7-WP3-T4-ST1: Survival of *L. monocytogenes* in food products and gastro-intestinal environment

Some harsh conditions (pH and water activity) have been selected to test the potential of adaptation of the different strains. The protocols will be applied on the whole set of strains.

JRP7-WP3-T4-ST2: Survival of *L. monocytogenes* in soil microcosm

Soil for spiking experiments has been chosen. First test on strains (including strain from soils) will be carried out in January 2019.

7.2.5. WP4: Identification of genetic traits in *Listeria monocytogenes* underlying adaptation to the ecological niches

JRP7-WP4-T1: Analyse the distribution / prevalence of clonal complexes among the reservoirs

The analysis of the strains CC distribution in the different food compartment has been done according to the three most recent papers in that field at EU levels (Maury et al.2016 , Nielsen et al. 2017, Felix et al. 2018). This diversity information was used for selecting the 100 strains for phenotypic characterization.

Figure 2. Clonal complex repartition in RTE according to the three main studies available

JRP7-WP4-T3: Biostatistic analysis of annotated genomes

JRP7-WP4-T3-ST1: Identification of statistically relevant methods and development of analysis

During the workshop (task 5.1), a list of relevant tools for identifying markers of adaptation to niches (environment, food industry) was established (see Table 4). ANSES partner has already tested most of these tools on a small dataset of 51 strains.

Table 4. List of tools to be used for GWAS (as defined in the workshop)

Publication	Year	Tool	Unit of genetic variation studied	Tested
Earle et al.	2016	-----	Genes, k-mer, SNP	X
Brynildsrud et al.	2016	Scoary	Genes (Pan-genome)	X
Lees et al.	2016	SEER	K-mer	
Marinier et al.	2017	Neptune	K-mer	X

Collins and Didelot	2017	TreeWAS	SNP	X
Thorpe et al.	2017	Piggy	Intergenic Regions	X

7.2.6. WP5 : Trainings and dissemination

JRP7-WP5-T1: Implementation of a workshop

The workshop related on statistical and bio-informatics tools useful for the project was discussed in the workshop on 6th of March 2018. The resulting choice for sampling is reported in task 1.3 and 3.1. For marker identification the group have listed the GWAS (genome-wide association study) tools to use (Table 4).

JRP7-WP5-T2: Trainings

Two training sessions were organized in April-May 2018 in ANSES Maisons-Alfort for LNRs of Slovenia (Dr. Bojan Papic) and Czech Republic (Dr. Tereza Gelbicova). Another training was organized with the same partners in October 2018.

JRP7-WP5-T4: Dissemination

- A poster related to description of the diversity has been presented in IAFP 2018 in Sweden in April:

Felix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M, Roussel S. 2018. Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France. Poster presented at IAFP EU Stockholm 25-27th April
- An oral communication on the same topic has been given in FoodMicro conference in Berlin (September 2018):

Felix, B., 2018. Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France, Food Micro, Berlin (Germany).
- Another poster has been proposed to the “International meeting on emerging diseases and surveillance”. This poster presents the diversity of strain in food premises (9th-12th November Vienna). S. Antoci, V. A. Acciari, V. Di Marzio, I. Del Matto, G. Centorotola, M. Torresi, C. Marfoggia, G. Iannitto, A. Ruolo, G. A. Santarelli, G. Migliorati, F. Pomilio. Preliminary results on prevalence and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* in different dairy and meat processing plants in Central Italy.

7.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

7.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-0.1	Consortium agreement	1		X	Discussion on content of Consortium Agreement initiated.
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-0.2	Internal reporting templates	3	3		The reporting template has been established based on template provided by EJPOH coordination team
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-1.1	Description of the panel of strains already sequenced	1	1		Sequenced strains were mainly isolated from food industry/ready-to-eat food. These strains further described with metadata
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-1.2	Description of the first panel of strains available to sequence	3	3		
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-1.3	Description of the second panel of strains to sequence	12		X	
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-2.1	Annotation of Lm genomes already sequenced (genomes available before the start of the project)	6	6		Assemblies and annotations of Lm genomes already sequenced (genomes available before the start of the project) were carried out with different tools by different LISTADAPT partners.
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-2.2	Annotation of the Listeria monocytogenes assembled genomes from 1st batch sequencing	10			
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-3.1	Resistance profiles to biocide and antibiotics for the 200 L. monocytogenes strains.	12		14	Resistance profiles have been established on a subset of strains
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-5.1	"LISTADAPT" workshop program	2	2		
LISTADAPT	D-JRP7-5.2	Minutes of the training sessions	10		13	

7.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-1	Kick off meeting	2	Yes		
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-2	Selection of the 200 strains of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> from genomic analyses in WP2	3	Yes/No	13	100 strains have been selected based on their genomic characteristic and context of isolation. These strains correspond to strains isolated along the food production chain. For the left 100, partners wait for the strains collected during the first sampling campaigns programmed (see. Tasks 1.2.1 and 1.2.2). The WGS analysis of the first batches of environmental strains (start in December, shown in that report and finished the 15 th of January) will be used to complete the selection.
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-3	Workshop done	3	Yes		The workshop on statistical and bioinformatics methods was completed with additional exchanges between EJP LISTADAPT members
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-4	DNA prepared for 1st batch WGS	4	Yes	9	The first DNA were prepared in September.
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-5	Strategy for selection of strains for sequencing in place	5	Yes		An original algorithm was developed for selecting strain based on meta-data describing the context of isolation of the strains
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-6	WGS raw data produced	6	No	9	The sequencing was reported of 2 months (related to report of M.2.2)
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-7	Face-to face meeting -2018	8	No	14	
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-8	First batch Lm genomes assembly completed	8	Yes	10	Anticipated as report written at month 9 (Should be delivered at month 10) => please update
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-9	Identification of Lm strains sequenced to be annotated	10	Yes	10	Done
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-10	First batch Lm genomes annotation completed	10	Yes	12	Done.

LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-11	WGS Training session done	10	Yes	10	Some trainings sessions has been done. This should be continued in 2019
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-12	All the strain collected and centralized at ANSES	12	Yes	12	All sequenced strains are in ANSES Maisons-Alfort. Some additional strains still need to be received from external partners (see WP 1)
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-13	DNA prepared for 2nd batch WGS	12	Yes		Done
LISTADAPT	M-JRP7-14	Selection of some representative <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains for adaptation to biocides	12	No	12	10 strain selected

7.4. Publications and patents

Felix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M, Roussel S. 2018. Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France. *Front Microbiol.* 2018 Apr 6;9:684. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2018.00684. eCollection 2018.

S. Antoci, V. A. Acciari, V. Di Marzio, I. Del Matto, G. Centorotola, M. Torresi, C. Marfoglia, G.

Iannitto, A. Ruolo, G. A. Santarelli, G. Migliorati, F. Pomilio. Preliminary results on prevalence and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* in different dairy and meat processing plants in Central Italy, presented at “International meeting on emerging diseases and surveillance” November 2018, Vienna (Austria).

7.5. Impact & relevance

LISTADAPT impacts in terms of:

- **Potential for providing evidence for EU policies in the relevant domain:** Listeriosis in animal is a real problem (see EFSA/ECDC zoonosis report). No characterisation of reported cases are done. The information gathered in LISTADAPT could help to define if characterisation of that strains might be useful for animal health or source attribution.
- **Closing the gap between Med and Vet:** The LISTADAPT project focuses for the first time at EU level on the diversity of Lm isolates in different animals of farm environment. It will help to assess the importance of that strains to public health (does the diversity of environmental strains fits with the food or human sporadic cases).
- **What results have been obtained regarding integration (e.g. databases, protocols, ...):** This point is still a question between LISTADAPT partners especially for sharing WGS data. For other types of data, a DMP plan is being planned to make every phenotypic data available (in a data repository such as Zenodo, DRYAD...). Within all the protocols established to quantify the adaptation of the 200 isolates, the most relevant (that is the more correlated to adaptation in environmental niches) will be shared to every EJP consortium partners. Specific training for applying these protocol might be organized.
- **harmonisation of procedures and other approaches :** The analyses conducted in year 2 on mobile genetic elements will be useful to share with people in epidemiology in order to complete core genome investigations they usually carry out.

7.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of isolates from human origin have been sought.	No isolates of human origin has been included in LISTADAPT right now. The phenotypic tests will be carried out from strains from environment or food. Sequences from strains isolated in listeriosis context might be used in year 2 but the sequences will be gathered in open Bioproject
The applicants must document the safety mitigation measures in place to protect the staff.	Every partners has the biosafety level associated with the handling of <i>Listeria</i>
The applicants must document there are no environmental safety issue from the sampling etc and protocols are in place	A video has been proposed to partners that samples environment (soil, water)

'Animal samples' are collected, please re-confirm no animal experimentation approvals are required for the animal sampling protocols (e.g. do to interventions, restrictions, etc).	No animal experimentation are done. Samples corresponds to faecal samples.
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7.7. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes/No T
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	Yes/No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information:

- Delay: All deliverables should be present at the end of Y2 but a prolongation (of a few months) could be needed to fully exploit the mass of data gathered in LISTADAPT
- Intra-project (JRP) relationship: An effort should be made to improve intra-project communication in 2019.

7.8. *Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project*

Samples collected in the context of LISTADAPT will be shared with EJP METVETKLEBS.

Related to H2020 COMPARE project, some discussions are made to use the list of genes involved in adaptation of Listeria in environment (deliverable from WP4/WP7 of COMPARE project).

The sampling of wild animal feces in Norway is possible due to the slaughter of deer in the CWD infected area.

7.9. *List of dissemination and communication activities*

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>IAFP's European Symposium on Food Safety</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>April 25 – April 27 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Brewery Conference Centre, Stockholm, Sweden</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>FoodMicro conference</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>September 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Berlin</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>International meeting on emerging diseases and surveillance”.</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>9th-12th November.</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Vienna</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

7.10. *List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year*

Meeting	Date	Theme	Partners invited
Face-to-face	February 2019	General meeting of LISTADAPT	all
Tele-conference	January 2019	Phenotypic characterization tests	ANSES coord, INRA, ANSES Fougères, NVI
Tele-conference	January 2019	Bioinformatics tools	ANSES coord, AGES, IZSAM, NVI, DTU
Face-to-face	December 2019	General meeting of LISTADAPT	all

8. METASTAVA

8.1. *Summary of the work carried out*

The Metastava project started officially on 01.01.2018. Following initial phone calls and teleconferences to shape the workplan, a kickoff meeting was organized in Brussels on 21.02.2018. In addition several WP specific teleconferences were organized, as well as teleconferences including all WP leaders ('general assembly'). The activities during the first 12 months focused largely on WP1, WP2 and WP3. In **WP1** (Collect reference data from other metagenomic projects, select the metagenomic methods to be used for the project, and provide guidance data for informed metagenomic workflow design), we organized several questionnaires, phone calls and teleconferences in order to document and standardize the methodologies available in our consortium for metagenomics data generation as well as analysis. The corresponding deliverables were met, specifying the methodologies for data generation and analysis. Publicly available datasets relevant for the sample types treated in our project were prospected (SRA). In **WP2** (Quality assurance tools for the validation and interpretation of metagenomics), work was followed up in a specific teleconference. Two potential exogenous controls for metagenomics experiments were identified and tested. NGS data was generated to determine optimal spiking levels in several sample matrices, and the evaluation of the robustness of the approach in panels of clinical samples was initiated with the spiking of a panel of wild bird swabs. Further representative sample matrices will follow. In addition, data regarding repeatability, reagent batch and contamination effects were generated and will be analyzed during the next months. Efforts to document available samples for organizing a proficiency test (PT) were initiated in collaboration with WP3, while three out of five Metastava partners already participated in the 2018 COMPARE Food PT and contacts are maintained with COMPARE to facilitate potential alignment to their PT in 2019. **WP3** (evaluation of the analytical properties of metagenomics workflows) progress was followed up in a specific teleconference, and a questionnaire was used to document the sample panels that will be used to determine the analytical properties of the metagenomics workflows for the different pathogen models. This work was slightly delayed due to an attention shift to the determination of the most suitable methodologies for data generation and analysis in WP1. A compiled inventory including a planning for the generation of the NGS data was delivered, while most sequencing efforts will be initiated in M12-M13. Discussions on the most suitable methodology for statistical analysis (analytical properties of metagenomics in the models) will be initiated based on the complete sample panel inventory (M13). **WP4** (Concertation with ongoing efforts and dissemination), focusing on integration with other ongoing efforts saw the participation in cogwheel workshop with COMPARE and EFFORT, and is indirectly linked by partner participation in GMI, relevant ISO norm meetings, COMPARE, and EFFORT. Moreover, the majority (3/5) of Metastava partners participated in the 2018 COMPARE Food PT and contacts are maintained with COMPARE to facilitate potential alignment to their PT in 2019. In **WP5** (Project management), project management, the focus was on internal project meetings and reporting to the OH-EJP. During the first months of the project, key management positions (WP leadership and co-leadership) had to be changed, and the composition of the General Assembly (WP leaders + assurance of representation of all partners) was updated.

8.2. *Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results*

8.2.1. WP1. Collect reference data from other metagenomic projects, select the metagenomic methods to be used for the project, and provide guidance data for informed metagenomic workflow design.

JRP8-WP1-T1: broad survey to collect information about sample selection and data generation methods for metagenomics.

We successfully organized several meetings about data generation methods, including one live meeting (during the project kickoff meeting) and three teleconferences. A detailed survey was finalized in M6 and listed all methodologies used by the partners (integration ensured by partners also participating in COMPARE). A conclusion report listed the methods that would be used as standardized methods for the Metastava project and was discussed in a follow-up teleconference. A modular approach was selected, offering alternative technical solutions for sample disruption or homogenization, nucleic acid extraction, cDNA synthesis and double stranding, library preparation, and sequencing. Partner FLI generated extensive comparative validation data for the cDNA synthesis modules (IonS5 NGS sequencing of 15 samples with both alternative modules). The objective is to maximize the use of the selected methodology modules. Where their use is not possible, parallel validation of in-house methods to the selected modules should be provided.

D-JRP8-1.1 includes a report on the questionnaire + a conclusion with selected methods.

JRP8-WP1-T2: broad survey to collect information about data analysis methods for metagenomics.

Data analysis methodology was initially discussed in a session during the kickoff meeting. A detailed questionnaire (finalized 15.06.2018) collected information about IT capacity, tools, and databases used by the partners and was discussed in a follow-up teleconference. It was decided to select one fast mapping approach (Kraken) and one more inclusive iterative assembly/mapping approach (Riems) as standardized tools. With a lower priority, if needed, or time permits, one commercial solution (CLC genomics) will be evaluated as well.

D-JRP8-1.2 includes a report on the questionnaire + a conclusion with selected methods.

JRP8-WP1-T3: identifying available sequence datasets.

Initial efforts to identify useful publicly available metagenomics datasets representative for the sample matrices used in Metastava have identified important metadata limitations: either the methodology of data generation (and the assurance that it was random) or the sample properties/origin could in most cases not sufficiently be traced. Although a list of publicly available datasets was produced (Deliverable D-JRP8-1.3), it was decided that we should focus on datasets produced within the consortium for the validation of QC metrics. This also highlights the need of the generation of this kind of well documented reference datasets, a need that we will partly try to accommodate with the limited resources available to Metastava. Data from Metastava partner's parallel projects will be investigated starting M12 to identify datasets with sufficiently documented metadata. (if unsuitable, focus will be on data specifically produced within Metastava).

We consider D-JRP8-1.3 a live deliverable that currently includes a set of 6 SRA query reports using keywords for relevant sample matrices in Metastava.

8.2.2. WP2. Quality assurance tools for the validation and interpretation of metagenomics.

JRP8-WP2-T1: The development of quality metrics to evaluate the significance of the outcome of a metagenomics experiment.

The task was initiated. JRP8-WP1-T3 identified that the available public data would not be suitable to define endogenous metrics for the selected sample matrices due to insufficient metadata. A focus will be put on general

quality metrics for NGS and data analysis workflows, and data generated in Metastava will be critically reviewed to assess the possibility to define or refine endogenous control metrics.

JRP8-WP2-T2: development and evaluation of external controls for metagenomics.

Technical evaluations (spiking level optimization in different matrices using different WP1 prescribed methodologies for data generation) were performed for two external controls (EC's): mengovirus (a commercial reagent) and murine norovirus 1. EC levels were monitored during the data generation workflow using EC specific real-time RT-PCR assays. Optimal spiking levels were determined for tissue (bovine lung), serum (porcine), and fecal material (porcine), and the corresponding output in NGS datasets was analysed. Currently, the reproducibility of using EC's for metagenomics (modeled by the Mengovirus) is being tested (sequencing in M12-M13) for series of clinical samples (chicken swabs, pig sera, pig fecal material).

JRP8-WP2-T3: reproducibility and batch effect evaluation

Repeatability was evaluated in the context of sample enrichment by ultracentrifugation (study 1) and detection limit (study 2) of metagenomics. In study 1, two technical replicates for each of the 12 swine fecal samples were included in sample preparation with/without an ultracentrifugation step in two Illumina MiSeq runs (6 samples per run). The overall results showed including an ultracentrifugation step increased proportion of viral reads, the number of identified viruses and the median number of reads blasted to viral reference genomes. In terms of repeatability, only 30% of total hits (viral genome ~ sample) were found in both replicates, regardless of enrichment or not, whereas 59.2% of hits were seemingly unrepeatable either in both replicates or including enrichment or not. Repeatability of viral reads was significantly higher in with enrichment (46.7%) than without enrichment (38.4%). The results suggested that there may be an added value for metagenomics studies to include at least technical replicates such that repeatability could be measured and used as an indicator when analyzing data. In study 2, a filtrate of a fecal sample from a SPF pig was used to prepare 10-fold dilutions of filtrate of three fecal samples, which included two technical replicates. One MiSeq run was done in October, and it was repeated in December. Analysis of the compiled data from both runs is ongoing. The complete dataset (four MiSeq runs) will be analyzed in depth to study repeatability of the metagenomics, while also reagent batch effects and contamination issues will be studied and compared to available information from literature.

D-JRP8-2.3: due M12. Data is generated. Some analysis needed. the final deliverable report will be delivered by M16

JRP8-WP2-T4: evaluation of QC metrics on additional parallel datasets

Waiting for output of JRP8-WP2-T1.

JRP8-WP2-T5: Metagenomic proficiency test

Three out of 5 partners participated in the COMPARE 2018 food metagenomics proficiency test. Via Dirk Höper (FLI) we will know firsthand what PT COMPARE will organize in 2019, and we will evaluate whether integrating our PT efforts with COMPARE may provide more added value. In addition, WP3 tracked in its sample

questionnaire the availability of material to be included in a PT. Unless urgent action is needed (e.g. joining the 2019 COMPARE PT), this will be further discussed during the half term scientific Metastava meeting.

8.2.3. WP3. Evaluation of the analytical properties of metagenomics workflows

WP3 teleconferences and questionnaires identified a final listing of samples that will be sequenced in each task (D-JRP8-3.1 contains a database of samples that will be sequenced for all model pathogens in WP3). This list was initially delayed due to the focus on methodology standardization in WP1, which did not cause significant delays in data generation. Sequencing in tasks JRP8-WP3-T1 through JRP8-WP3-T5 is starting in M12-13 for most datasets.

JRP8-WP3-T1: analytical sensitivity, HEV

Sequencing is starting in M12-13

JRP8-WP3-T2: analytical sensitivity, norovirus

Sequencing is starting in M12-13

JRP8-WP3-T3: analytical sensitivity, large DNA viruses

Sequencing is starting in M12-13

JRP8-WP3-T4: analytical sensitivity, STEC

Sequencing is starting in M12-13

JRP8-WP3-T5: analytical sensitivity, detection of ABR genes.

Sequencing is starting in M12-13

JRP8-WP3-T6: bioinformatics and statistical analysis of analytical performance experiments

A preliminary discussion about the bioinformatics and statistical analysis approaches has been launched. Due to the delay in D-JRP8-D3.1 and a delayed hiring at partner Sciensano, D-JRP8-3.2 will be delayed from M12 to M16 to allow a reasonable timeframe to discuss the standardization of the analysis methodology based on the sample panels identified in D-JRP8-3.1.

8.2.4. WP4: Concertation with ongoing efforts and dissemination.

JRP8-WP4-T1: concertation with ongoing initiatives.

Good integration with COMPARE via shared participation (FLI, ErasmusMC, ANSES). Steven Van Borm participated in two cogwheel workshops organized by the OHEJP, one with COMPARE (12.04.2018), and one with EFFORT (26.10.2018). Closest fit was observed with COMPARE. However, the exchange possibilities (e.g. protocols) were limited by reporting restrictions of COMPARE (e.g. COMPARE deliverables had to be validated by EC before becoming public). Public deliverables of COMPARE are taken into account when published (<https://www.compare-europe.eu/library/deliverables>) and where still possible integrated in the Metastava conclusions. However, given the short time frame available to Metastava, we cannot reconsider e.g. the decisions we made regarding methodologies (WP1). It should be stressed that several Metastava partners also participate in COMPARE, resulting in an indirect integration of e.g. methodologies. In addition, Metastava is indirectly linked by partner participation in GMI and relevant ISO norm meetings.

JRP8-WP4-T2: formal dissemination. (deadline: M24)

Two abstracts were presented at a scientific conference:

Liu L, Hakhverdyan M, Leijon M. The influence of sample preparations on high-throughput sequencing detection of viruses in clinical samples. The 11th International Congress for Veterinary Virology. Vienna, Austria, 27-30 August 2018.

Sander van Boheemen. Sample Pretreatment: Challenges in Virology. Workshop: ESCV Next Generations Sequencing in Clinical Virology. 20-21 November, 2018

JRP8-WP4-T3: dissemination of recommendations to stakeholders

Nothing to report in Y1 (deadline: M24)

8.2.5. WP5: Project management

JRP8-WP5-T1: Consortium agreement

The grant agreement of the entire Onehealth EJP covers all necessary agreements between partners and includes the work plan of our project as it was submitted. There is no need for a joint research project – level consortium agreement.

JRP8-WP5-T2: Internal communication

Pre-kickoff meeting phone calls with work package leaders. Kickoff meeting (21.02.2018, Brussels). WP1 phone calls (coordinator- WPL) about standardization. Internal WP1 questionnaires on data generation and data analysis + follow up teleconferences. Mailings to all collaborators or partner contacts about general EJP-OH information. Teleconference on WP1 standardization (end of M6). Internal WP1, WP2 (19/07/2018) and WP3 (5/10/2018) teleconferences. Internal WP3 questionnaire to document the sample collections. WPL/general assembly progress teleconference (11/12/2018).

8.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

8.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-1.1	Dataset: reference data metagenomics data generation	12	2/10/2018		Methodology documented and selected
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-1.2	Dataset: reference data metagenomics analysis	12	28/06/2018		Methodology in consortium documented and selected
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-1.3	List of sequence datasets	10		14	Partially delivered (public datasets). Partly to realize (partner's datasets from parallel projects).
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-2.3	Report on batch and contamination effects in metagenomics	12		16	Data generated. Analysis ongoing. Report to be written.
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-3.1	Spiked sample panels ready for analysis	6	m12	12	M9 report mentioned delay due to attention shift to WP1. Now all sample panels documented.
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-3.2	Procedure for analyzing analytical sensitivity and robustness datasets	12		14-16	Due to delay of D-JRP8-3.1
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-4.1	Report of meeting with ongoing initiatives to assure input in WP1	7	9.05.2018 Cogwheel workshop report		Cogwheel workshop report =EJP deliverable 4.3. The interaction with other initiatives will continue throughout the project.
METASTAVA	D-JRP8-5.1	Consortium agreement	6	27.09.2017		The OHEJP grant agreement contains all necessary details in the integrated Metastava work plan, and details interaction rules between partners. It hence replaces the consortium agreement

8.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast date	Comments
METASTAVA	M-JRP8-M1	Concertation meeting with ongoing initiatives	6	y		Cogwheel workshop with COMPARE and EFFORT. Additional contacts are ongoing.
METASTAVA	M-JRP8-M2	Public and own dataset identified	8	No	14	Partially delivered (public datasets). Partly to realize (partner's datasets from parallel projects).
METASTAVA	M-JRP8-M3	External control constructs ready for evaluation	10	y		
METASTAVA	M-JRP8-M4	Procedure for analysing analytical sensitivity and robustness datasets agreed	12	no	14	Due to delay D3.1
METASTAVA	M-JRP8-M5	Progress meeting	12	y/n	13	Teleconference done. Live midterm meeting in February

8.4. Publications and patents

Liu L, Hakhverdyan M, Leijon M. The influence of sample preparations on high-throughput sequencing detection of viruses in clinical samples. The 11th International Congress for Veterinary Virology. Vienna, Austria, 27-30 August 2018.

Sander van Boheemen. Sample Pretreatment: Challenges in Virology. Workshop: ESCV Next Generations Sequencing in Clinical Virology. 20-21 November, 2018

8.5. Impact & relevance

High throughput sequencing technologies are becoming key in the diagnosis and characterization of pathogens of veterinary and public health importance (e.g. <https://ecdc.europa.eu/sites/portal/files/media/en/publications/Publications/food-and-waterborne-diseases-next-generation-typing-methods.pdf>). Since metagenomics pathogen detection is in principal the method for comprehensive detection of all pathogens from all samples obtained from all hosts, the results outlined in this report are an important step towards closing the gap between veterinary and human diagnostics. The initiated efforts for cross validation of various methods from labs working in the different sectors are key to full integration of protocols from the different sectors. Therefore, initially proven protocols were collected and distributed among the partners with the aim to build a modular integrated workflow for diagnostic metagenomics. The modularity will enable stepwise harmonization because labs can switch to validated modules without the need to implement integral novel workflows. Currently, the final analyses of data obtained from cross validating experiments are ongoing, paving the way for the definition and application of harmonized procedures for diagnostic metagenomics in veterinary and human health and the food sector. The results of the validation undertaken within Metastava will be published and hence flow into the definition of the relevant ISO standards. Moreover, our efforts to standardize and validate metagenomics methods and their implementation in Vet and Med reference laboratories will allow better understanding of these methods and help further exploit NGS based diagnostics as an integrative platform for all sectors. Additionally, its complementarity to other diagnostic methods, as well as increased preparedness for emerging threats will be further elucidated..

8.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of biological samples, human and non-human animal (as appropriate) have been sought.	Each partner provided a detailed statement describing their measures to safeguard data protection, ethics, safety and biosafety and the way this is integrated with national and EU legislation. These statements are available on request form the JRP leader.
The applicants must confirm the compliance with GDPR	Each partner provided a detailed statement describing their measures to safeguard data protection, ethics, safety and biosafety and the way this is integrated with national and EU legislation.

	These statements are available on request form the JRP leader.
The applicants must document the safety mitigation measures in place to protect the staff	Each partner provided a detailed statement describing their measures to safeguard data protection, ethics, safety and biosafety and the way this is integrated with national and EU legislation. These statements are available on request form the JRP leader.

8.7. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	yes
Delay in work plan execution	yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information:

- Delay in work plan execution : partner Sciensano-animal health had to replace a critical senior laboratory expert. New person only implemented in Metastava from September 2018.
- Key management positions in the JRP had to be replaced (Work Package leadership). Has been sorted thanks to flexibility of the consortium team during the first months of the project.
- Only minimal delays in the work plan execution as documented in the present report.

8.8. *Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project*

- MAD-Vir (OHEJP-JRP): contacts about virus discovery methodologies and metagenomics.
- COMPARE : cogwheel workshop. Shared partners.
- EFFORT: cogwheel workshop. Shared partners.
- European Society for Clinical Virology: shared partners. Workshop participation by EMC.
- European Society for Veterinary Virology: shared partners. Conference participation by SVA.

8.10. List of dissemination and communication activities

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Joint 11th International Congress for Veterinary Virology and 12th Annual meeting EPIZONE.</i>		
	<i>Liu L, Hakhverdyan M, Leijon M. The influence of sample preparations on high-throughput sequencing detection of viruses in clinical samples.</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>27-30 August 2018.</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Vienna, Austria</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>y</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>320</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Cogwheel workshop between OH-EJP and COMPARE</i>		
Date:	<i>12.04. 2018.</i>		
Place:	<i>teleconference</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>y</i>
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Cogwheel workshop between OH-EJP and EFFORT</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>26.10.2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>teleconference</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>y</i>
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>Workshop: ESCV Next Generations Sequencing in Clinical Virology</i> <i>Title: Sample Pretreatment: Challenges in Virology</i> <i>Presenter: Sander van Boheemen, Erasmus MC</i>		
Date:	20-21 November, 2018		
Place:	Leiden, The Netherlands		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	y
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	40	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

8.11. *List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year*

- M13: First annual meeting (face to face, Brussels, 18 February 2019).
- M15: Intermediate progress teleconference with focus on WP2 and WP3
- M18: Intermediate progress teleconference with focus on WP1; WP2; WP3

9. AIR SAMPLE

9.1. *Summary of the work carried out*

The project is proceeding according to the plan, there is a good sense of collaboration and active dialogue by e-mail, exchange of protocols, Skype meetings and phone calls. Eleven newsletters were circulated to stimulate the internal communication (Appendix 1).

The project has a formal agreement with Sartorius (Germany), that supplied the partners with equipment (AirPort 8) and air filters for sampling poultry farms last summer 2018. All partners were in contact with their local Sartorius office, obtained the equipment and implemented the protocol.

Overall, the project will move through the following four phases:

Harmonization ->Implementation > Evaluation > Validation.

We have completed the method harmonization and implementation phases. During the summer, we focused on sampling, sample analysis and data generation. All protocols were implemented by the partners between April and June 2018 (Appendix 2). The results of the sampling were discussed at the Annual project meeting on September 27-28 in Teramo, Italy. It was agreed to use one pair (one per foot) of sock samples according to national practice. However, the socks were weighed in advance, wetted and then enriched in a broth according to the ISO protocol in the ratio of 1:10 (or 1+9). *Campylobacter* colony confirmation were done by colony PCR or colony-MALDI-TOF, in the case the biochemical testing is too tedious.

DTU has carried out extensive spiking experiments on the filter system, which needs further optimization if it is to be used for DNA purification and PCR. In addition, the presence of blood in Bolton broth has inhibited the PCR. Hence, it was decided at this stage to abandon the harmonization of PCR testing on this summer's samples until these technical problems are resolved. Nevertheless, some partners have setup their own PCR to analyze the filters and sock swabs using their own in-house PCR protocol.

9.2. *Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results*

JRP9-WP1-T1: Sampling activities and creation of a sample bank (air and boot-swab samples) from different regions.

For the creation of a sample bank of air samples, the method of culturing, size of gelatin filters, temperature, time, volume of samples and samples preparation have been optimised . The work has been done by inoculating the gelatine filters with different levels of *Campylobacter jejuni*.

The same results were obtained for the incubation of ½ filters in Bolton Broth for 44±4 h and the incubation of boot socks ISO 10272-1. There were no false results from gelatin filters. In addition, the PCR results from the filters corresponded to the results obtained with the culture based method.

Optimisation of protocols for boot swab samples were provided by NVI. The protocols were optimised with regard to ISO 10272-1 for the detection of *Campylobacter* in the boot socks of own choice. Both protocols were shared among the partners. The protocols include the sampling step, cultural method, optimised PCR step and the storage (Figure1)

Figure1. Protocols for culture-based detection of *Campylobacter* from chicken farms.

For the sample bank, a “Farm questionnaire” was designed. The metadata associated with sample collection includes:

1. Type of farm with biosecurity measures: organic or conventional farm (open housing farms must be exclude)
2. Size of the farm (number of houses)
3. Size of the house (square meters; or length x breadth)
4. Size of flock (number of chicken per house)
5. Type of bedding: Shavings, sawdust, straw, paper, peat, etc.
6. Age of chicken coming in and out the house
7. Feed composition or feed compound type
8. Additional equipment (floor heating, fly net, etc.)
9. Type of chicken breed
10. Chicken supplier
11. Number of breeding cycles per house and year
12. Type of disinfection
13. Biosecurity measures (rodent and insect control, dead-bird disposal, water sanitation, litter removal, visitor’s control, owner’ pets on the farm)
14. Health care anamnestic data (use of antibiotics; first week mortality)
15. Date
16. Age of animals (days)
17. Outdoor temperature
18. Indoor temperature
19. Farm region (not exact address, because identity of farms participating in the sampling plans are not be revealed.)
- 20.
- 21.
- 22.

The data was stored on the drives of the participating institutions. All stored samples were linked to the farm's questionnaire lists. The 1mLx2 of each positive enriched samples and the extracted DNA were stored at minimum -70°C in the facilities of each partner. The data was shared among the partners. The data (results) will be associated with the analyses of electronic journals/ reports stored in the institutional servers of the participating countries. The raw data was stored in Mx3000P and Mx3005P QPCR Systems instruments, Microsoft Excel files, Microsoft Word in the institutional servers of the project participants.

Sampling activities for creation Sample bank

The DTU sampled at three farms with five different houses. One house was found to be positive for both boot socks and air filters. Overall, it was found that the results from the incubation of ½ filters in Bolton broth for 44±4 h are the same as the results of the incubation of boot socks (ISO), with no false results from gelatin filters. In addition, the PCR results from the filters corresponded to the results obtained with the culture based method.

In June 2018, the NVI sampled eight flocks from seven farms by collecting one pair of sock samples and one air filter sample from each flock. In September 2018, NVI also sampled two flocks from one farm. Here, one pair of sock samples and two air filter samples were collected from each flock. NVI found three flocks positive for boot socks, while all the air filters were negative.

The VRI sampled ten different houses from four farms. From each house, two pair of socks and two air filters were sampled. According to the cultivation method, all the flocks were negative. Nevertheless, the molecular methods retrieved two positive samples out of the ten samples. Gelatine filters do not seem to be able to keep campylobacters alive, and a 15-minute air sampling does not seem sufficient. The cultivation methods do not seem sensitive enough, whereas the PCR method (direct DNA extraction) is more effective in some filter samples.

The NVRI sampled from two farms with three houses at eight different time points. The first two samplings showed positive PCR results from filters, but they could confirm the results through strain isolation only from socks for sampling no. 2, and only after 24h incubation in Bolton broth. For the remaining samplings, two out of six were positive in culturing from socks but only in one of the air filters *C. jejuni* was isolated. Finally, three filters showed positive PCR results. In conclusion, for the socks samples, plating out after incubation in Bolton broth for 24h, seems better, perhaps due to a high level of background microflora present in direct plating. Air filter-culture based detection gave one positive result, while in real-time PCR, the air filters resulted in three positive results. In one case (sampling no. 3), for the positive samples, 100% correlation was observed (the same results for socks, filter culturing and real-time PCR). For the negative samples, four times (sampling numbers 4, 5, 7 and 8) resulted in 100% correlation for different type of samples. Three samplings gave divergent results for various kind of samples.

The IZSAM sampled in ten different houses from two farms. From each house, two boot socks pairs and two air filters were sampled. The culturing was performed using direct plating and enrichment using the Bolton broth. The DNA was extracted directly from air filters and boot socks. For the first five houses the culturing from boot socks revealed one positive sample using the direct plating while all the enriched samples were negative, and the air filters were all negative. The other five houses were positive to the direct plating and negative to the enrichment method, while one air filter was positive to the enrichment. Direct plating for boot socks was shown to be the best option while enrichment with Bolton Broth was not the appropriate method for the isolation of *Campylobacter* from boot socks.

Summary results of field studies shown in Table 1 below:

Country	No of samples (n)	Number of positive samples							
		Boot socks				Air filters			
		cultivation methods		real-time PCR		cultivation methods		real-time PCR	
		direct plating	enrichment	direct	enrichment	direct plating	enrichment	direct	enrichment
Italy	10	6	0	7	5	0	1	8	5
Czech R.	10	-	0	-	0	-	0	2	0
Norway	10	-	3	-	-	-	-	0	-
Poland	8	-	3	-	-	-	1	3	-
Denmark	6	-	1	-	-	-	1	1	-

JRP9-WP1-T2: Development of a protocol for non-complex DNA extraction for diagnostic qPCR and metagenomics analysis from gelatin-filter samples.

DNA extraction

For PCR- and metagenomics detection of *Campylobacter* in air using gelatin filters following parameters were tested:

size of the filter, filter preparation before DNA extraction, methods of DNA extraction. The DNA concentration was measured in duplicate using Qubit and Nanodrop spectrophotometer.

Size of the filter. Whole filter, ½ filter and ¼ filter were analysed. The results showed that ¼ filter gave the best PCR results, when the sample was enriched.

Filter preparation before DNA extraction.

Sartorius method from Microsart Genprep and an initial protease treatment, using the DTU method, were compared. Protease treatment gave the best results.

Methods of DNA extraction:

The following DNA purification kits were included:

- 1) Sartorius. Microsart Genprep. Concentration and DNA Extraction Kit for Liquids ≥100 ml.

- 2) QIAampFastDNAstool mini kit, QIAGEN with modifications.
- 3) DNeasy® Blood & Tissue. QIAGEN with modifications.
- 4) MagneSil KF Genomic system Promega in KingFischer.
- 5) PowerSoil DNA Isolations kit with modifications.
- 6) Power Soil DNA isolation kit (QIAGEN with modifications in step 1) and further modifications according Wenjun Jiang et al. 2015.

Every biological sample from DNA extractions was tested with qPCR in duplicate. PCR reactions were performed on an Mx3005P (Stratagene, Agilent Technologies, Hørsholm, Denmark) using a protocol for the detection of a 287 bp sequence of the 16S rRNA gene from *C. jejuni*, *C. coli* and *C. lari* (Josefsen et al. 2010)(Appendix 3)

Results show that:

- All DNA purification kits gave low DNA concentrations.
- PCR results from all kits (excluding QIAampFastDNAstool mini kit and Microsart Genprep) gave positive signals from 10² and higher levels of spiking.
- DNeasy Blood&Tissue Kit protocol (with some modifications) gave stable and good results for PCR and DNA measurements.
- The PowerSoil DNA Isolations kit (with the necessary modifications) is quite time consuming, in particular with the modifications suggested by Jiang et al. 2015.
- The Sartorius Microsart Genprep is time consuming and needs several optimizations, but is good to handle a whole filter.
- Overall, none of the DNA purification kits tested resulted in a high DNA concentration.
- Blood&Tissue kit could be used for DNA purification from filters using a pre-treatment with Protex (a protease), as well as on Bolton enriched broth.

The benefits of the Microsart GenPrep was the use of whole filters that could be used across the countries. Nevertheless, the method was time and labour consuming with the use of special and costly equipment. The challenges from the other methods are: The use of only ¼ of filter (too much proteins), and the MagneSil KF Genomic system Promega, which needs the KingFisher machine. The DNeasy Blood&Tissue Kit protocol with some DTU modifications was selected for future studies. However, none of the methods allowed the DNA purification of many samples at the same time, the kits are expensive and finally, the quality of the DNA for metagenomics should be evaluated.

Metagenomics analysis

Positive and negative samples from the field study were selected. Shotgun metagenomics analysis were performed on selected samples at IZS. Shotgun metagenomics and metagenomics with larger depth were also performed on selected and inoculated samples at DTU.

IZC performed shotgun metagenomics using Minlon (Oxford Nanopore) technology. The first experiment comprised air filters spiked in with *C. jejuni* cells from 10,000 to 10. The analyses showed the presence of *C. jejuni* reads for all the samples but the positivity was possible at least for the filters spiked in with 10,000 and 1,000 cells. The second experiment was applied to five DNAs from air filters in addition to one DNA obtained from the boot sock. The experiment paired the PCRs with the metagenomics. Overall, the samples were found positive

with a total amount of reads from 0.3% to 0.5% of the total reads. The reads were assigned to the *Campylobacter* genus. Filter background (negative control) were measured as a false positive. We do not know whether this is a *Campylobacter* or a *Campylobacter* associated microbiome. In future investigations, other air filter samples from poultries will be tested, cross-contamination will be monitored, and replicate for spiking-in will be set up.

DTU carried out metagenomics by using Illumina MiSeq. DTU has tested two positive airfield samples, One sample was a non-spiked filter and one sample was spiked without filter. The tested samples were negative airfield samples, spiked with *Campylobacter* cells from 5000 down to 10. All samples were pre-treated with enzyme Protex (Danisco) before the DNA extraction step. The DNA sequencing resulted in positive identification of one of the naturally contaminated, positive samples and the spiked sample without filter. All sequencing results were of poor quality. The experiment showed that the method needs to be further optimized before it can be used in industrial settings.

NVI proposed the setup of the next experiment for the use of the PCR methods and the metagenomics. The PCR from NVI uses primers and probes from Josefson et al. (2010). The metagenomics will use Illumina sequencing on spiked and sterile filtered air samples from Norwegian flocks. The spike-in includes *C. jejuni* from 5,650 to 56 CFU. The experiment was carried out in December 2018.

The raw DNA sequence data of analyses were stored in FASTA files, on the computers connected to the Mx3000P and Mx3005P qPCR instruments, in Microsoft Excel files, Microsoft Word, PDF, or the Analyses Reports on the computer servers of the project participants.

Experiments raised the question about DNA concentration and DNA quality, false positive results from the negative filters, quality of sequence on both machines, which affects quality/results of bioinformatics. This should be investigated in future experiments.

9.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

9.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
AIR Sample	D-JRP9-1.1.	Prototype laboratory method to detect and enumerate <i>Campylobacter</i> in air samples.	9	3 August 2018		
AIR Sample	D-JRP9-1.2.	Prototype metagenomics method for characterization of <i>Campylobacter</i> in air samples.	12	Dec 15 2018		

9.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
AIR SAMPLE	M-JRP9-1	Sample bank is established	9	Yes		A decentralized sample bank at partner organizations involved.
AIR SAMPLE	M-JRP9-2	Sample preparation method is selected	9	Yes		QiaAMP Tissue&Blood kit

9.4. Publications and patents

The following draft manuscript is in preparation:

Giuliano Garofolo, Gro S. Johannessen, Ivana, Renata, Kinga, Jasek, Julia, Mona Torp, Jeffrey Hoorfar. *Campylobacter* in chicken houses – critical parameters for international, multicentre evaluation of sampling and detection methods. For submission to Food Control.

9.5. Impact & relevance

In the EU, monitoring of *Campylobacter* in poultry is mandatory according to Directive 2003/99/EC. Our aim is to develop and validate air sampling as a low-cost and multi-purpose alternative to fecal droppings or boot swabs. The project will provide the European community (authorities, industry) with a low-cost and harmonized tool for interventions and codes of best practices. The main outcome is a harmonized and standardized, filter-based sampling protocol that can replace the current cumbersome and time-consuming microbiological methods. Air sampling should be feasible for surveillance, monitoring and eradication of *Campylobacter* in confined and bio-secured broiler production. So far, we have completed the method harmonization and implementation phases. The harmonized protocols have been uploaded on the OneHealth-EJP website and made available to all reference labs. This is expected to facilitate method harmonization across the consortium, and a later stage, across Europe.

9.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
Due to the sampling protocol, the programme team may be collecting personal and business data. Please confirm compliance with GDPR.	This project does not make use of animals and will not impact any societal or ethical aspects. The identity of farms participating in the sampling plans will not be revealed. All personal and business data collected will be treated confidentially and in accordance with strict national and EU data law.
'Samples' are collected in an animal unit, please confirm no animal experimentation approvals are required for the animal sampling protocols (e.g. do to interventions, restrictions, etc)	This project does not have animal experimentations.

9.7. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	no
Delay in work plan execution	no
Conflicts within the consortium	no
Lack of commitment of partners	no
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	no
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	no
Potential entry/exit of partners	no
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information: /

9.8. *Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project*

We will present the project at the next EJP annual meeting in Dublin, Ireland. Dissemination meeting at the national levels have been planned for 2019. Two pitch events have been done by the project leader, one at the last MetVetNet annual meeting in Reading, UK, and the second at the annual FFOQSI meeting in Tulln Austria.

9.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:		<i>One-day Sartorius Workshop in</i>	
Date:		<i>January 2018.</i>	
Place:		<i>National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark</i>	
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activity linked to the One Health EJP project			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>EJP web-site</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>no</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Special course for DTU students</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>Fall Semester 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>EJP web-site</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>no</i>		
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

Name of the activity:	<i>FoQCSI annual meeting</i>		
Date:	<i>October 2018</i>		
Place:	<i>Vienna, Austria</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Training:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>EJP web-site</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>no</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>2</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>10</i>		

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>Department workshop</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>November 19, 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Training:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>EJP web-site</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>no</i>		
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

Name of the activity:	<i>Department workshop on Data Management Plan</i>		
Date:	<i>November 2018</i>		
Place:	<i>National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Pitch Event: DTU-Innovation Office, September 2018.</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Training:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>EJP web-site</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>no</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	<i>DTU-Innovation Office</i>		
<i>Date:</i>	<i>September 2018</i>		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark</i>		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Training:</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>yes</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>EJP web-site</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>no</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>no</i>		
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

9.10. *List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year*

- Metagenomics meeting will be hold by March 2019 at the latest.
- The DTU will prepare online animation material (video) for the education of broiler industry. The deadline is August 2019.
- Decentral dissemination through hands-on, wet-lab workshops will be held towards the end of 2019.
- Two workshops and 5-8 Skype meetings are envisaged for 2019.

10. MoMIR-PPC

10.1. *Summary of the work carried out*

This project is based on recent studies, which have uncovered the importance of host heterogeneity in the most important zoonotic infections. In particular, it has been shown that a minority of the infected individuals (Super-shedders) are responsible for the majority of the transmissions and thus infections. To improve the microbial safety of food and to develop new preventive measures for controlling zoonosis, we have to take into account this heterogeneity of infection and target the interventions to the super-shedders. Moreover, it seems important to determine why some animals are super-shedders and other are low-shedders. Preliminary data suggested the role of gut microbiota in addition to variability of the host immune response. In this project, we will develop new approaches to predict, identify and prevent the appearance of animal super-shedders based on immune response and gut microbiota composition and to identify the risk factors to be human carriers. Moreover, developing new mathematical models of pathogen transmission within a population taking into account the heterogeneity of infection and the role of gut microbiota will help to test several intervention strategies in order to optimize husbandry and feeding practices, but also decrease the use of antimicrobials and block the spread of antimicrobials resistance genes.

The start of the project has been in part delayed due to the withdrawal of a number of partners. Indeed, SAIM is no longer member of the EJP consortium, Vet-DTU has been closed by Danish government, A.L. Wester left the NIPH. Consequently, the project proposed by NIPH has been modified and is now supervised by AC Stüken. Works devoted to SAIM will be in part performed by Partner 18 and H. Dashalov group (NDRVMI) entered within the consortium to performed the Vet-DTU works. Due to these difficulties, some experiments have been delayed especially those using pigs and related to human *Salmonella* infection. Consequently, numerous experiments were performed but are not analyzed yet and/or the interpretation of the results are not finalized. Nevertheless, very interesting results have already emerged from the MoMIR-PPC project.

Concerning the immune response in chicks, we showed that level of non-specific immunoglobulins cannot be a predictive marker for level of *Salmonella* shedding. Similarly, the *Salmonella* specific IgA responses was low just after infection and it was not related to the low and high shedder phenotypes. Interestingly, low-shedders show a significant earlier increase in total IgM level than observed with high shedders and naïve chicks. The relationship between this earlier total IgM response and the low *Salmonella* colonization needs to be further analysed. The blood cell composition and the transcriptomic level, which are under analysis, should help us to confirm and interpret these results.

Concerning the microbiota composition, we identified two predictive markers for the low-shedder phenotype. The presence of these bacterial genus, before infection, in chicks that will become low-shedders after *Salmonella* infection open the way to the development of predictive diagnostic kits. We are waiting for the interpretation of the pig experiments to validate these promising results.

We already purified and characterized numerous putative probiotic strains for poultry and pigs, which will be tested in experimental and farm conditions by several partners.

We developed an *in vitro* gut model (chicken and pigs) to test *in vitro* the growth conditions of putative probiotics and their potential to mitigate zoonotic pathogens. We have also identified the prebiotics that could favour their growth. Several nutraceuticals have been tested in laying hens and have demonstrated their efficacy and their impact on gut microbiota.

To analyse the transmission of zoonotic pathogens and improve intervention strategies, a generic mathematical model of the dynamic interplay between the gut microbiota, the pathogen and the host's immune response has been formulated. The model was used to explore biological scenarios that contain between-animal heterogeneity in the pathogen concentration in the gut. An experiment studying the indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* between broilers has been performed. Numerous exchanges of data between partners will improve this first model.

10.2. *Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results*

10.2.1. WP1. WP0: Management

JRP10-WP0-T1: Draft and agree Consortium Agreement

As a consortium agreement was signed between the EJP coordinator ANSES and the EJP beneficiaries, we considered at the first MoMIR-PPC meeting that it was unnecessary to sign a particular consortium agreement at the MoMIR-PPC level.

JRP10-WP0-T2: Produce project-planning, control documentation and Data Management Plan.

The project planning has been modified several times due to the departure of SAIM from the EJP consortium and of Vet-DTU, which has been closed by its Government. We also modified the project planning of the Norwegian Institute of Public Health because Astrid Louise Wester left her institute. The modified project planning was approved by the EJP Board in June (month 6). The Data Management Plan has been performed in relation with the EJP board. It will be finalized with the help of the EJP board (especially Valérie De Waele, Sciensano) in January 2019. An Excel file describing the different animal experiments, the samplings and the analyses, which will be performed, is circulating among the MoMIR-PPC members. We expect to share this file through the EJP website, but this has been delayed.

JRP10-WP0-T3: Control and manage activity progresses, the timely delivery of project tasks and outputs

Numerous exchanges have been performed to supplant the withdrawals of Vet-DTU and SAIM, as well as the modifications of the program, which will be performed by Norwegian partners due to the departure of A.L. Wester. These major modifications have an impact on the activity progress, but all the consequences have been taken into consideration and managed. Numerous exchanges between partners have been made to define who will test what, especially concerning the pro and prebiotics, which will be tested in farms and to define the immune related markers, which will be tested by partners. Informal meetings and exchanges of data have been made for the development of the mathematical models.

10.2.2. WP1. Risk prediction for Super-shedder animals and human asymptomatic carriers through the use of gut microbiota and immune status analyses.

The goal of this WP is to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to high/low shedding before and/or after infection, which allow us to predict and identify the animals, which will be high-shedders. To decrease the number of animals tested and to correlate immune response and gut microbiota composition, in the majority of cases, the same animal will be used to define immunological (WP1-T1) and microbiota markers (WP1-T2) and to test the virulence of *Salmonella* strains (WP1-T3).

JRP10-WP1-T1: Predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

The goal of the task will be to identify immune markers able to identify the super-Shedders and other able to predict the most susceptible animals and/or the animals that will become super-shedders, if infected. The activities will be focused on the most prevalent serotypes: *S. typhimurium* for pig and *S. enteritidis* for chicken.

Concerning experimental infection of pigs, they have been delayed, but all experiments are in progress. Several exchanges between partners allowed us to define the best conditions to define immunological markers. A set of immune markers to be tested has been defined by partners and especially by Partners 27 and 29 after a review of the literature. The first step was, indeed, an in-depth review of the current literature in order to investigate the activation and differentiation of naive T cells into TH1/Th2/TH17 and in N1/N2 population. In particular it was assessed: 1. the unique immune status of the super-shedding animals compared to animals that have lower levels of *Salmonella* in their gut; 2. the role of the neutrophils and TH1; 3. which responses are required to mediate protection against a variety of intracellular infections, and the several immune markers. These immunological panels were considered to be analyzed, at the beginning, on mice, due to the greater availability and the easy-to-study character of the animals, and then in pigs and chickens.

Partner 27, from ISS, carried out experimental studies on 40 CD1 mice during the first experimental phase, and 20 CD1 mice, during the second, of 8-10 weeks old, which were inoculated at day 1, by intraperitoneal route, with 2×10^2 CFU of a wild type strain of *Salmonella typhimurium*, 14028 strain, which allowed us to obtain a sub-lethal infection in a susceptible mice with a good response to infection. At day 0 and 7 blood was collected from orbital sinus. At day 7 after infection, the animals were euthanized and spleens were collected. The number of viable *S. typhimurium* strain was determined by plating serial dilutions on LB agar plates. We obtained a wide distribution of the colonies, from a low to a high, passing through an intermediate population, confirming a different ability of *S. typhimurium* to colonize the spleens. This allowed us to select two groups of mice, with low and high *S. typhimurium* spleen colonization, for further studies on the involvement of the immune system specific for the two levels of infection spread.

We, then, performed several parallel studies, whose results are still ongoing, to analyze the immune system:

- The serum, obtained from the blood at 0 and 7 days post-infection, and the spleen were used to analyse 23 cytokines at the same time, for each sample, by Luminex technology. This technique is a bead-based multiplexed immunoassay system in a microplate format. This experiment is allowing us to look for changes in concentrations of multiple targets under the two different conditions. In particular, we are looking for the following cytokines: IL-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-3, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-9, IL-10, IL-12 (p40), IL-12 (p70), IL-13, IL-17A, Eotaxin, G-CSF, GM-CSF, IFN- γ , KC, MCP-1 (MCAF), MIP-1 α , MIP-1 β , RANTES, TNF- α .
- The spleens were also used for the high throughput transcriptome studies to obtain a specific transcriptome databases for the identification of genes that are differentially expressed in the two distinct shedding populations.

- Histopathological analysis are also planned to discriminate and differentiate the low and high-shedders in terms of inflammatory response (lymphohistiocytic, neutrophilic, eosinophilic).

Partner 29, from IZSLER, started the procedure for authorization in accordance with directive of the Service for Biotechnology and Animal Welfare of the Istituto Superiore di Sanità and authorized by the Italian Ministry of Health, adhered to the guidelines contained in Italian Legislative Decree 116/92, based on European Directive 86/609/EEC on Laboratory Animal Protection (decree numbers 84/12.B and 255/2012.B). Whilst waiting for the procedure authorization, the selection of *Salmonella* free farms with negative and seronegative sows was carried out. The animals were confirmed as *Salmonella*-free using microbiological and serological analysis. The health status of the farm of origin was monitored during last years. Particularly, the selection of *Salmonella* free sows farms was conducted by confirmation of the negative production of antibodies against a broad range of serogroups (IDEXX Herd-check Swine *Salmonella* Antibody test kit) and faecal samples, collected during last weeks of pregnancy, were negative for *Salmonella* culture performed in accordance with ISO 6579:2002. Similarly, serum and feces of their piglets, that will be enrolled in the studies, will be collected a week before movement to test seroconversion and presence of positive culture.

Partner 1, from ANSES, has started a trial with a total of 45 piglets, which were divided into 5 random groups: one group with five piglets as control and 4 groups each with 10 piglets (n=40) as inoculated pigs. The 40 inoculated piglets at 7 weeks of age received orally 10 ml of suspension of 10^8 UFC/ml of a monophasic variant of *S. typhimurium* strain. Following challenge the pigs were monitored for 3 weeks. Twice a week, faeces were sampled in order to quantify *Salmonella* and follow the excretion of *Salmonella* from the pigs during the trial, which will be determined by calculating the LAUC (Log area under the curve). High and low shedders will then be identified and monitored further. During the experimental trial, blood samples were taken twice a week and total blood cells were enumerated. Serum and blood have been frozen for further analysis (ELISA tests, Transcriptomic etc...). The purpose of the study is to ultimately identify predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in pigs. Similar pig immune markers will be tested by partners 27, 29, and 1.

Partner 18, from INRA tried to identify predictive immunological markers associated with high and low shedders in chickens. Experimental infection of chicken have been performed month 4 and 6. Partner 18 has analyzed the immune response by flow cytometry, transcriptional response and level of immunoglobulins. For this task, a Post doc who has carried out her PhD in Partner 27's (ISS) labs, has been recruited by Partners 18 (INRA-Tours). She will manage part of the work devoted to SAIM. Currently, she analysed the differences of the humoral immune response of low and high-shedders and compared their response to non-infected chicks by measuring the production of total (non-specific) IgA, IgY, IgM before and after infection. The specific anti-*Salmonella* LPS IgA response in serum of chickens was also recorded at different time-points. Generally, the analysis has revealed that the total antibody responses follow a classical pattern with a rise in levels of total IgM preceding the rise in IgY. The total immunoglobulin response was low before infection and increase after infection. Moreover, no significant differences were observed, before infection, between naïve, low shedders and high shedders. This result shows that level of immunoglobulin cannot be a predictive marker for low shedders and high shedders. Interestingly, just after infection, low-shedders show a significant earlier increase in total IgM level than high shedders and naïve chicks. In contrast, IgY levels were higher in super-shedders compared to low-shedders/naïve chicks and thus seems to early discriminate between high-shedders and low-shedders/naïve; in fact, a statistically significant increase in IgY level has been observed at 7 days post infection in high-shedders when compared with low-shedders and control groups. Finally, the evaluation of anti-*Salmonella* LPS IgA levels has revealed a lack of response in all the samples analysed except in two of them, suggesting that anti-*Salmonella* IgA response is not a good candidate to investigate differences between low-shedders and high-shedders in contrast to total IgM response. Does the high IgM response in low shedders explain their phenotype, needs to be further analysed. The level of IgY after infection seems related to the level of bacteria. For this experiment, the blood cell

composition and the transcriptomic level are under analysis. This work had been performed in collaboration with the Bernd Kaspers's lab (U. Munich), during a short stay, funded by MoMIR-PPC.

Figure 1: Level of total IgM response before and after *Salmonella* infection. Chicks were infected by the oral route at 7 days of age (point 0).

JRP10-WP1-T2: Predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

The goal of the task is to analyse the gut microbiota composition before and after *Salmonella* infection to identify predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs.

Several studies indicate an overall influence of the gut microbiota composition on *Salmonella* colonization and suggested its involvement in the development of the low/high-shedder phenotypes. We previously demonstrated that it is possible to transfer through gut microbiota the high shedder phenotype in chicks as well as the resistance to *Salmonella* colonization, suggesting that gut microbiota composition before *Salmonella* infection determines the low/high-shedder phenotypes. In light of these results, the differences of microbiota composition (genus frequencies) among high-, intermediate and low-shedders were investigated using variance analyses before and after infection. We detected a total of nine genera presenting significant differential abundances among the 3 shedding categories, for at least one sampling time. Interestingly, this included two genera presenting reasonably high relative abundance (> 5%), that were more abundant before infection in the low-shedder chicks: *Enterococcus* sp. (at 7 days age, *i.e.* just before infection) and *Streptococcus* sp. (at 7 and 11 days (before and after infection)). This result suggested that high level of *Enterococcus* and/or *Streptococcus* before infection correlated to the low shedder phenotype. The correlation high *Enterococcus* level before infection and low *Salmonella* level after infection has been in part confirmed in an independent experiment. These results suggested that presence of *Enterococcus* and *Streptococcus* could be a predictive markers of low shedder phenotype. In other words, presence of these bacteria correlated to low *Salmonella* colonization. We will test in the next experiments if these bacteria can protect against *Salmonella* colonization and thus could be used as probiotics.

This work has been performed in collaboration with partner 8 (Ivan Rychlik, VRI, CZ).

Figure 2: PCA analysis of the genus frequencies observed before infection (i.e. at 5 and 7 days of age), in order to highlight predictive markers among the three shedding level categories (Low (resistant), intermediate and high (super) shedder phenotypes). Chicks were orally infected at 7 days of age and faecal samples were recovered before and after *Salmonella* infection. Gut microbiota composition was analysed by 16S rDNA sequencing.

The analyses in pigs have been delayed, but numerous samples have been already collected and will be analyzed in few months. A collaboration between the ISS-IZSLER (partners 27-29) and the University of Surrey (partner 22) partners is in taking place to analyze the gut microbiota of pigs. Similarly, the faecal samples before and after pig infection have been recovered by ANSES (partner1) and will be analyzed by partner 22.

The data obtained, concerning the immunological markers (before and after infection) will be compared with the microbiological ones to study the existing correlations.

JRP10-WP1-T3: Risk factors associated with prolonged convalescent *Salmonella* shedding in humans

No scientific results are available yet. The task is delayed due to difficulties to obtain all necessary permissions to use personal and health related data in accordance with GDPR. Data collection is currently planned to start 01.01.2019. Study and recruitment protocols, information letters for potential participants and a task-specific website (in Norwegian) have been established.

JRP10-WP1-T4: Virulence of *Salmonella* strains originated from high and low shedders

Due to the delay in some animal experiments, the recovery of *Salmonella* strains from low and high shedders has also been delayed. Several partners have already recovered and stored *Salmonella* strains. The strains from the different pig experiments will be sent in the first quarter of 2019. The level of virulence will be thus measured in March 2019. The purpose is to follow the level of virulence of the inoculated strain during the trial through animal excretion and see any relation of this level of virulence with high and low shedders.

10.2.3. WP2. Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedder animals and asymptomatic carriage in humans and animals by modifying feed and/or microbiota

The removal of super-shedders from a population may significantly reduce transmission and contamination with pathogens. However, far from being beneficial, prolonged antibiotic treatment may alter dramatically the intestinal flora composition, may increase the pathogen's antimicrobial resistance and trigger the super-shedder phenotype (Ng et al Nature 2013; Sana & Monack 2016 Nature). The aim of WP2 is to ascertain, through the use of -omics technology, whether pre-biotics, pro-biotics or nutraceutical formula would be able to lower the numbers of *Salmonella*. The tasks included in this WP are still in progress, so no final result has been obtained yet. However, promising data have been achieved from the partners involved.

JRP10-WP2-T1: Use of probiotics in chickens and pigs

The main objective of this task will be to improve immune response and barrier effect procured by gut microbiota by introducing already identified probiotics.

Partner 22 (Univ. of Surrey) have been isolated *Lactobacillus* spp. from both chickens (105 isolates) and pigs (80 isolates). To date these isolates have been identified by PCR and 16S rDNA sequencing as *Lactobacillus* spp. and established to be genetically unique (using random amplification of polymorphic DNA (RAPD)). Work is currently being undertaken to ensure that isolates meet the EFSA probiotic guidelines and are inhibitory against several relevant *S. typhimurium* isolates.

In parallel, a chicken probiotic library from previous research at partner 22 is being investigated for suitable targets to take forward to the *in vivo* studies, which will be carried out by NDRVMI. NDRVMI has supplanted the left of Vet-DTU and has joined the MoMIR-PPC consortium only recently. Four isolates have now been identified from this library for *in vivo* use and the transfer of these isolates and the development of a study protocol has recently been initiated.

Finally, partner 18 (INRA) has tested the protective activity of *Enterococcus faecium* against *Salmonella* colonization with no clear success. This putative probiotic strain was identified as a predictive biomarker in WP1 and thus was tested as a probiotic strain in WP2.

JRP10-WP2-T2: Use of pre-biotics and nutraceutical already defined by the consortium partners in chicken and pig

The goal of this Task is to measure the effect of several pre-biotics and nutraceuticals on gut microbiota composition and protection against pathogens in farms and in experimental conditions.

For experiment with chickens, Partner 8 (VRI) developed a model for *in vitro* testing of growth conditions of particular gut microbiota members. He tested specific supplementations of nutrient broths to identify bacterial species, which are dependent on particular supplements or growth substrates. So far, they have found out that addition of all tested mono- or oligosaccharides into nutrient broths positively selected for *Lactobacilli*. Though the explanation of this observation is quite simple, i.e. that *Lactobacilli* rapidly fermented carbohydrates into organic acids, decreased pH and therefore also the growth of competing microbiota members, this may also explain the protective effect of *Lactobacilli* against pathogen overgrowth *in vivo*. Selective effect was also observed when bile salts were added to growth media and these were inoculated with caecal contents of adult hens. Such supplementation has led to a positive selection of *Selenomonadales* (genera *Megamonas*, *Megasphaera*, *Phascolarctobacterium*, *Acidaminococcus* etc). These bacteria are therefore the most resistant to

bile salts out of all microbiota members. On the other hand, addition of polysaccharides, *e.g.* starch, cellulose or inulin, was of minimal effect on growing microbiota. We also tested selective effect of several herbs like mint, chamomile, black and green tea, coffee or cacao, and found out that addition of mint positively selected for *Megamonas funiformis* and *Megamonas hypermegale*. However, black tea selected only for *Megamonas funiformis*. Addition of coffee or cacao to nutrient broths supported the growth of Gram negative isolates from genera *Bacteroides* and *Parabacteroides*. These results are now being used for the designing of growth strategies to positively select for bacterial species which are common microbiota members. Besides, selective growth conditions needs to have tools for identification of growing colonies. To have such tools available, partner 8 performed shotgun metagenomic sequencing in 10 samples originating from washes (bacterial pools) from selective agars. Using this approach, they obtained partial genomic sequences from unavailable bacterial species belonging to genera *Sutterella*, *Phacolarctobacterium*, *Acidaminococcus*, *Dialister* or *Prevotella*. These sequences have been used for the designing of primers specific for target species and are now being positively selected and identified among growing colonies.

To measure the effect of nutraceuticals, Partner 16 (VISAVET-UCM) has finished the previous studies in hens with “alperujo”. In this experiment, two groups were defined (control and treated), having tested several percentages of inclusion in the diet. Production parameters were analyzed from 12 samplings performed between week 2 and week 90 of life. No abnormal visual signs were observed in any of the animals tested, without any signs of rejection to the food even in higher inclusion percentages. Very slight variations of weights were observed between the animals. However, considering the average of the weighing, a higher value was obtained in the animals treated compared with the animals of the control group. During the experiment, the treated batch presented a higher percentage of eggs production and lower feed consumption per bird that has resulted in an increase of 1.3% of the profit of sale of eggs and a decrease of 1.7% in the cost of the feed consumed, comparing with the control one. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the distribution and percentage of eggs that were eliminated (broken or cracked) have been observed. These results indicate that the “alperujo” provided an improvement of the intestinal health, since it influences not only the digestibility of nutrients, but also the composition of the shell and quality of the eggs, reducing the loss due to broken or cracked eggs. Macroscopic measurements of various portions of the digestive tract of the animals showed that in the treated animals there was a greater number of intestinal villi at the level of the small intestine, having a higher height. The depth of the intestinal crypts of the anterior portion of the digestive tract and of the caecal mucosa was higher in the treated animals than in the control one. In the large intestine, the number of crypts observed per visual field is superior in the control animals; however, depth of crypts was higher in the treated animals.

Fig1: duodenum treated animal; figure 2: duodenum animal control; figure 3: caecum treated animal; figure 4: caecum control animal)

A metagenomic study performed in a selection of samples showing differences shows statistically significant differences in diversity for the groups tested (1, 2 and 6%) compared with control group (figure 2).

Figure 2: 16S rDNA sequencing of gut microbiota after nutraceutical treatment.

A resistome study was achieved in the same selection of samples showing differences between the proportion of resistance to different antimicrobial classes in each of the groups tested (1, 2 and 6%) (figure 3).

The experimental test with broilers which should be carried out by partner 16 has been delayed due to the availability of BSL3 boxes and authorization by the Community of Madrid to use experimental animals in projects (RD 53/2013). This study will be performed at the beginning of February. The animals after a week of adaptation and 42 days of feeding with nutraceutical, will be challenged with a strain of avian *Salmonella*. The objective of these approaches will be to analyze the modification of the microbiota before and after the challenging, comparing treated and control groups. At this time, Partner 16 is also collecting data from a pig farm and a fishery whose animals are being fed with these nutraceuticals.

Partner 22 (Univ. of Surrey), have been identified two *Lactobacillus* poultry probiotics for use in chickens (JRP10-WP2-T1), along with a prebiotic (GOS). Pig probiotics are currently being assessed and two candidates are expected to be identified and fully characterized by end April 2019. Prebiotic (GOS) for the pig studies will be provided by a commercial company. Partner 22 is currently in contact with Dr Hristo Daskalov, (partner 6, Bulgarian Food Safety Agency) in order to carry out *in vivo* studies in both chickens and pigs to assess the effectiveness of the pre and probiotics in a farm setting.

JRP10-WP2-T3: Use of pre-biotics in human travelers to high-risk areas for contracting salmonellosis and AMR

Due to the departure of Astrid Louise Wester, from the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), this task has been deleted in the new version submitted in month 6 and approved by the EJP Board.

10.2.4. WP3. Modelling the transmission of zoonotic agents to improve intervention strategies on livestock farms

JRP10-WP3-T1: Transmission modelling at within-host and between-host scales

JRP10-WP3-T1-ST1: Within-host scale: modelling individual responses and shedding

A first set of data analyses is ongoing and aims to link gut microbiota composition and immune response parameters to shedding status; this is at first based on existing data on chicken (with P18-Tours and P8). A second set of analyses consists in inferring interactions between the pathogen (here *Salmonella*) and the resident microbiota, based on time series of gut microbiota composition.

A generic mathematical model of the dynamic interplay between the gut microbiota, the pathogen and the host's immune response has been formulated. Part of this work was done through a work session at the CEMRACS 2018 summer school in Marseille. This model has been extended to the between-host scale.

JRP10-WP3-T1-ST2: Between-host scale: modelling transmission, linked to within-host results

Extended to the between-host scale, the generic mathematical model described above serves as a first model at both the within- and between-host scales. The model is used to explore biological scenarios that contain between-animal heterogeneity in the pathogen concentration in the gut. An experiment studying the indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* between broilers has been performed in the experimental animal facilities of Wageningen Bioveterinary Research. This experiment serves to validate and refine a first model for transmission of bacteria between spatially separated animals, and to do so consisted of three different spatial setups that were each studied in two repeat animal rooms. A PhD student has been selected from international applicants and was appointed on 1 August 2018. This PhD student is currently carrying out modelling analyses of the outcomes of this experiment using different versions of the first model. Experimental results obtained by Partner 18 on heterogeneous *Salmonella* shedding have been detailed to this WP by Partner 18 and data are being exchanged.

JRP10-WP3-T2: Interventions strategies: Identification and evaluation tools

JRP10-WP3-T2-ST1: Systematic inventory of relevant intervention measures

The research for this sub-task has been started during the summer of 2018, through involving an MSc student in literature studies of relevant intervention measures and/or risk factors in poultry. The task is due to be completed in January/February 2019 when the thesis period for the MSc student terminates. In addition to literature, expert opinion is being sought.

JRP10-WP3-T2-ST2: Inclusion of potential interventions into the modelling

The models are formulated to be able to incorporate specific potential interventions; this incorporation is planned at a later stage.

JRP10-WP3-T2-ST3: Development of economic analysis tools

The approach for developing the economic analysis tools has been worked out in the past months. It will be building on previous modelling by Van Wagenberg et al, which assesses the livestock production- level intervention costs, directed at Campylobacter control in broilers, made per human DALY gained for a set of six different countries. For reasons of better availability of research capacity in 2019, the further development of the economic analysis tools will take place in the second year of the project.

10.2.5. WP4: Communication and Dissemination for Impact

JRP10-WP4-T1: Dissemination of data within the project and management of data

The impact of this task is described later in the document

JRP10-WP4-T2: Dissemination of data outside the project and management of data

The impact of this task is described later in the document

10.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

10.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-0.1	Project initiation, Kick off meeting, Project-planning and management documentation	2	2		
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-0.2	Approved and signed Consortium Agreement	6	1		This has been done at the EJP level
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-0.3	Minutes of project meetings (Kick off meeting)	2	2		
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-1.1	Panel of immunological markers to assess in pig and chicken	3	6		Each partner has defined its markers. A general discussion will be done to harmonize these markers
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-1.02	Identification of risk factors for shedding of Salmonella in pigs and poultry farms	12		16	The task is delayed due to difficulties to obtain all necessary permissions to use personal and health related data
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-1.03	Identification and purification of commensal bacteria present before <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in low shedders (first round)	12	12		
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-2.01	In vitro effect of already characterized probiotics on Salmonella growth and cell invasion	10		18	Some experiments have been delayed due to the modification of the partners. The recovery of Salmonella strains required for this task has been thus delayed
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-2.02	Description of the microbiome and resistome in farms	12		18	NDRVMI has supplant Vet-DTU at month 6 of the projet.
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-4.1	Development and production of MoMIR-PPC website	4	12		We use the OHEJP Website
MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-4.2	Data management policy and strategies	4		14	Partly done.

MoMIR-PPC	D-JRP10-4.3	Creation of a database of each animal group included in the study (age, conformation, diet, clinical status, previous antibiotic treatments, infectious status, etc.)	2	12		The database cannot be uploaded on the website that hampered us to diffuse quickly this information
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10.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-1	Organization of the consortium kick off meeting	1	y		
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-2	Protocols and ethical committee requests for the different experiments	1	y		The ethical clearance from the Norwegian Committee for Medical and Health Ethics has been received for the human part of the MoMir-PCC project (granted 15.05.2018). Additional ethical approval has been sought and granted (22.11.2018); based on this approval for use of data from the Norwegian Surveillance System for Infectious Diseases (MSIS) has been granted (05.12.2018).
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-3	Update of the members of the steering committee and of the leader and deputy leader for the WPs and tasks	2	y		Discussions with NDRVMI, which has join the consortium
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-4	Define the panel of probiotics for use in pigs and chickens	2	y		Currently on going, expected to be completed April 2019.
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-5	Define the panel of pre-biotics and feed for use in pigs, chickens	2	y		Prebiotics for use in chickens and pigs have already been identified by UoS and VRI and will be shipped to partners carrying out <i>in vivo</i> studies as requested.
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-6	Identification and selection of farms	4	y		

MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-7	Recovery of samples from the first round of experimentally infected animals	8	N	14	Some experiments have been delayed due to the modification of the partners
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-8	Four sets of NGS derived 105 mimotope sequences – positively and negatively enriched in IgM and IgA	8	N		Resulting from the left of SAIM (A. Pashov), this task has been deleted in the new version of the project. Part of this task has been performed by partner 18 (INRA)
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-9	Recovery of samples from experimentally infected animals and from farms, pretreated with pre-biotics or neutraceuticals	8	N	14	Pig experiments have been performed but chicken experiments have been delayed due to availability of BSL3 boxers
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-10	In vitro infection of cell lines and organoids with the <i>Salmonella strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (from the first experiments)</i>	10		18	Some experiments have been delayed due to the modification of the partners. The recovery of Salmonella strains required for this task has been thus delayed
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-11	Selective cultivation of commensal bacteria correlated to low shedding in pig and/ or chicken	10	Y(12)		
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-12	Comparison of immune response of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs	11		14	
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-13	Comparison of microbiota composition of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs.	11		16	Done for chicken. Three experimental pig infection studies are planned (in ISS, IZLER and ANSES). Two are currently underway and the second will be carried out in 2019. All fecal samples from these studies will be shipped to UoS for 16S community analysis.
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-14	Histological characterization of different intestinal lesions between high and low shedder in	12	Y(12)		

		chickens and pigs. Immunohistochemical studies on intestinal mucosa.				
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-15	Comparison of the predictive markers obtained in pigs with those obtained in chickens.	12	N	16	Pig experiments have been delayed
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-16	Comparison of the transcriptomic immune response induced <i>in vitro</i> between different strains to identify immunological markers	12	N	18	Some experiments have been delayed due to the modification of the partners. The recovery of Salmonella strains required for this task has been thus delayed
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-17	Recruitment of the first three sets of human participants including stool sampling and Salmonella culture	12	N	18	Recruitment and sampling of the human subjects was delayed. It is predicted to start 01.01.2019. In addition, the sampling protocol has been changed to continuous recruitment and sampling of subjects.
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-18	First version of within-host models completed	12	Y(12)		
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-19	First version of between-host models completed	12	Y(12)		
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-20	First inventory of intervention measures completed	12	N	14	Due to be completed in January/February 2019 due to timing of thesis period for MSc student
MoMIR-PPC	M-JRP10-21	First version of economic analysis tools completed	12	N		New planning due to better availability of research capacity in 2019

10.4. Publications and patents

- Moreno MA., Florez-Cuadrado D., Ugarte-Ruiz M. and Dominguez L. *Veterinarios y antibióticos: destinados a entenderse. Profesión Veterinaria*. ISBN: 2253-7244. 2018.
- Florez-Cuadrado D., Moreno MA., Ugarte-Ruiz M. and Dominguez L. Antimicrobial Resistance in the Food Chain in the European Union. *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research*. Elsevier, 2018.
- Menanteau P, Kempf F, Trotereau J, Virlogeux-Payant I, Guitton E, Dalifard J, Gabriel I, Rychlik I, and Velge P. Role of systemic infection, cross contaminations and super-shedders in *Salmonella* carrier state in chicken. *Environmental Microbiology*. DOI : 10.1111/1462-2920.14294 (open access)

10.5. Impact & relevance

The research performed in this project will better define the super-shedder concept, which has great consequences for livestock health and welfare, and control measures. Although this proposal focusses on reducing levels of *Salmonella* infections in poultry and pigs, it has implications for the other farm animals and thus huge implications for reducing zoonotic spread to humans. This project will be specifically tailored to suit a range of different resources and development stages, which necessitates participation of partners from European regions. Below, we highlight that the results obtained will account not only for these different needs, but also those of stakeholders (particularly EFSA) in order to produce European strategies that can be of value to all member states.

There is long term potential for economic and public health gains from applying these technologies or products for the European companies by supplying the pre- and probiotics identified in this project as well as the mathematical models able to measure their impact at the farm level. The predictive biomarkers identified with animals could be tested in humans. Similarly, the conditions of the *Salmonella* chronic stage in humans will help to understand the animal carrier state.

This project will have impact on farm and food sectors. The cost of veterinary and agricultural services was €24 billion in 2017 for Europe. The EU has more than 40,000 poultry farms, producing 13.1 million tons in 2014. It is the world's 4th largest producer of broiler meat and the second largest egg producer (>11 million tons, 2014). The European industry employs 302,000 staff across Europe with an annual turnover of €30 billion. Salmonellosis, campylobacteriosis and avian colibacillosis are considered the main bacterial infections in the poultry sector having an important economic impact worldwide. For these infections the super-shedder phenotype has been observed. Moreover, there are approximately 2 million pig farms in the EU which produced 257 million pigs in 2017 and 23.4 million tonnes of pork meat in 2016. Salmonellosis in pigs is considered as a major issue. Infectious disease is thought to lead to <10% of value in losses through death, loss of productivity, cost of chemotherapeutics, disinfectants etc. The economic costs of enteric infections arise for mortality, loss of production and chemotherapy. The impact on welfare and economic loss of reduced infection and increased treatability of bacterial infections to chemotherapy would be substantial.

The methods proposed here will provide a comprehensive approach to reduce infections caused by enteric pathogens. The use of pre- and probiotic preparations should reduce the incidence of enteric infections in young poultry and pigs, and reduce carriage of *Salmonella* in poultry and pigs, which have huge consequences for human health. Livestock disease imposes, indeed, a considerable burden on public health with extrapolations from UK figures suggesting this to be €582 million p.a. in Europe. Our work on persistence of *Salmonella* in humans will contribute to understand the contributing factors of this persistence and thus will allow development of new control measures

Optimum and rapid utilisation of project results and innovations by all stakeholders requires an effective dissemination strategy that provides information in formats and through dissemination channels suited to each stakeholder group. We will use especially all the tools, which will be developed by the EJP OneHealth. Moreover, fundamental scientific results will be freely disseminated through scientific publications, presentations at international conferences and workshops. Partners have agreed to release this information without any delay.

For all other results or products, partners will actively seek to protect all exploitable knowledge to favour future exploitation. Different protection and exploitation strategies adapted to the nature of the results will be used, including patents for pro and prebiotics and predictive indicators.

10.6. *Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors*

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
The applicants must confirm that animal samples used have been collected with the appropriate ethical approvals (approval letters, etc) so complying with EU standards.	All animal experiments have been approved by appropriate ethical committee before manipulations. The time necessary to obtain this approval delayed some experiments.
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the conduct of the clinical study have been sought.	No clinical study will be undertaken, as described in the changed project description approved December 2017.
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of biological samples have been sought.	For the human part, the ethical clearance from the Norwegian Committee for Medical and Health Ethics has been granted 15.05.2018, and updated 22.11.2018.
More detailed information must be provided on the recruitment procedure of the study participants.	All persons living in Norway diagnosed with Salmonella during the sampling period (now 01.01.2019 – 31.08.2020) will be contacted by the Norwegian Surveillance System for Infectious Diseases (MSIS). MSIS will send an information letter about the study as well as consent forms. If the persons (or both guardians, in case of children) give their consent, then FHI will send them a self-sampling kit, a questionnaire and pre-paid return envelope.
The applicants must confirm that an insurance policy has been established to cover the study participants.	No insurance policy is needed, as the health risk of taking a stool sample with a self-testing kit is considered minimal.

The applicants must confirm the compliance with GDPR.	Data collection and treatment is in compliance with GDPR.
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10.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Y
Delay in work plan execution	Y
Conflicts within the consortium	N
Lack of commitment of partners	N
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Y
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	N
Potential entry/exit of partners	Y
Other risks (please describe)	N

Additional information: We already managed the loss of partners, person by the entry of a new partner (NDRVMI), which has induced delay in work plan execution and delay in several tasks.

10.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

1- CEMRACS 2018 summer school in Marseille, session/project entitled 'A multi-scale epidemic model of Salmonella infection with heterogeneous shedding'. <http://smi.emath.fr/cemracs/cemracs18/projects.php>

2- Interaction of partners 8 (VRI) and 18 (INRA) with the Aniwha "AWAP" project concerning the influence of gut microbiota composition and *Salmonella* infection on chicken behavior.

10.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	CIAG Prévenir et guérir les maladies infectieuses dans le concept One Health. « L'approche microbiote : Stratégies pour prédire et prévenir les infections à <i>Salmonella</i> chez le poulet »		
Date:	21 June 2018		
Place:	Tours, France		
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	X	Media	X
Industry	X	Investors	X
Civil Society	X	Customers	
General Public	X	Other	
Policy Makers	X	Approximately Total number of people	100

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	Animal Microbiome congress « Faecal gut microbiota composition of chicks can predict the super-shedder phenotype of <i>Salmonella</i> Enteritidis”		
<i>Date:</i>	20-21 June 2018		
<i>Place:</i>	Paris, France		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	X	<i>Media</i>	X
<i>Industry</i>	X	<i>Investors</i>	X
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	X
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>		<i>Approximately Total number of people</i>	100

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	IV VETINDOC PhDay, <i>Facultad de Veterinaria</i> . - Poster communication. (<i>Identificación y caracterización de bacterias resistentes a la colistina. Evaluación de su persistencia y posible diseminación</i>)		
<i>Date:</i>	27/06/2018		
<i>Place:</i>	Universidad Complutense, Spain, Madrid.		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	YES
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other : Poster</i>	Yes
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	50	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	XXII Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica, Sociedad Española de Enfermedades Infecciosas – Oral communication. (Nuevos determinantes de la resistencia a la colistina en <i>Escherichia coli</i> de origen animal)		
<i>Date:</i>	24/05/2018		
<i>Place:</i>	y Microbiología Clínica, Spain, Bilbao		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other : oral communication</i>	YES
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	100	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	20	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>	10	<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases – Poster communication. (Whole genome sequencing analysis of <i>Salmonella enterica</i> serotype Choleraesuis isolates in Spain provides insight into possible transmission chains)		
<i>Date:</i>	22/04/2018		
<i>Place:</i>	Madrid (Spain)		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other : POSTER</i>	YES
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	200	<i>Media</i>	5
<i>Industry</i>	50	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>	10	<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>	20	<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>	20		

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	Congrès Mbio : Les microbiotes et la santé humaine, animale et environnementale : Prévention et traitements du futur - poster presentation (Les niveaux d'excrétion de Salmonella sont liés à la composition du microbiota intestinal chez le Poulet.)		
<i>Date:</i>	19 - 20 June 2018		
<i>Place:</i>	Biocitech, Cité des entreprises de santé et de biotechnologies, Romainville		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other : Poster</i>	YES
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	X	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	X	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>		<i>Approximately Total number of people</i>	200

<i>Name of the activity:</i>	Velge, P., Kempf, F., Menanteau, P., Beaumont, C., Leterrier, C., Virlogeux-Payant, I. (2018). L'approche microbiote : stratégies pour prédire et prévenir les infections à <i>Salmonella</i> chez le poulet. In: Prévenir et guérir les maladies infectieuses dans le concept One Health (p. 37-47). <i>Innovations Agronomiques</i> , 66.		
<i>Date:</i>	2018		
<i>Place:</i>	<i>Innovations Agronomiques</i> , 66.		
<i>Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	YES	<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	X	<i>Media</i>	X
<i>Industry</i>	X	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>		<i>Approximately Total number of people</i>	100

Name of the activity:	International symposium <i>Salmonella</i> and salmonellosis - oral communication (<i>Salmonella</i> shedding levels are related to the chicken gut microbiota composition)		
Date:	24-26 September 2018		
Place:	Saint-Malo, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	X	Media	
Industry	X	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers		Approximately Total number of people	250

10.10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

Informal face to face meetings were (or will be) arranged during the EJP meetings (June 2018) ; the international congresses like “Salmonella, salmonellosis international symposium (Sept 2018) ; the CEMRACS 2018 summer school in Marseille (July-August 2018) etc. Numerous email exchanges and video conferences are planned between partners for scientific and technical exchanges but also to plane common experiments.

The midterm MoMIR-PPC meeting is planned the 8th February 2019 in Spain.

11. MedVetKlebs

11.1. Summary of the work carried out

One of the first and main goals of MedVetKlebs project is the development and harmonization of detection, isolation and quantification methods of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*Kp*) from different sources. For this purpose, we have tried culture, proteomics and molecular approaches. Regarding the culture approach, the productivity and specificity of the selective SCAI medium was tested in comparison with other selective and differential media (*Klebsiella* Selective ChromoSelect Agar Base from Sigma and other not yet commercialized from Liofilchem). Based on the experiments, SCAI showed similar recovery rates but higher specificity, being easy to prepare and to identify *Kp* colonies from. After the establishment of SCAI as the most suitable medium for *Kp* detection and isolation, we focused our efforts in the design of protocols for the detection and isolation of *Kp* using SCAI according to the different sources. In this context, 3 different protocols with different enrichments conditions and incubation temperatures have been optimized, one for fecal samples from humans and animals, other for food products and the last one for environmental samples (soil).

Regarding the proteomics approach, we demonstrated for the first time the potential of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry, a fast and cost-effective technique that is well established in routine laboratories for microbial identification, to correctly identify strains of the *K. pneumoniae* complex at the phylogroup level. This approach was validated with an external dataset and the corresponding article has been already published in *Frontiers in Microbiology* (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2018: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000>). This represents an important advancement for fast and simple identification of *K. pneumoniae*.

Regarding molecular approaches, we developed a real-time PCR for the identification and quantification of the *Kp* complex and the different phylogroups (or species) directly in the samples in order to allow a more efficient broad sampling. Two partners were involved in this task (IP, INRA). For this purpose, a pan-genome strategy was applied to a collection of reference genomes. Candidate genes exclusive to the different phylogroups were obtained, which were filtered based on BLAST results and GC content, reducing the number of target candidates. These candidates were mapped in a large collection of genomes ($n=1001$), leading to define seven optimal specific target genes. qPCR primers/probes were designed and validated on a reference panel of strains. The qPCR protocol (zKir qPCR) for the detection of bacteria belonging to *Kp* complex by specific amplification of an intergenic sequence of 78 bp between *zur* (zinc uptake regulation protein) and *khe* (annotated as coding for a haemolysin) was distributed to all the partners and the publication is being prepared. The sensitivity of this qPCR was tested on spiked soil in INRA Dijon during 6 consecutive months, and it will be also tested on other matrices by the different MedVetKlebs partners. In addition, the qPCR strategy for the identification of the different *Kp* phylogroups is also being optimized by developing a multiplex qPCR.

Regarding broad sampling (WP2), this task has started a few months ago and will involve all partners.

11.2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

11.2.1. WP1. Methods for *Kp* detection and isolation

JRP11-WP1-T1: Evaluation and optimization of culture-based approaches

Productivity and specificity tests – two partners were involved in this task (IP, IZSAM). The tests were performed in accordance with the ISO 11133:2014 and using a collection of 57 reference panel of strains from our IP internal

collection, that included members from the *K. pneumoniae* complex and also other related species (*K. oxytoca*, *Raoultella* spp., *K. aerogenes*). Three different media - SCAI, *Klebsiella* Selective ChromoSelect Agar Base from Sigma and other not yet commercialized from Liofilchem - were compared with a non-selective agar media. The results showed similar recovery rates (productivity) for the three different media tested but higher specificity for SCAI compared to the other selective and differential media tested. In addition, SCAI appeared easy to prepare and to identify *Klebsiella* colonies from. Furthermore, productivity tests with SCAI at two different incubation temperatures (37°C and 44°C) were also performed. This was done because at 44°C, we detect less interferences of other species besides *Klebsiella* spp., and we wanted to be sure that all *K. pneumoniae* complex members are able to growth at 44°C. Our results revealed similar productivity rates in SCAI at both temperatures.

Isolation tests from different sources - After the establishment of SCAI as the most suitable medium for *K. pneumoniae* detection and isolation, we designed 3 protocols for the detection and isolation of *K. pneumoniae* using SCAI according to the different sources (human and animal fecal carriage; food; environment). Seven partners were involved in this task (AGES, ANSES, IP, IZSAM, INRA, SSI, NUIG). In the case of human and animal fecal carriage, the protocol established includes an enrichment step in Luria-Bertani (LB) broth plus ampicillin (10 µg/mL) at 37°C/overnight and then plating 100 µL of the enrichment in SCAI plates (37°C/48h). The protocol for environmental sources, which was optimized using soil samples, is the same described for human and animal fecal carriage with the only difference being the incubation temperature in the enrichment step (28-30°C instead of 37°C). In the case of food samples, the protocol was optimized using chicken meat samples (legs and chest with and without skin from free-range and not free-range chickens). The best strategy achieved includes an enrichment in buffer peptone water and then plating 10 µL of the enrichment in SCAI (44°C/48h). In the three protocols, all typical *Klebsiella* spp. colonies (large, yellow, moist colonies) were taken and identified using MALDI-TOF MS.

JRP11-WP1-T2: Detection and quantification

MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry – *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp1), one of the major drivers of antibiotic resistance worldwide, is phylogenetically closely related to *K. quasipneumoniae* [subsp. *quasipneumoniae* (Kp2) and subsp. *similipneumoniae* (Kp4)], *K. variicola* (Kp3) and two novel taxa (arbitrarily designed Kp5 and Kp6), together forming the *K. pneumoniae* complex. Currently, the phylogroups within the complex can only be correctly identified by whole-genome sequencing (WGS) or by sequencing of specific genetic markers. However, such methods, can be expensive and laborious, not being available for all the microbiology routine laboratories, resulting in misidentifications that mask the epidemiological contribution of each of the species. In this context, our goal was to evaluate and validate the potential of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry, a fast and cost-effective technique well established in routine for microbial identification, to discriminate *K. pneumoniae* complex members using a collection of reference strains from the six *K. pneumoniae* phylogroups. Mass spectra obtained from the cell extracts of 46 isolates (10 Kp1, 9 Kp2, 9 Kp3, 7 Kp4, 6 Kp5 and 5 Kp6), previously characterized by WGS or by sequencing of specific genetic markers, were acquired on a Microflex LT mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, Germany). Spectra were pre-processed using the FlexAnalysis software applying the “smoothing” and “baseline subtraction” procedures and subsequently analyzed using BioNumerics v7.6 (Applied Maths, Belgium). Our results revealed, for the first time, the existence of mass spectrometry biomarkers associated with each of the phylogroups tested, with a sensitivity and specificity ranging from 80-100% and 97-100%, respectively. Whereas Kp1, Kp2 and Kp4 each presented two specific peaks, Kp3 and Kp6 presented only one specific peak that was also common to Kp5 and Kp1, respectively, and could only be identified by exclusion criteria. Our MALDI-TOF MS based model was successfully validated using a test collection of 49 isolates belonging to the *K. pneumoniae* complex, with spectra obtained from different culture media and extraction procedures. Our results demonstrate the potential of MALDI-TOF MS for precise identification of *K. pneumoniae* complex members. Reference spectra databases should be updated in order to test and implement the approach in microbiology laboratories. This

would represent an important advance for fast and simple identification of *K. pneumoniae* and related species, opening the way to a better understanding of their epidemiology, ecology and pathogenesis. These results have been published (Rodrigues *et al.* 2018 Frontiers Microbiol: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000>). While the reference spectra databases are not updated within the MALDI-ToF commercial databases, we will diffuse our spectral model for the identification of *K. pneumoniae* complex members within the MedVetKlebs consortium and beyond.

qPCR - we developed a real-time PCR for the identification and quantification of the *K. pneumoniae* complex and the different phylogroups (or species) directly in the samples in order to allow a more efficient broad sampling. Two partners were involved in this task (IP, INRA). The targets for the qPCR were chosen based on a pan-genome strategy applied to a collection of reference genomes (n=66). Candidate genes exclusive for the different phylogroups were obtained, which were filtered based on BLAST results and G+C content, reducing the number of target candidates. These candidates were mapped in a large collection of genomes (n=1001), leading to define seven optimal specific target genes.

qPCR primers/probes were designed and successfully tested on a reference panel of strains (n=67) from our IP internal collection and using as positive control the *K. pneumoniae* ATCC 700603. The qPCR protocol (zkir qPCR) for the detection of bacteria belonging to *K. pneumoniae* complex is based on the specific amplification of an intergenic sequence of 78 bp between *zur* (zinc uptake regulation protein) and *khe* (annotated as coding for a haemolysin) using a SYBR green strategy. The protocol was already distributed to all the partners and the publication is being prepared. The sensitivity of this qPCR was tested on spiked soil in INRA (Dijon) during 6 consecutive months, and it will be also tested on other matrices by the different MedVetKlebs partners. In addition, the qPCR strategy for the identification of the different *K. pneumoniae* phylogroups is also being optimized by developing a multiplex qPCR.

JRP11-WP1-T3: Harmonization and alignment

Enrichment/selective procedures were optimized by different partners of the project and the optimized protocols were distributed to all the partners.

11.2.2. WP2. Sampling

JRP11-WP2-T1: Broad sampling of potential reservoirs and sources of Kp

Regarding the broad sampling, this task has started recently in a large-scale, once optimization of isolation and detection protocols were defined. A broad set of samples has already been tested by the partners using the SCAI medium, showing recovery of *K. pneumoniae* from large number of sources. Most sampling has focused on food items so far, and one sub-study investigates pet and human carriage within single households. More sampling will be scheduled early 2019 after discussions during the one-year meeting.

11.2.3. WP3. Genomics and Modeling

JRP11-WP3-T2: Modeling and source attribution

Will depend on WP2 first – therefore not started yet, although the strategy to follow was already discussed.

11.2.4. WP4: Management, dissemination, exploitation

JRP11-WP4-T1: Implementation of the project management structure

As planned.

JRP11-WP4-T2: Administrative, legal, financial and ethical support to the consortium

As planned.

JRP11-WP4-T3: Exploitation of results and Intellectual Property rights management

The identification *Klebsiella pneumoniae* complex members using MALDI-TOF MS was published on Frontiers in Microbiology (Rodrigues *et. al* 2018: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000>)

11.3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

11.3.1. Deliverables

JRP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-1.1	Optimized culture protocols	12	OCTOBER 2018		Productivity and specificity of SCAI medium tested. Best enrichment steps and incubation temperatures defined according to the different sources. Protocols distributed across MedVetKlebs partners.
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-1.2	qPCR protocols	12	NOVEMBER 2018		qPCR for the identification of Kp complex members designed and validated. Protocol distributed across MedVetKlebs partners.
MedVetKlebs	Additional	MALDI-TOF MS	12	DECEMBER 2018		Demonstration and validation of the potential of MALDI-TOF MS to correctly identify strains of the <i>K. pneumoniae</i> complex at the phylogroup level. Article published.
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-2.1	List of high-Kp occurrence sources	12	NO	FEBRUARY-MARCH 2019	This task has started recently in a large-scale, once optimization of isolation and detection protocols were defined.
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.1	Project Periodic Reports	12	DECEMBER 2018		-
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.3	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	1	18 SEPTEMBER 2018		TC with 5 partners (AGES, NUIG, INRA, ISZAM, SSI) 2 hours
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.3	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	1	17 OCTOBER 2018		TC with 5 partners (AGES, NUIG, INRA, ISZAM, SSI) 2 hours
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.3	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	1	11-12 JANUARY 2018		Kick-off meeting, Paris, two days
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.4	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	12	29 MAY 2018		TC with all partners, 2 hours
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.4	Consortium meetings – Review of work done/progress made and definition of priorities for next period	12	11-12 JANUARY 2019		This date is more suitable for all the partners than the end of December.
MedVetKlebs	D-JRP11-4.6	Communication strategy plan	12	NO	JANUARY 2019	We are working on it.

11.3.2. Milestones

JRP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-1	SCAI medium culture protocol validated on sites	3	YES		Best enrichment steps and incubation temperatures defined according to the different sources. Protocols distributed across MedVetKlebs partners.
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-2	Preparation of draft of the strategic communication plan	10	NO	JANUARY 2019	We are working on it.
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-3	Project reporting template	10	YES		
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-4	Standard culture methods defined	12	YES		Productivity and specificity of SCAI medium tested. Best enrichment steps and incubation temperatures defined according to the different sources. Protocols distributed across MedVetKlebs partners.
MedVetKlebs	Additional	MALDI-TOF MS	12	YES		Demonstration and validation of the potential of MALDI-TOF MS to correctly identify strains of the <i>K. pneumoniae</i> complex at the phylogroup level. Article published.
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-5	qPCR protocol available for quantification	12	YES		qPCR for the identification of Kp complex members designed and validated. Protocol distributed across MedVetKlebs partners.
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-6	Broad survey of Kp in multiple sources complete	12	NO	FEBRUARY-MARCH 2019	This task has started recently in a large-scale, once optimization of isolation and detection protocols were defined.
MedVetKlebs	M-JRP11-7	Development of model frameworks for dynamic modelling and source attribution	12	NO	APRIL 2019	Will depend on WP2 first – therefore not started yet, although the strategy to follow was already discussed.

11.4. Publications and patents

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Brisse S (2018). Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and related phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry. *Front. Microbiol.* 9:3000. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Brisse S. Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and related phylogroups by MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. In 14th National Congress of French Society of Microbiology (SFM), 01-03 October 2018, Paris, France.

11.5. Impact & relevance

The main ambition of our MedVetKlebs is, by using an integrated population biology and epidemiological approach, to bring *K. pneumoniae* ecology from a neglected status to solid baseline knowledge, and to develop innovative tools enabling risk managers to act efficiently on an outbreak of *K. pneumoniae* infections. Within this framework, one of our first goals was to design efficient strategies for the detection and isolation of *K. pneumoniae* in complex sources and deliver harmonized procedures by defining and disseminating standard and validated procedures. Different culturomic, proteomic and molecular approaches have been developed and validated. From this work different protocols have been obtained and distributed across our partners (or published) in order to facilitate the next steps of our project - probe the occurrence of *Kp* in a broad range of samples and define the potential role of multiple foods as sources of *Kp* infection in humans and animals, that will contribute to explore the gap between Med and Vet in the case of *K. pneumoniae* species. The use of a unified methodology will generate, for the first time, comparable data that will allow identifying major sources of exposure to *K. pneumoniae*.

11.6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements	Measures and actions taken
	"This study received ethics approval from the Medical Research Ethics Committee of Utrecht University (WAG/om/14/012490). Informed consent was obtained from all participants. All participants gave consent and in the case of children, parents gave consent."
The applicants must confirm that ethics approvals for the use of isolates from human origin have been sought	"This study received ethics approval from the Medical Research Ethics Committee of Utrecht University (WAG/om/14/012490). Informed consent was obtained from all participants. All

	participants gave consent and in the case of children, parents gave consent.”
Isolates of Human Origin are used therefore resubmit the Ethics Checklist based on the requirements noted above	See above

11.7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	No
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information: Nothing to declare.

11.8. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project
none

11.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	14 th National Congress of the French Society of Microbiology (SFM)		
Date:	01-03 October 2018		
Place:	Cité des Sciences et de l'industrie		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (poster)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500	Media	
Industry	13 companies	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

11.10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

We have planned a face-to-face meeting in 10-11th January 2019 at Institut Pasteur (Paris, France) with all the MedVetKlebs partners, and also some invited researchers with expertise in the field of *K. pneumoniae*. WP3 leaders are welcome! (Arnaud Callegari will participate as far as we are informed as of today, 19th December 2018).